

CLASS STRUGGLE IN YORÙBÁ HISTORICAL AND
PROTEST PLAYS

BY

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A Thesis in the
DEPARTMENT OF LINGUISTICS AND AFRICAN LANGUAGES

Submitted to the Faculty of Arts
in partial fulfilment of the requirements
for the Degree of

DOCTOR OF PHILOSOPHY
of the
UNIVERSITY OF IBADAN
IBADAN - NIGERIA

MARCH, 1997

DEDICATION

This work is dedicated to my Late father:

PRINCE EMMANUEL JÍMÒ ARÓHUNMÓLÀŞE, (21 January, 1960)

the architect of my education, and my Late Son:

OLÚWASÈYÌÍ ADÉBÒWÁLÉ AKÍNBOĐÉ ARÓHUNMÓLÀŞE (12 February, 1995)

Ọmọ Àbú Olódodo

Ọmọ Inúnbáyé

Ọmọ Aşèlú-jígíjígí

Aróhunmólàşe a-ji-ka-sílè-bí-ẹni-ń-kawó-eyọ

Ọmọ A-kọko-má-mògbè-e-rẹ

A-níşu-má-à-lódó

A-kó-wón-sílè-tàìgbón-tàìmọ

A-ní-ńńkan-ọbẹ-jobínrin lọ

Ọmọ Ayánrán òkè ò jẹ ẹ gùn

Ọmọ Ikàkùmọ A-gbógun mọ jí.

(E sùn un re lódọ Èdùmàrè)

ABSTRACT

This study is an examination of class struggle as depicted in Yorùbá plays. By class struggle we mean the conflict between the social classes in the society. In the study an attempt is made to identify the ways in which intra-class and inter-class struggle are artistically depicted in Yorùbá plays. In addition the study aims at identifying the characteristics of Yorùbá historical and protest plays which reflect the class struggle in Yoruba society.

The general theoretical framework of the study is informed by Marxism as it relates to the sociology of literature. The views of Marxist critics on ideology and literature, commitment and class struggle are silhouetted against the back-drop of formalism and structuralism for the purpose of properly foregrounding our theoretical basis.

The data are made up of written Yorùbá plays that depict class struggle which for the purpose of this study are categorized into two: the historical and the protest plays. The historical plays essentially depict the intra-class struggle. They include Basòrun Gáà, Efunsetán Aniwurà, Líṣàbí Agbòngbò Àkàlà, Mòrèmi, Olàòré Afòtèjoyè,

Sàngó and Olú Omo. Similarly, the protest plays which include: Ìgbà Ló Dé, Réré Run, Àtārí Àjānākú, Ayé Yẹ Wón Tán and Kòseégbé are preoccupied with inter-class struggle. For the historical and the intra-class phenomenon, the emphasis is on the ideology of the ruling class. Members of the ruling class are ever in conflict with one another for individualistic ambitions at the expense of the ruled. This is the artistic presentation of the social realism in Yorùbá community. The Yorùbá protest plays by contrast, represent the struggles between the ruling class and the ruled. This in essence is the real socialist struggle. The commitment in such plays is to the freedom of the suffering masses from the oppression of the ruling class.

The plays under reference in this study tend to suggest that the masses have not exploited in full the apparent-weaknesses of the ruling class. On the other hand, the ruling class, in most cases, has been able to infiltrate the rank and file of the masses through coersive means and through the exploitation of the weaknesses of the masses to crush their struggle. It is also observed that despite the powerful thrust of the artistic vision in the plays under reference, the

playwrights seem to lack necessary awareness that could inform successful inter-class struggle in the plays. This is probably because of their lack of a socialist consciousness. Therefore this study validates the views of Marxists that bourgeois literature legitimises the ideologies of the ruling elite in a class society. By logical extension the two categories of Yorùbá plays we have identified above belong to bourgeois literature. In other words the Yorùbá playwrights seem not to have weighed the implications of a defeatist artistic vision on a society that seriously needs a drastic socio-economic and political re-generation.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I thank my Supervisor, Dr P.A. Ògúndèjí for his painstaking efforts in going through and reading the draft of this work and his friendly advice throughout this period. I also thank Dr E.O. Olúkòjú who started the work with me before he went on sabbatical leave.

I am grateful to other members of the Department of Linguistics and African Languages such as Professor Ayo Bámbóṣé, Professor Òlátúndé O. Òlátúnjí, Professor B.O. Elugbe, Professor Kúnlé Adéníran, Dr D.K.O. Owólabí and Dr Afólabí Òlábòdé who keep on asking me about my progress on this work.

I thank my employers, the National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE) and the Provost, Adéyemí College of Education, Oñdó, Professor Babátúndé Ipàyé who is so much interested in my academic pursuit and development. I am grateful to Professor E. Nolue Emenanjo, the Executive Director, National Institute for Nigerian Languages, Ogbor Hill, Aba, Abia State for my Sabbatical Leave at the Institute in 1995. This has afforded me the opportunity to concentrate on this work. Professor E. Nolue Emenanjo's encouragement on this study

is highly appreciated. I also give thanks to Professor Oládélé Awóbùlúyí for his encouragement and advice.

There are some people who had helped me in one way or the other in making this work a reality. Mr J.B. Ògèdèngbé and Mr E.O. Adéfaratì of Adéyemí College of Education, Oṅdó Library are of immense help to me in going through the archives of the library to help me find out useful materials for this study; Mr C.O. Ayòdélé, Department of History, Adéyemí College of Education, Oṅdó also released some of his useful books for this work. My thanks also go to Mr Olánipèkun Olúránkínṣé who gave me his Masters Thesis and some books on Marxism. Dr Bèwàjí Dasyilva now of the Department of English, University of Ibadan is also helpful as regards the release of some useful texts for this study. I cannot but thank Messrs Sunday Adéjùbèḗ, Bóláwá Akinṣolá, Túndé Ònàdèkó and R.A. Adésuyan for their roles in reducing my work-load in the Department during the period of this study. I also thank Dr Durótoyè Adéléké and Mr 'Gòkè Àlámù for their concern for this work.

I thank my wife, Mrs Beatrice Fàtí Aróhunmólàṣe, my children, Pastor Olútáyò Olúṣolá, Kíkélomọ Olúyémísí, Adégbóyèga Olúkúnlé, Olúṣínà Oládèjì and Olúyemí Adéléyè

for their encouragements and responsibilities during the period of my study. I cannot but mention the role played by my Late son Olúwaşèyíí Adébòwálé Akinbòdé, he was with me at Aba in January 17th to February 12th 1995 when the preparatory draft of this study was concluded. I did not know that you wanted to answer God's call on Sunday, the 12th of February, 1995 when you asked if I had finished writing the draft of this work. We are always consoled by your Bible quotation - Romans 8, verse 28:

And we know that all things work together for good to them that love God, to them who are the CALLED according to his purpose.

Your last song:

I surrender all, I surrender all,
Unto You MY BLESSED SAVOUR,
I surrender all.

is a comfort to us. This work is specially dedicated to you for your role in the family, in your Church and the community. My sincere thanks go to Mr Kelim Olenloa of the Department of Linguistics and African Languages, University of Ibadan, for typing this thesis.

Finally, I thank my Good God for His protection throughout the period of my study and the period of writing this thesis.

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CERTIFICATION

I certify that this work was carried out by

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.0 Aims and Objectives

The purpose of this work is to determine the characteristic features of Yorùbá historical and protest plays in relation to the presentation of the class struggle in them. This study is interested in the relationship between Yorùbá literature particularly Yorùbá drama and society. In this respect, we limit our examination to class struggle in Yorùbá historical and protest plays. It is our contention that in any class based society with definite class interest there will be contradictions that will lead to a struggle within or between members of the class. We are concerned with the type of socialist views that these plays reveal in our examination and analysis of intra- and inter-class struggles in them.

We will examine the relevance of the playwrights visions of class struggle created through their knowledge of Yorùbá society in these plays. In doing this Marxist literary theories as they are applicable to Yorùbá society in general and the plays in particular will be our major focus in this work. We are interested in the

masses who are agents of dynamic or radical change in any society. There can only be a social change when there is an awareness created for a class struggle that may lead to a revolution in a society. For a revolution to occur in a society, the masses who are the agents of change must be educated in the laws that will facilitate a social change. The masses must also be educated about their place in a social change and their historical mission, through an expansion of their consciousness. This study is of the view that, the laws of revolutionary transformation as seen in class struggle, also give rise to opposition and strifes. The study is also interested in the leaders who mobilize the masses and those who are the leaders of the masses in their struggle. This study believes that there is a need for the literary cleansing of our society and the establishment of humanist literary criticism through the flushing out of reactionary forces and those who are opposed to social changes in Yorùbá society. This study also attempts to show that there can be a new explanation of the meaning of social change, and that a new awareness can be created in the masses by examining issues such as intra-class and inter-class struggles, ideology and commitment of the authors and

characters in Yorùbá plays.¹

The goals of Yorùbá historical and protest plays should be to bring to focus and make it unmistakably clear, the essence of the masses struggle for liberation. They should also show the masses failures and successes, their setbacks and achievements. Yorùbá playwrights should adopt a sort of unyielding or intransigent working class or masses orientation and ideology in both inter-class and intra-class struggles in their domestic, and socio-economic issues, in all their fundamental tasks of revolutionary transformation of the Yorùbá society. We will ascertain in this work how Yorùbá playwrights share the above named purposes and how they use the laws of dialectics in their knowledge from their personal experiences and the reflection of objective reality. This is because by using dialectics the Yorùbá playwrights are helped to reflect in their plays the progressive development of men, the various facets of their social development and the inevitable victory of the revolutionary masses in the social order.

1 Also examine the views of Udenta, O.U. (1993)
pp xi-xxiv.

Yorùbá revolutionary plays should be a mirror of life in Yorùbá society. The plays that are governed by the law of historical dialectics should show positive characters who cooperate with other members in their class for the improvement of their positions in the society. These plays should also show the noble qualities of the leading characters, the courage of these characters their apprehension, their frustrations, dignified visions and their efforts at making real their potentialities. As expressed by Mao (1950:66-67, 77) artists and writers of high promise must go into the mist of the masses of workers, peasants and soldiers. According to him writers and artists should go into the passionate struggle, which is the proper way to observe, learn, study and examine all men, all classes, all brilliant patterns of life and struggle: and all the raw materials of art and literature before they can go on to writing. Playwrights in Yorùbá society in our opinion must cooperate in the struggle of the Yorùbá masses for a significant national goal in Nigeria. Yorùbá playwrights must be concerned in showing the feelings in the background of the struggle in Yorùbá society. These views are comparable to those of Ngugi, Wa Thiong'O

(1975:50) when he says that:

African intellectuals must align themselves with the struggle of the African masses for a meaningful national ideal ... perhaps, in a small way, the African writer can help in articulating the feelings behind this struggle.

We are also interested in knowing through the analysis of Yorùbá historical and protest plays how Yorùbá playwrights are able to show from the dialectical perspectives the reality in some fallacious ideologies and the illusion in actuality, the relationships between the contents and the forms of social life and the forms and contents of these plays. We will examine in our analysis of Yorùbá plays how in principle these plays try to resolve issues of struggles by making a synthesis of the conflicting ideologies in dialectical ways in their known methods. A radical and humanistic sociology of Yorùbá historical and protest plays should be able to show clearly from the dialectical perspectives the reality in some ideologies. These views are succinctly expressed by Jéyifò (1985:7-8) when he says that:

... a radical sociology of drama ... must seek to discover the truth in the lie and the lie in the truth of the relationship between the content and forms of social life and the forms and content of dramatic art itself.

Yorùbá society must not be left out in our critical analysis in this work as there are some relationships between ideological and cultural views which will definitely emerge from the historical background of Yorùbá society in the pre-colonial, colonial and post-colonial periods when the masses were subdued and their desires were to free themselves from oppression.

1.1.0 Scope of this Study

In this study we will examine Yorùbá historical and protest plays which include: Dúró Ládipò: Morèmi,¹ Adébáyò Fálétí: Basòrun Gáà,² Ọládẹ̀jọ Okédíjì: Sàngó,³ Akinwùmi Ìṣòlá: Efúnsetán Aníwúrà,⁴ Olú Omo,⁵ Olú Owólábi: Lísàbí Agbòngbò Àkàlá,⁶ Afólábí Ọlábíntán: Oláòre Afòtẹ̀jọyẹ⁷ and T.A.A. Ládélé: Ìgbà Lò Dé.⁸ All the plays listed above are historical plays. Protest plays are: Ọládẹ̀jọ Okédíjì: Rẹ̀rẹ̀ Rún,⁹ Akinwùmi Ìṣòlá: Ayé Ye Wón Tán,¹⁰ Kòseégbé¹¹ and Láuuyí Ọ̀gúnńíran: Àtàrí Àjànàkú.¹²

Historical plays are the plays which emanate from historical accounts or records. These are Morèmi, Basòrun Gaa, Sàngó, Efúnsetán Aníwúra, Olú Omo, Lisàbi Agbòngbò Akàlà, Olàoré Afótèjoye and Igbà Ló Dé. They take their sources from known Yorùbá historical figures or characters and events. The literary artist is not a historian, he has changed, recorded and re-interpreted certain historical facts in line with whatever objectives he has adopted for writing. According to Lákojú:

The genre of historical drama does not place any obligation on the playwrights or dramatists to be faithful to history. Depending on his artistic and ideological purpose, the dramatist can falsify or even distort historical facts (1983:8).

Yorùbá historical playwrights are generally not faithful to historical accounts in the presentation of their plays; they falsify and distort historical facts (Ogundeji, 1991). Lákojú (1983:8) is also of the view that any interpretation of history that shys away from an analysis of the objective relationship between the classes is reactionary.

Protest plays are plays in which there are protests

against the established systems or in which there are class struggles and revolts. These are: Réré Rún, Ayé Ye Wón Tán, Kòseégbé, Àtárí Àjànàkú, Igbà Ló Dé and Lísàbí Agbòngbò Àkàlà. Our classification of some Yorùbá plays as protest plays follows Iṣòlá's (1981:405-407) classification. These protest plays are also classified by Nicoll (1949:855), Adédèjí (1983:7-8) and (Ògúndèjí (1991:1-19, 1996) as 'problem' plays. People may be saddled with problems and yet they may not protest. They may believe in the capitalist view of endurance and hope for a better future. Ògúndèjí (1991:11-19, 1996) in his discussion of plays with 'social problems' says in his analysis of Akinwúmi Iṣòlá's plays, that we can only regard Kòseégbé and Ayé Ye Wón Tán as problem plays. These two plays according to Ògúndèjí examine:

... the economic and other problems of the society.

... As expected of problem plays, the two plays are also didactic and they propose solutions to the problems. The problems are also mostly presented in the realistic rather than in the fantastic mode. These are the main features that qualify them as problem plays (Ògúndèjí 1991:15, 1996).

Whereas this view may be right and legitimate it does not agree with our own theoretical approach. We agree with Ògúndèjí's view that problem plays like protest plays examine the economic and other problems of the society. Protest plays also propose solutions to problems created in the plays. Our choice of the label protest is essentially agreeable with our theoretical approach and it does not remove the fact that there can be a class of problem plays in itself. Whereas all protest plays tend to be problem plays, not all problem plays are protest plays. Protest plays are plays that:

... decry the poor economic conditions and the political powerlessness of the working class (Iṣòlá 1987:405-407).

Protest plays are plays which depict revolts against the established systems or in which there are class struggles and revolutionary developments. Udentá explains that:

... The emergence and assertion of revolutionary aesthetics was concomitant with the appearance on the world scene of a new progressive and revolutionary social force, the working class, which is a true producer of human values. The first work of this artistic method were created in the conditions of the crisis

of capitalism, the upsurge of the proletarian class struggle and the preparation of socialist revolution (1993:9).

Though classified above as historical, it should be noted that Lisàbí Agbòngbò Àkàlá and Ìgbà Ló Dé have enough of protest in them to also include them in the category of protest plays. This means that the two plays can be seen at the same time as historical and protest in this study.

Ìgbà Ló Dé and Oláòrè Afètèjáyè are classified as historical plays in this study. Ògúnṣínà (1995) is of the view that Ìgbà Ló Dé is based on the Ísèyín and Okèihò rising of 1916, while Olúfajò (1991), Iṣòlá (1995) are of the view that Oláòrè Afètèjáyè is a political satire based on the conflict between the Late Chief Ọbáfẹmí Awólẹwọ and the Late Chief Ládòkè Akintólá between 1963 and 1966 in the old Western Region of Nigeria. These two plays do not depict names of historical characters as done in the other plays. The playwrights use their creative imaginations in their characterization in these plays. The interpretations of the events in these plays by critics show that the playwrights present historical events in the colonial and post-colonial Yorùbá society.

Yorùbá historical and protest plays are expected by social critics to be revolutionary and used as ideological weapons in the service of the Yorùbá masses. They are also expected to have close bonds with the working people's struggle. In the words of Onoge (1974:24) revolutionary writers should be confident that the masses are agents of change. Yorùbá historical and protest plays are expected to show the changes desired by the poor masses. The playwrights of these plays should voice out the protest and struggle for a revolutionary change in Yorùbá society. They should be committed to the cause of the poor toiling masses in their plays. The views of James (1969:109) are also relevant for our desire on what we expect from our historical and protest plays. James (1969) says that in explosive situations today in Africa, we cannot but have creative literature that is in some way political, and in some way protest. A writer who is not interested in social struggles of his society and tries to create a private world of art, is saying something controversial about the duty of an artist to his society. Yorùbá historical and protest plays examined in this study are expected to reveal much, and say much of the social struggles and revolutionary developments

of the poor masses against their oppressors in the society.

We have chosen only Yorùbá historical and protest plays in this study because they are the plays that aptly and succinctly illustrate the Marxists views of class struggle , ideology and commitment. They are the plays that say much about the social and revolutionary struggle of the poor masses against their oppressors in the society.

1.2.0 Existing Works on Yorùbá Drama

Not much work has been done in the area of Marxist literary criticism of Yorùbá drama. The efforts made so far as regards criticism in Yorùbá drama are examined below. Scholars views on criticism of Yorùbá drama are seen in journals, chapters in books and published books. Critics of Yorùbá drama have given various names and labels to identify the various forms of drama. These names include: folk opera, modern travelling theatre, contemporary travelling theatre, modern traditional theatre, Nigerian theatre, professional itinerant theatre and the Yorùbá popular travelling theatre of Nigeria (Ulli Beier 1954, 1967, 1970, Adédèjí, 1969, 1971, 1978,

Clark 1979, Íṣṣṣlá 1981, Jeyifo 198^a, etc). All the above named labels are regarded as inadequate descriptive and classificatory labels for Yorùbá drama (Ogúndèjì 1988:51-64). In the classification of Yorùbá drama, Ógúndèjì initially sub-classifies it under two broad headings of the 1 unscripted and 2 scripted. The unscripted is further sub-classified into three groups namely: (i) Sacred, (ii) Eégún Aláré and (iii) Ógúndè Dramatic Tradition. The scripted is further sub-classified into two groups namely: (i) Scripts emanating from edited transcribed texts, and (ii) the Originally Scripted forms.

Before discussing Ógúndèjì's views and classifications, we would like to examine Jéyifò's (198^a) 'The Yorùbá Popular Travelling Theatre of Nigeria'. One may be tempted to accept the descriptive name of Jéyifò if one accepts the fact that this theatre named as 'Ógúndè Dramatic Tradition' by Ógúndèjì (1988) is Yorùbá. Ógúndèjì (1988: 51-64) accepts this view when he writes:

When we talk of Yorùbá drama, we mean the drama that uses the Yorùbá language and other communicative codes in expressing views on the Yorùbá world in general.

It is also true and correct to say that, the theatre is popular and that it is a travelling theatre that has its abode in Nigeria. Jéyifò's title also includes such titles as: Folk Opera, Contemporary Travelling Theatre, Modern Travelling Theatre, and Professional Itinerant Theatre, etc. One may feel that Jéyifò is telling us that plays under his label are more popular than those of the Sacred Drama and the Eégún Aláré (Clark 1979: 33-34, 55-56, Jéyifò 1984:200-203). This fact is well validated by Jéyifò when he states:

The secret of Ogunde's initial advantage and historic influence is that he was, and remains profoundly well-tuned to the outlook, demands and taste of the popular audience (1984:54)

It is our contention that plays under the label 'Ògúndè Dramatic tradition' or 'The Yorùbá Popular Travelling Theatre of Nigeria' can be said to be more popular than those of the 'Sacred Drama' and 'Eégún Aláré' if we are only thinking of the contemporary situation. We must also recognise the popularity or the folkness of the 'Sacred Drama' and the 'Eégún Aláré', especially before the so called modern trends.

Ògúndèjì's (1988) classification of unscripted plays as 'Sacred', 'Eégún Aláré' and 'Ògúndè Dramatic Tradition' is acceptable.² This view is also supported by Clark (1979) when she says:

The greatness of Ògúndè's achievement, therefore, is that he changed the direction of Yorùbá theatre and gave it new impetus and dimension. Almost single-handed, he established what is now loosely termed 'Contemporary Yorùbá Theatre' of which there are many exponents but of which Ògúndè remains the supreme artist and father-figure (1979:5)

Ògúndè is a pioneer in the new direction he had built or developed out of the existing ones.

Under the sub-classification labelled 'Scripted' by Ògúndèjì (1988:52) there are yet two sub-classifications namely: (1) Scripts emanating from edited transcribed texts,

2 A research is to be conducted on the acceptability of this classification to our Yorùbá Theatre Practitioners. At the National Folklore Fair organised by the Nigerian Folklore Society on 20th-25th May, 1996 at the National Theatre, Lagos, they/ ^{are} called Association of Nigerian Theatre Practitioners, which is the name of their Association.

and (ii) 'Originally Scripted'. Işòlá (1981:349-410) regards Ògúndèjì's 'Scripted Drama' as 'Modern Yorùbá Drama'. This study is interested in the 'Scripted Drama' of Ògúndèjì or the 'Modern Yorùbá Drama' of Işòlá. Işòlá (1981:402-407) sub-classifies his Modern Yorùbá Drama into 'Historical', 'Didactic' and 'Protest' plays. Işòlá writes:

Modern Yorùbá plays, on the other hand first had their existence as written scripts. In fact some of them have never been staged. The texts are available for critical studies and for use by theatre companies (1981:399).

Ògúndèjì (1991:20-28) in his critical analysis of Dúró Ládipò's plays, classifies them into four categories, namely:

- i) The biblical plays
- ii) The mythico-historical plays
- iii) The plays adapted from other foreign sources apart from the Bible, and
- iv) The social plays.

Ògúndèjì's classification as shown above relates to only the plays of a single dramatist and it deals with his

scripted and unscripted drama.

In our own classification of Yorùbá plays, we will have these categories, namely:

- i) The historical plays
- ii) The didactic plays
- iii) The adapted foreign literary plays, and
- iv) The protest plays.

Our historical plays would include plays styled the mythico-historical plays by Ògúndèjì (1988). We deleted mythico- from our own title because it does not include legends and folktales. Our main focus in this study are the Yorùbá historical and protest plays as earlier shown. Examples of plays that are mythical and of folktales in origin are: (i) Wálé Ògúnyemí: Obalúayé and (ii) Kólá Ògúnmólá: Òmùtí, The Palm Wine Drinkard. Didactic plays are many and they include: Adébáyò Fálétí: Idààmú Páàdì Minkáílù and Akínwùmí Ìṣòlá: Abé Ààbò to name a few. Adapted foreign plays are: Dúró Ládípò: Èdá which is adapted from the medieval Everyman (Ògúndèjì 1991:20-22) and Olánipèkun Èsan: Orékeléwà which is adapted from Classical Greek works (Babalólá 1971).

The works of Ògúnbà (1967, 1978:3-26), Adédèjì

(1969, 1978:27-3^a, 1981:221-2^a7), Beier (195^a, 1967, 1978), Clark (1979) and Jéyifò (198^a) are based on the historical development of Yorùbá drama classified by Ògúndèjì (1988:51-6^a) as 'unscripted' which is sub-classified to 'Sacred', Ògúnbà's (1967) 'Ritual Drama', Eégún Aláré', Adédèjì's (1969) 'Alárinjò's Theatre and Ògúndèjì (1988), 'Ogúndè Dramatic Tradition', Beier's (1967) 'Yorùbá Theatre', Clark's (1979) 'Nigerian Theatre' and Jéyifò's (198^a) 'The Yorùbá Popular Travelling Theatre of Nigeria'. According to Jéyifò (198^a):

... the Yorùbá Travelling Theatre has not received the kind of comprehensive critical attention it deserves. There is only one full length published work dealing with this theatre tradition and while this is very well-researched, highly informative and readable, it deals with only one of the troupes of the movement... There is no published work to date which has attempted to take in the movement as a whole ... and the social impact and functions of the theatrical art of these companies (198^a:2).

In the opinion of Jéyifò (198^a) his critical analysis of the Yorùbá Travelling Theatre is an overview to fill

an evident vacuum. Jéyifò (198^a) is aware of the works of some scholars as is evident in their Masters and Doctoral Theses in Nigerian Universities. Jéyifò's work uses sociological and technical parameters in its critical analysis of the emergence and growth of Yorùbá Travelling Theatre. This work is also based on known theatre practitioners in Nigeria and it helps immensely in shedding light to our understanding of literary criticism. This work does not concentrate on Marxist theories in its discussion of Yorùbá travelling theatre troupes. It mainly deals with the social impact and uses of the Yorùbá travelling theatre and it does not say anything about class struggle in the travelling theatre troupes' plays examined. Apart from this the study is not on written plays.

As we have stated above, the works of Ògúnbà (1967, 1978), Adédèjí (1969, 1978, 1981), Beier (195^a, 1967, 1978) and Clark (1979) are based on historical reconstruction of the development of the ritual drama (the indigenous festivals), Eégún Aláré, Alárinjò or Agbégijó, Yorùbá Professional Theatre or Ògúndè Dramatic Tradition. They also deal with the emergence of these theatres. Clark's (1979) major focus is on Ògúndè's theatre plays

from the emergence of the theatre troupe to the contemporary Nigerian era. We can infer from the discussion of some of Ògúndè's plays by Clark (1979) that there were intra-class struggles between the British colonial administrators and the emergent Nationalists in the colonial era in Nigeria. Clark's (1979) discussion and analysis of Ògúndè's plays are not centralized on class struggles but on developments. Ògúndè's plays the major focus of Clark's study, are not written.

The works of Armstrong (1978), and Òlájúbù (1978) are based on explication of texts, the use of traditional poetry in Ládipò's Oba Kò So and the sources of Dúró Ládipò's Oba Kò So. As seen by the titles of these works, they are merely concerned with the identification of these concepts. They are not interested in any sociological criticism of the Yorùbá plays examined.

There are some works which are not only analytical but are also based on theoretical analysis of Yorùbá drama. Such works are those of Iṣòlá (1981, 1991) on Modern Yorùbá drama and indigo revolt in Basòrun Gáà. These works classify Yorùbá drama as we have shown above into historical, didactic and protest plays. Iṣòlá

in his critical analysis of protest plays wants the masses to revolt against their capitalist oppressors because:

It is an illustration of what the people themselves could do to save themselves (Işòlá 1981:207).

Işòlá's (1991) work on indigo revolt in Basòrun Gáà uses Marxist literary theory in his analysis of this play. Işòlá believes like Eagleton, a Marxist literary critic, that:

literature may be at least much a question of what people do to writing as of what writing does to them (Işòlá 1991:29).

Işòlá's critical analysis of 'indigo revolt' is comparable with our intra-class struggle in this work. Işòlá says:

... Gáà's apparent decision to stand up for the defence of the down-trodden raises a hope. It is an "Indigo" revolt raising a "brown" hope. The working class is there waiting to be mobilised ... Is Gáà sincere? Has he noble aims? Is he prepared to commit class suicide by abandoning elitist privileges and abuses and taking his place among the working class? (1991:32).

Işòlá's analysis of indigo revolt is on one play and one

author. There is no systematic analysis of intra-class struggle in *Ìṣòlá's* work as we have done in this study.

Adéwolé (1987) in his critical analysis of *Òkédìjì's Rêré Rún* says:

RÊRÊ RÚN is the story of the struggle of workers for better conditions of service and how employers cleverly infiltrated their ranks, broke their solidarity, and shattered their dreams (1987:38).

Adéwolé (1987) asserts that *Òkédìjì* shows "a profound sympathy with the ordinary people who have not made it into the elite". *Òkédìjì* identifies himself with the downtrodden masses. The views expressed in Adéwolé (1987:38-45) in his critical analysis of *Rêré Rún* are comparable to those of *Ìṣòlá* (1981: 405-406). Adébòwálé (1989: 70-75) in her analysis of *Rêré Rún* contends that, Marxist theory is useful because it enables us to know that literature is primarily conditioned by socio-political factors and the prominence Marxist theory gives to the exploited in society. She is of the view that the insistence of Marxist theory that acclaimed writers are those who create human types as characters has greatly reduced the value of Marxist theory. Adébòwálé has seen

the usefulness of Marxist theory in her critical analysis of Réré Rún. Apart from her knowledge of the importance and usefulness of Marxist literary theory she has gone to bring in the discredited Stalinist party elements into her Marxist literary theory ideas. It was Stalin usually referred to as the party thug who wants artists to write compulsorily for the glorification of the Communist party (Arvon 1973:30). Stalinist views are criticised by some Marxist literary critics because no one can set up rigid critical standards for a work of art as done by Stalin. These views are well explained by Eagleton when he says:

The layman's image of Marxist criticism, in other words, is almost entirely shaped by the literary events of the epoch we know as Stalinism... the 1928 decree of the Bolshevik Party Central Committee that literature must serve the interest of the party... All of this comes to a head with the 1934 Congress of Soviet Writers, with its official adoption of the doctrine of 'socialist realism', cobbled together by Stalin and Gorky and promulgated by Stalin's cultural thug Zhdanov (1976:37-38).

The views of Stalin quoted above by Eagleton may be those

accepted by Adéḡwálé as Marxist literary theorists views. She has made a point that Marxist literary theory is useful, it is the usefulness of this theory for Yorùbá plays that depict the society that should be our concern.

Those who are opposed to the use of Marxist literary theory as seen in Fánìlólá's (1989:175) critical analysis of the use of Marxist theory in Yorùbá literature should understand that we should not fold our arms while our oppressors cheat and maltreat us. Fánìlólá (1989) feels that the fault of this theory (Marxist) is that many of its proponents are fanatics who use the theory beyond its limitations. Their dreams that, one bushfowl is not taller than the other is not useful to Yorùbá society because Yorùbá people still make an addition that, only the one that climbs a heap will be taller. In Fánìlólá's opinion, we can say that the bushfowl that climbs a heap and the one that does not climb a heap will not be exempted from sleeping in the hunter's pot of soup (that is being cooked by the hunter). Before the bushfowl that is on top of a heap is caught by the hunter, it would have been lording it over the one who is on the ground. Therefore, in Yorùbá society, there is no time when we will not see

a richman (capitalist) as a ruler. Fánilólá's views are not Marxist literary theorists views, they are capitalist oriented views. Fánilólá may be thinking of the dismantled 'Stalinist Communist Structures'. According to Abdullahi (1989:6), Stalinist form of socialism promises to take the 'Communist Soviet Socialist Republic' to a socialist 'Canaan', that is to say, the dictatorship of the proletariat did not materialise for forty years. What we see in the 'Union of the Soviet Socialist Republic (U.S.S.R.)' is the dictatorship of the party instead of the dictatorship of the proletariat. In the opinion of Babáwálé (1990:9-10), the unpleasant dictatorship of the party and the horrible personality cults of some comrades have outshamed the most hated feudal and capitalist despots. The masses of the 'Union of Soviet Socialist Republic (U.S.S.R.)' rejected the dictatorship of the party and they unanimously called for the removal of their various communist parties from power. This is because the parties were not satisfying the yearnings and aspirations of the people and they no longer deserve to rule but to be replaced. Another plausible reason that is responsible for the dismantling of the 'Stalinist Communist

Structures' is given by Yòlòyè (1995) when he says that:

Ideology: Given a democratic situation the tussle is often between capitalism and socialism (with the collapse of communism, socialism seems to be giving way totally to capitalism since the main protagonists of socialism are now courting and wooing the capitalist world. Left alone as the major ideology, it is not clear if there will be any tussle any longer) (1995:34).

We can infer from the views of Yòlòyè stated above that the capitalists in the world are responsible for the dismantling of the communist structures in U.S.S.R.

In the opinion of Yál (1982:2), it is an accepted fact by even anti-Marxists that some forms of arts and literature are related to forms of social development. Our difficulties according to Yál lies in our revelation of the dialectical nature of the relationships in literature, the relative consistency and stability between forms of literary expression and the socio-economic contexts, the possibilities of these literary forms to survive their socio-economic determinations or conditionings, or even the likelihood of hibernation. Yál is

telling us about the usefulness of Marxist literary theory in the criticism of Yorùbá literature.

Other scholars who use Marxist literary theory in their analysis of Yorùbá plays are: Ògúnṣínà (1987, 1995) and Agbájé (1989). Ògúnṣínà (1987) examines folklore and social change in Wálé Ògúnṣínà's play Obalúayé. Though Ògúnṣínà (1987) examines issues on Marxist views about the Yorùbá society depicted by the author in this paper, these views are not in line with our views on Marxist criticism in this study. We are not concerned with national consciousness based on Yorùbá religion, an issue examined by Ògúnṣínà in this paper. Ògúnṣínà (1995) examines the effect of colonialism in T.A.A. Ládélé's play Ìgbà Ló Dé. He examines the struggle between the masses of Ògbojò and the Ajéḗlẹ̀ who is an agent of colonialism on one hand and the masses and the Ológbojò and his chiefs on the other hand. The masses under the name of "Ayé" resent the colonial taxation and innovations in Ògbojò. Ògúnṣínà uses Marxist literary theory as a tool in his analysis of Obalúayé and Ìgbà Ló Dé. These two works help in the elucidation of our understanding of consciousness in intra- and inter-class struggles in Yorùbá plays examined in this study. As we have earlier

indicated, Ìgbà Ló Dé is one of the plays analysed in this work, while Obalúayé is not.

Agbájé (1989:47-70) uses Marxist literary theory in his examination and critical analysis of the use of songs in Akinwúmi Ìṣòlá's play, Kòseégbé. Agbájé (1989) specifically uses Marxist sociology of literature in the analysis of songs in Kòseégbé as he accepts the views of Barber (1979:1) that the:

Study in sociology of literature ... seeks to investigate the relationship between social and verbal forms, that is between the organisation of a society and the literature produced by the society ... (Agbájé 1989:49-50).

This is the theoretical framework used by Agbájé in his analysis of the five songs used by Ìṣòlá in this play. We examine the use of folksongs as a strategy for educating the masses in their struggle against their oppressors in Yorùbá plays. Agbájé (1989) does not say anything about intra-class and inter-class struggles in this play. Agbájé is mainly concerned about the use of these songs in Yorùbá society.

Other scholars who examine Yorùbá plays are Adédèjì

(1983), Olúfàjò (1991), and Ògúndèjì (1988, 1991, 1995, 1996). As we have shown above, Adédèjì's (1983) work and Ògúndèjì's (1996) work are concerned with the examination of the plays of Akínwùmí Iṣòlá. They all classify Iṣòlá's plays as 'problem' plays. They also examine the socio-political and economic situations as presented in these plays. Ògúndèjì (1991) examines the classification and some literary aspects of Dúró Ládipò's plays. Ògúndèjì (1991:20-28) shows through the classification of Ládipò's plays, "the wide range of the plays" and how Dúró Ládipò is well "known for the mythico-historical plays". Ògúndèjì asserts that:

There is no doubt that Dúró Ládipò's plays are very successful on the entertainment scale as an art of spectacle. The present short exposition has also hopefully indicated that the plays are of serious literary significance, through its treatment of the musico-poetic features, setting and themes ... (1991:26)

Ògúndèjì's (1988) work examines the mytho^{ic}-historical plays of Dúró Ládipò using semiotics as his theoretical base. Ògúndèjì's (1988) use of binary opposition, archetypal purposes and characterization mode are

informative to us in these works. According to him:

The notion of binary opposition which was borrowed by literary structuralists from their linguistic counterparts is also crucial to semiotic textual analysis (1988:23).

Binary opposition as a model used in structuralism in Ògúndèjí's (1988) work has some similarities with Marxist views on contradiction in our society. Ògúndèjí's (1988) analytical tools are useful for some of our critical analysis of Yorùbá plays. We should note that our own critical approach in this study hinges on Marxist literary theories and their applicability to intra-class and inter-class struggles in Yorùbá historical and protest plays.

Other notable works of Ògúndèjí (1995) are his examination of culture, Yorùbá drama and religion in pre-colonial and post-colonial situations. This paper like the others illuminates our understanding of Yorùbá historical and protest plays that depict pre-colonial and post-colonial society in this study. Ògúndèjí's works examined above are not concerned with Marxist literary theory and class struggle. We have earlier in this study examined the

classifications of Yorùbá drama by Ògúndèjì (1988, 1991) and have stated our views on these classifications.

Olúfàjọ (1991), Ìṣòlá (1995), as we have earlier seen in this work, are concerned with the use of satire in Oláòré Afòtèjọyè. They are of the view that the play is a satire of the struggle between the Late Chief Obáfẹmi Awólọwọ and the Late Chief Samuel Ládokè Akíntọlá of the defunct Action Group Party between 1963 and 1966. Olúfàjọ's (1991) analysis of this play helps in throwing more light to our fuller analysis of Oláòré Afòtèjọyè and other plays in the same category in this study. We are not working on satire in this study.

As we have shown with a review of some of the existing works on Yorùbá drama, they reveal that much works are still needed in the area of Yorùbá written plays. This study is interested in adding to the list of existing works on literary criticism on Yorùbá drama. This work will examine more plays and playwrights in the area of historical and protest plays than the earlier works have done. Apart from this, our literary weapon of criticism of these plays is Marxist literary theory canons such as class struggle, ideology and commitment; as

are artistically created by the playwrights.

1.3.C Marxist Literary Theory and Yorùbá Society

Marxist literary views about class divisions and contradictions that lead to class struggle, materialism, individualism, alienation, ideology and commitment as revealed in Yorùbá plays that depict intra-and inter-class struggles show that Yorùbá playwrights are members of the society. The playwrights show the ideas, values, and feelings by which Yorùbá people experience their society at different times. In adopting the Marxist literary theories we note the views expressed by Olátúnjì that:

The plea is that concepts which derive from other cultural milieus should be considered or redefined in the light of Yorùbá cultural attitudes before they are applied to the criticism of Yorùbá literature (1975:4)

In our analysis of Yorùbá historical and protest plays we shall adapt Olátúnjì's (1975) approach in our examination of features such as intra-class and inter-class struggles. We can liken the intra-class struggle within the ruling elite in Yorùbá plays to what Caudwell (1975:

103-106) refers to as the "bourgeoisie's struggle against the monarchy", which according to him is nothing but the bourgeoisie's will challenging the will of the monarchy which can only be obtained at the expense of the "haves". According to Marxist critics, class division in a society with varying interests will definitely lead to class struggle. Class struggle is basic and essential for any revolutionary development.

The commitment of Yorùbá playwrights should be to the popular masses of the people that constitute the oppressed of the society. The oppressed produce the wealth upon which the rulers feed and live and the oppressed are only given a meagre wage or reward mainly to keep them strong for further work and not for any other purpose. The predicament of the poor is succinctly summarised in the Nigerian Pidgin English proverb that says "Monkey de work baboon de chop", which literally translate while the monkey (the poor) does all the work, the baboon (the rich) does all the eating. We are aware that the Yorùbá society is always a stage of rivalry between two different and incongruous opposing classes: the oppressed (poor) and the oppressor (rich) classes. According to Jéyifò (1985:7-8) it is an accepted fact

that drama deals with the contradictions in our social life. He says:

There is no drama that does not in one way or the other show in its structure a physical conflict, a moral conflict, and a clash between two different beliefs or ideas (1985:7)

However, the plays selected for this work are those in which the *cause* of the oppressed in their struggle to free themselves from oppression are presented either fully or partially. For the playwrights to be able to pursue this, they should see the Yorùbá society the way the *masses* see it and are able to meaningfully interpret the socio-economic and political situation the way the poor suffering workers interpret it. According to Bámidélé (1993:150-158) literary critics in our society should adopt a humanist approach in their criticism of literary works instead of a radical criticism. This view is also expressed by Craig (1975) in his critical analysis of Marxist literary theories. Craig says that, critics should reflect the humanist nature of Marxist literary theories in their criticisms of 'Socialist Realism' and 'Critical Realism'. These views we find

useful for literary criticism of Yorùbá plays and Yorùbá society.

1.4.0 Limitations of this Study

This study is mainly concerned with class struggle in Yorùbá historical and protest plays. We are mainly concerned with plays that depict Marxist literary theories views such as ideology, commitment and that exhibit the consciousness of the masses in their revolutionary struggle . Because of the reasons given above, Oba Kò So and Ààrè Agò Aríkúyèrí, which are also historical plays, are not included in this study. The Marxist literary approaches adopted in this study are not just alternatives for examining Yorùbá historical and protest plays, but the approaches are used because of our desire that these approaches should express our views adequately about the liberation of the working classes, peasants and the masses from oppression.

CHAPTER TWO

ISSUES IN MARXIST LITERARY THEORY

2.0 Introduction

We want to examine literary theories such as formalism, structuralism so as to know their relevances to Marxist literary theory. Sociology of literature and Marxist approaches will also be examined.

2.1.0 Formalism and Structuralism

Formalism is a literary theory developed in Russia by the 'Moscow Linguistic Circle' in 1915 and the 'Society for the Study of Poetic Language' (Opoyaz), headed by Shklovisky in 1916. Formalism according to its proponents is interested in the written words which is the real text of a written work. This should be taken by a critic of a written text as the most important tool of literary analysis. Formalists are of the view that a literary critic's major concern should be the text and not other extraneous features. According to them, 'the link between literature and our daily lives is seen in the linguistic structures' (Arvon 1973: 64-65). They use linguistic science in their interpretation of literature.

Formalism differentiates between poetic language and the practical language in their evolution of the theory of 'versification' and that of 'narrative prose'.

Formalism illuminates our understanding of our analysis of class struggle which are based on the Yorùbá plays examined and the society. There is a sort of relationship between this theory and the views of some Marxist literary critics. Marxist literary theory sees a work of art as intimately concerned with social life as a whole and the relationships between content and form. In this regard Marxist literary critics also examine the form of a work of art as the formalists do. According to Arvon (1973:41) in:

... the relations between the economic base and the ideological superstructure; content is the governing factor, and though form in the final analysis is always necessarily subservient to it ...

Arvon (1973:66-67) asserts that, Trotsky, a Marxist literary critic accepts the views of the Formalists when he admits that, "Marxism, in and of itself, cannot provide the criteria for literary criticism". Trotsky accepts the view that formalism can be used in conjunction with Marxist

literary theory. He contends that, Marxism is the only philosophy that can explain why and how a certain development takes place in a work of art in any known historical era. He is of the view that Formalists interest in giving information on specific artistic features of a literary form is acceptable. He opines that the Formalists are wrong when they reduce all literature to the style of verbal communication. It is not the interest of a literary critic to limit his criticism mainly to the descriptive and the statistical analysis of the syntax of a poem and a simple catalogue of the vowels and consonants. This leads us to Structuralism.

The inadequacies of Formalism leads to the rise of Structuralism. Structuralism is a theory which wants a critic in his examination of any work of art to have a very deep understanding of certain facts that are not contained in the work. Structuralism is interested in examining the cultural milieu that is not in a literary text. This is why it finds ways of investigating the relationship that exists in the structure of literature and culture. According to Scholes (1974:10) structuralism

can help us to:

look at individual works, literary genres
and at the whole of literature as a system
within the larger system of human culture.

Structuralists are interested in the differences between paradigmatic and syntagmatic connections in signs of a work of art. According to the Structuralists (Scholes 1974), in a specific sentence, the meaning given to a work of art is usually resolved by the position where a word occurs in a sentence and the inter-relationship of that word with other words used and the grammatical elements of such a sentence. Our choice of a word to be used for our analysis should be guided by many of such words used in the same semantic range in the already established context in order to be able to select the most correct word for the text where the word is to be used. This is when we situate such a word properly in connection with the other words in the established syntagmatic context. This paradigmatic and syntagmatic connections as we see among signs in a work is not restricted to the analysis of a sentence alone. This method can also be used in our analysis of texts.

Another important feature of Structuralism that may illuminate our understanding of the relationships that may exist between Marxism and Structuralism is the notion of "Binary Opposition". According to Jakobson, binary opposition is a:

... fundamental operation of the human mind, basic to the production of meaning ... the smallest common denominator of all thoughts (Culler 1975:15-16).

Ògúndèjì (1988:23) is of the opinion that Culler (1975: 15) says that the important factor that can necessitate binary opposition is that the occurrence of one component demands the co-occurrence of another opposing component. Binary opposition is important as an essential function of human idea. Ògúndèjì (1988:23) also asserts that

... In the making of a round character within a literary text the good and bad aspects of human nature are presented, and in the development of a plot there are usually two forces at loggerheads to complicate issues and make the story interesting.

Binary opposition which is comparable to class struggle

in Marxist view shows the contradictions in the society. Binary opposition is helpful for our understanding of the contradictions between two opposing classes (the oppressors and the oppressed) in a society. It is comparable with the views of Ilésanmí (1989:96-117) in his features of the twin theory applied in the analysis of Ifá literature. Ilésanmí enumerates some Yorùbá beliefs as examples of binary opposition and the similarities and differences noticeable in twins in Yorùbá society.

Structuralism and its binary opposition show some similarities between some of our Marxist literary approaches. Selden (1985:37-42) gives an analysis of "Structural Marxism". According to him, Marxist criticism was affected by the widely accepted views on Structuralism which was an intellectual theory in Europe in 1960s. Structuralism like Marxism believes that individuals cannot be understood unless we examine their social existence. Selden (1985) also classifies the works of Marxist literary critics such as Goldman, Lukács, and Althusser under his class of "Structural Marxism". Goldman's genetic structuralism, Lukács and

Althusser's views on ideology will be examined in this study.

2.1.1 Sociology of Literature: Marxist Approaches

Literature is about the experience of men and their conception of life in any given society. Literature according to Wellek and Warren (1980: 94-95):

... is a social institution, using as its medium language, a social creation.

Literature may represent life, a social truth where human beings are regarded as objects of literary creation. Literary artists are part and parcel of society with specific social status, social recognition and reward. A literary artist writes for his society. Literature raises some social questions as regards the culture of a people and their customs, standards, styles, symbols and myths. Literature may reproduce life as well as help in moulding life. People in a society may be taught to pattern their lives as seen in the struggle by fictional characters to free themselves from oppression. The relationship between literature and society is seen in some studies of literature as social documents. This may

be shown in assumed images of social reality. Some kinds of social images may be abstracted from literature. Literature may be used as a social weapon to reveal some outlines of history as seen in some Yorùbá historical drama. According to Wellek and Warren (1980:105) literature is a bank of costumes and customs and is a source book for the history of civilization.

Sociology in the opinion of Onyeonoru (1994:54) was:

... coined by Auguste Comte in 1837. The term is a hybrid of the Latin word "socius" which means society, and the Greek word "logos" which means science. Hence the conception of sociology as the science of the society.

From the above definition we can see that literature and sociology though two different disciplines are both interested in the study of the society. Hence the area of study called sociology of literature.

Marxist literary critics systematically examine the relations between sociology and literature, what these relations should be in a class society and in the envisaged classless society. Marxist sociology of literature is an

evaluative criticism of the para-literary aspects of a work of art such as ethics that feature in a work.

Marxist sociology of literature succinctly explains not only what we saw and we now see in the social relations and the meaning of an artist's work, but what these social relations should have been or ought to be.

Marxists are not merely critics of literature and the society, they are in a limited sense also prophets of the future events. They are also social critics and propagandists. It is very difficult for the Marxist literary critics to separate the above stated functions.

Sociology of literature is interested in the analysis of the inter-relationships between a work of art and the society that produces such a work. It is mainly concerned with the notion that an art work cannot exist in isolation from the society that creates it. The language used by our artists belongs to the society and a literary artist as a member of a society is usually influenced by other members of his society. This is to say that the relationship between a literary work, the creator of such an art work and the society of an artist is that of regular interactions. Sociology of literature according to Ògúnṣínà (1987:38-39) deals with literature

as a literary creation and it is not mainly regarded as mere reflection of the society's social structure.

Marxist sociology of literature is a well researched scientific theory of human societies and how the oppressed in these societies can change the oppression in these societies by organised struggles of the masses so that they can free themselves from exploitation and oppression. Literature in capitalist societies according to Marx and Engels (1977) is used by the capitalists to legitimize and establish their power as the ruling class. Marxist literary theory approaches to literature is interested in illuminating the understanding of the relationships between literature and the social structure of the society by examining the historical forces which are depicted in the content of such a literary text. Sociology of literature is interested also in showing and revealing the ways by which a literary work reacts, negates and distances itself from the society in order to explain systematically how literature is regarded as a part of a known and established society.

Marxism is a theory used in the critical analysis of history, society, revolution and economics before it

is applied as a literary theory. Marxism as a literary theory is developed from the writings of Karl Marx (1818-1883) and Frederick Engels (1820-1895). Marx and Engels views are collected from their scattered writings on literature which they did not develop systematically. Some Marxist literary critics views are built on early views of Marx and Engels. Marxism is also built on quite different critical literary approaches and literary theories. Marxism is an existing body of ideas and a set of actual political practices. Marxism is influenced by some changes in the world.

Marx and Engels were of the opinion that, class struggle between the proletariat and the bourgeoisie would definitely lead to the overthrow of capitalism. This will inevitably promote the cause of social progress. In many modern societies, including the Yorùbá society today, class struggle between the bourgeoisie and the proletariat has not yet led to the overthrow of capitalism. It, however, remains a persistent feature in Yorùbá society. Some conscious Yorùbá playwrights depict class struggle in their plays. According to Melotti (1977:25) Marx knew that history does not look at individuals but at peoples. It was the contention of Marx that when

history looks at people, history finds that there are different groups of people. Some groups of people are pulling one way, while some other groups are pulling in a different way. These classes developed after the primitive classless society into the slave owning society. The slave owning society developed into the feudal society, while the feudal society developed into the modern capitalist society with different class interests. Although the development of classes in Yorùbá society did not follow the same scheme as described by Marx, we still have classes with varying class interests in Yorùbá society. These classes and class interests are reflected in Yorùbá historical and protest plays analysed in this work.

Engels contributed immensely to the corpus of Marxist writings on literature and society. Engels raised the problem of the relationship between literature and political commitment. He believed that commitment had to be shown from the situation and action which should not be explicitly explained. According to him a poet is not compelled to present the reader with the historical, and future solutions to the conflicts which

he describes. Engels view on literature is of an evident political bias and it is a source of contradiction in Marxist literary theory. Engels also accepts the view that every character in a novel should be a type as well as being a particular individual. He is of the opinion that the choice of typical characters should be consistent with the demands of realism. According to Engels:

Realism ..., implies, besides truth of detail, the truthful reproduction of typical characters under typical circumstances (Fokkema and Kunne-Ibsch 1977:88).

Engels in later years explained further that Realism means loyalty to historical truth. Engels asserts that, Miss Margaret Harkness in her novel City Girl should have concentrated more attention to the rebellious protest of the proletariat against exploitation because that protest had revealed itself as an historical fact.

Engels theory of a possible disagreement between the political ideas of an author and the meaning of his work is an important development in Marxist literary criticism. According to Slaughter (1980) Fokkema and

Kunne-Ibsch (1977), Engels theory is inconsistent with a quick assessment of literary works on the basis of the author's biography and critical purposes. This theory directs the critic's attention to the literary text, and as a result rejects what the new literary critics called "the intentional fallacy". The rejection of intentional fallacy implies that Engels did not agree that such a fallacy exists. The views of Engels and his theories stated above were never developed systematically into literary theories. These were left to other Marxist theory developers such as Lenin, Mao Tse-tung, Lukács, Goldman to name a few who made useful points on the development of Marxism and literature.

Marx, Engels and all Marxist theory developers believe that it is only through struggles that the proletariat can be able to liberate themselves from their capitalist oppressors. They all believe that an awareness should be created among the masses so as to awaken and arouse their consciousness for class struggles. As we will show later in this work the views of Marx and Engels are developed by later critics.

2.2.0 Relevant Marxist Literary Approaches

Marxist literary approaches that are important for our analysis in this study include ideology and literature, commitment and genetic structuralism. We shall examine them one by one.

2.2.1 Ideology and Literature

Ideology is a very difficult term to explain satisfactorily. The concept of ideology challenges Marxists to develop theories of literature. The possibility of seeing how ideology and literature are related opens a wide range of inquiry by Marxist literary theorists. Literature is recognized as a special kind of social and historical category by Marxist literary critics. In the opinion of Williams (1977) the notion ideology does not come from only the Marxists. Ideology is an important term used by Marxists in their thoughts about culture, literature and ideas. There are three popular distinctive views about the concept of ideology in Marxist theories that can be modified in relation to a literary work being analysed. They are:

- a) a system of beliefs that are distinctive features of a particular class.

- b) a system of false beliefs, ideas, consciousness which we can contrast with true scientific knowledge.
- c) the general method of the production of meanings and ideas (Williams 1977:55).

According to Williams (1977) some Marxist combine the first and second ideas above together. William's view of combining the first and the second ideas above is comparable to what Jéyifò (1985:7) says that:

... a radical sociology of drama which establishes its line of demarcation from these perspectives must seek to discover the truth in the lie and the lie in the truth of the relationship between the content and forms of social life and the forms and content of dramatic art itself.

We can say that ideology examines beliefs that are distinctive features of a particular class such as the oppressed or the oppressors, note some false beliefs, ideas, consciousness which are contradictory to scientific knowledge and be able to produce meanings and ideas from all the above views. There are some illusory ideas that are revealed in a literary text and we need a literary analysis that produces meanings for our understanding of

such a literary text. These views are also succinctly expressed by Eagleton (1976) when he writes:

Marxist criticism is part of a larger body of theoretical analysis which aims to understand ideologies - the ideas, values and feelings by which men experience their societies at certain times (1976: viii).

Some of these ideas, values and feelings as Eagleton puts it are available to us in literature. Ideology is not a set of dogmas. Ideology dictates the way by which men live and perform their roles in a class-society. They constitute the ideas, values and images which tie men to their social functions. Literature springs from an ideological view of the world. This is one of the reasons why Barber (1984) asserts that, "all literature is ideological". There is no literature that does not exhibit a kind of ideology in its content.

There are two opposing views about literature and ideology. There is the view that literature is an expression of the ideology of the time when such literature is written. This is a position taken by the "Vulgar Marxist" literary theorists who see

works of literature as mere reflections of the prevailing ideologies of their time. This view cannot adequately explain why we see literature that actually challenges or negates the ideological views that are common when it is written. There are those who believe that literature challenges, negates or distances itself from an ideology. A good literature always transcends the ideological limits of the time such literature is written by giving us much facts about the realities which literature hides from us.

According to Forgas (1986:149-150), Eagleton (1976: 17-19) and Ògúnṣínà (1987^b:38-42), Althusser contends that ideology shows the imaginary ways in which men experience the real world. This is the type of experience which literature gives to its users. Althusser says that literature does more than merely passively reflecting the experience it gives. Literature is held within ideology, but it tries to distance itself from ideology so that literature will allow us to 'feel' and 'perceive' the ideology from which it springs.

The way literature enables us to understand ideology fully is well developed by Macherey. Macherey's important theoretical work is concerned with how literary works are made. According to Macherey literature is like productive

labour where raw materials are worked into an end-product. He is of the opinion that the author is not a creator but someone who works pre-existing literary genres, conventions, language and ideology to an end-product, the literary text (Forgacs 1986:145). Macherey's ideology is a compact system of illusory beliefs. Ideology is complete, but there are certain things ideology cannot see or say. Literature challenges ideology.

Macherey's theory though a novelty, is not without its own problems. According to Forgacs (1986), this theory is innovative in the sense that it is able to overthrow interpretive criticism as revealed in his theory of reading and the incomplete text. Though Macherey restricts the application of his theory to narrative fiction there is nothing that hinders it from being applied to poetry and drama. Macherey's theory is not an evaluative theory, it is a descriptive theory. It is his opinion that it is only fictional language and a number of specifically literary resources which bring about the production or transformation of ideology.

Ideology is an important weapon in a society with classes of varying views. These classes will hold conflicting ideologies that will result into

class struggle . Conflicting ideologies of the oppressors and the oppressed in a class based society will engineer class struggle between them. Ideology is important for our analysis of Yorùbá historical and protest plays as regards the examination of the struggles in them.

2.2.2 Commitment

There are critics of the Marxists who feel that it is only Marxists who say literature should be committed to the cause of the proletariat. Commitment is consciousness, activity, openness and a choice of position. According to Acholonu (1986), the idea of commitment is still a matter of controversy and a critical issue in literature. She asserts that

Many literary scholars are of Satre's view that "writing is a certain way of wanting freedom", once you have begun, you are committed willy-nilly (1986: 261).

For Marxist literary theorists like Eagleton (1976:38), Marxist criticism wants a writer to devote his work to the cause of the proletariat. The doctrine of 'Socialist Realism' adopted by the 1934 'Congress of Soviet Writers'

asks a writer to produce a truthful historical account of realism in its development of revolution. He must also take into account the problems created by ideological transformation and the education of workers as laid down by socialism. This doctrine also want a literature that must have a leaning to the Communist party. It must be optimistic and heroic. This literature must contain revolutionary views showing Soviet heroes. As pointed out by Eagleton (1976), Meyerhold, a theatre producer does not support Socialist Realism, because its prescription has nothing to do with art. Marx and Engels (1977) stated in their comments on works of literature that, the political views of an author may run counter to what his works objectively reveals. According to Eagleton (1976:43-44), Trotsky knows that artistic form is a product of social content and says that artistic form is a product of social content. He says that artistic work should have a high degree of freedom and that literary texts should only be judged by their own laws. Plekhanov criticised Chernyshevsky for saying that art should be only for propaganda. Plekhanov refused to put literature at the service of party politics. He made a distinction between the social function of literature and its aesthetic value.

He believed that it is only art which serves history and not the immediate pleasure that is important. Commitment in Marxist literary theory means conscious alignment. The interesting Marxist theory in its emphasis on practice defines the pressing and limiting conditions within which at any period certain kinds of writing can be done. These writings agreeably emphasise the required relation involved in other writings.

According to Eagleton (1976:58) the question of how 'progressive' a work of art should be to be an authentic work of art is an historical issue, and cannot be settled assertively at any time. This is because there are times and societies where conscious, 'progressive' political commitment should not be an important weapon for the production of major literary works. There are some periods such as fascism when in order to live and write as an artist needs a sort of questioning that is likely to lead to open commitment. In some societies, conscious political alignment and the power to write important literature go naturally together. These types of periods are not mainly restricted to fascism. There are periods of bourgeois society when literary creations are relegated to the background. They are trivial and castrated, because they

are not developed by the unproductive ideologies from which they originate. They are also not able to make important connections and give sufficient discourses. In this period, a need for an openly revolutionary literature becomes necessary. As far as Nigeria is concerned this is a period when we need an explicitly revolutionary literature that is in support of the masses.

The matter of commitment has been a critical issue in Marxist literary theory. There are Marxists who still support the Communist Russia's prescription of rules for a committed literature, while others hold the view that literature should not be an instrument in the hand of a political party. Trotsky expresses the view of non-interference of the party in literature when he says,

... the domain of culture is not one in which the party is called to command, yet this does not mean eclectically tolerating counter revolutionary works (Eagleton 1976:42-43).

Trotsky's idea of not tolerating counter revolutionary works is bias and it restricts the freedom of literature. But his views that, "we force poets willy-nilly to write about nothing but factory chimneys or a revolt against

capitalism is absurd" (Slaughter 1980:86), show that he is not partisan. Trotsky is of the opinion that a work of art must be judged only by its own laws. We are of the view that critical standards should not be set up for realism or commitment based on party rules. The question really then is to what should the writers be committed if as in the case of Nigeria there is no socialist party? The Yorùbá playwrights examined in this study are committed to a cause . We may add that there is no radical socialist party in Nigeria as there is in Communist Russia. Yáí (n.d) on a political reading of Fágúnwà's novels shows that Fágúnwà in his novels is committed to the cause of the capitalist in Yorùbá society, while Barber (1984) in her style and ideology in Fágúnwà and Òkédíjì, shows that Fágúnwà is committed to the cause of the capitalists in Yorùbá society, while Òkédíjì is committed to the cause of the proletariat in their novels. Alàbá (1993:1-6, 1985) shows that Agbè artists in Yorùbá society perform their art for the oppressors in the society, we cannot categorically say that they are generally committed to the cause of the capitalists as we are told by Alàbá (1993:4) that these

artists recognise that they are the exploited class in the society. Some of them however may be seen as committed to the cause of the capitalists, since according to Alàbá, there are no evidences of struggle in their Agbè songs.

... the oral poets are indirectly and, sometimes directly influenced in their performances by the wealthy who are the elite class. The oral poets see themselves as all the better for it since they get what they want - money, food, drinks, and admiration. They do not seem to have any reason to complain, for they believe and say in Yorùbá thus: Ònpèni ní ʒolá (He who pays the piper dictates the tune) (1993:4).

The artist in Yorùbá or Nigerian society should be committed to the cause of the down trodden masses. Commitment is also important in any analysis of class struggle in a society. A committed literary artist will show the struggle between the masses and their oppressors in his works.

2.2.3 Genetic Structuralism

There is a very old method of Marxist literary theory

that is interested in how literature in conjunction with other arts developed out of social life and what make literary works to take the form they take. This approach is called 'genetics' because it is solely concerned with origins, judgements and purposes. One of this theory's interesting modern accounts is that of Lucien Goldmann (1964). Goldmann (1964:8) was interested in the fact that 'Objective meaning' of a literary work was often not completely understood by the author. Goldmann's other choice to the biographical approach of linking a literary work with that of an author and his personality was not centred on the text but to link the structure of the work with the 'mental structure' of the social group of the author. Goldmann was influenced by Lukács. According to Goldmann, literary works come out of social consciousness and behaviour. He is mainly concerned with how social consciousness and behaviour are linked to society and how to establish this.

'Mental Structure' and the structure of a literary work does not mean linguistic structures in Goldmann's view but they mean patterns of ideas and concepts. He is of the opinion that certain privileged social groups have

a superior form of ideology which he calls a 'world view'. In Goldmann's view, a world view is the expression of those groups in a society "whose thoughts feelings and behaviour are oriented towards an overall organization of interhuman relations and relations between men and nature" (Forgacs 1986:146-151). According to Goldmann (1964:17) social groups can either be 'revolutionary' or 'reactionary' classes. He contends that, a world view is expressed as a mental structure and this structure is coherent in the work of great writers who represent the social group.

Goldmann's theory has similar views with older views of literature as a form of expression. This theory is also different from other theories because it sees a literary work as not an expression of the author but that of the social class to which an author belongs. He asserts that, the origin of a literary work's mental structure is found in its social behaviour. This social behaviour is not from the will of different individuals but from two or more individuals acting as one. The basic unit of activity is called 'trans-individual subject'. According to Goldmann, literary works are collective products of social groups. He did not cancel the role of

an individual author entirely. He contends that, a great writer elaborates the mental structure of his group. This is to enable the work of the author relay back to the group a sharpened awareness of that structure. He stresses the view that a writer does not merely reproduce the group's consciousness in a mechanical way. What the writer does is to advance very reasonably the degree of structural unity which the collective consciousness has achieved in a rough and ready fashion. This is to make the work in Goldmann's (1973:115) view have a collective achievement through the individual consciousness of its writer. This is an achievement that will later prove the goal of the group.

Goldmann's theory is not mainly based on the view of reflection, but on the process of expression and this is what makes his theory genetic. Goldmann's emphasis on the method by which an individual writer 'advances' and gives coherence to group consciousness is shown as a complete rejection of the reflection theory. In spite of this, Goldmann and Lukács say that reality and thought are dialectical totalities. Goldmann shows the connections between a work and the author's social group which is made

up of only a section of the totality. Goldman's theory is more sociological than that of Lukács. Goldman is more interested first in groups within a society and not with a whole society. His view of a social class is more restricted and more specific than that of Lukács. He is interested in social classes that are involved in class struggle and great literary works which produce world views about class struggle. These world views are privileged forms of ideology of the conflicting or struggling classes, which are 'global' rather than partial ones. He is just explaining the coherence with which ideology can be shaped in literature.

We can see Goldman as a person who brings changes in Marxist literary theory in his interest to show how many sections of the superstructure such as literature, art and religion, etc. are related to each other and to class relationships and struggle. In Goldman's theory there are innovations. This is because his theory overcomes the view of the vulgar Marxists that the economy directly determines the nature of literary work and it attempts to work out a more systematic analysis of the intermediary between them. There is much in Goldman's theory which is

grounded in conventional literary studies. Some views in his theory are rather vague and questionable. The view of Goldmann about social consciousness is inherited from Hegel and not from Marx. Goldmann sees social consciousness as the direct expression of a social class. The literary work also becomes the direct expression of this consciousness. Goldmann's view that a work of art is an expression of the dominant ideology of a class the writer belongs creates some problems. There are some literary works where the authors transcend the social classes which they belong in order to ally with the masses in their struggle against oppression.

Capitalist societies can develop literature that transcend the ideology or world visions of the bourgeoisie. In the same vein a society can equally develop literature that transcends the world vision of the socialists. Another flaw of Goldmann's theory is that it excludes the dialectical theory of cognition - which is knowledge gained from personal experience in its analysis. Slaughter states that:

Goldmann's structural homologies between the images, the artist's work and ideology of his class were the typical result of

dispensing the dialectics of cognition
(1980:210).

According to the dialectical theory of cognition an artist should not be an ordinary photographer who produces objective social forces, but should be a creative mediator who infuses such cognition with his subjective criticism of these forces. It is important for an author to be a member of a particular class, but when an author's class is used as an important criterion in our analysis as Goldmann has done in genetic structuralism, the field of study of genetic structuralism becomes narrow. A literary artist in our own view can unconsciously envisage the contradictory ideologies and classes of his time in the society. These ideological contradictions, and class struggle which can be sensitively realised, recorded and creatively presented by an author can negate or challenge the ideology of the author's class.

2.3.0 Relevant General Marxist Concepts

Our next step is to examine Marxist concepts such as materialism, individualism, superstructure, alienation and class struggle in relation to literature and literary

criticism.

2.3.1 Materialism

Materialism can be defined in two ways as dialectical materialism and historical materialism. We can even give a common name dialectics to describe both dialectical materialism and historical materialism. Dialectics is not an easy notion to understand. Dialectics describes a process of development from a lower to a higher stage. Dialectical materialism explains the development of the world as dialectical. The word "dialectic" is derived from the Greek verb which means "to carry on a discussion". A statement, which is a thesis and counter statement, known as antithesis may lead to a conclusion, which is a synthesis. In some cases, the conclusion may be regarded as belonging to a higher level or it may be the first point in a new argument. According to Fokkema, and Kunne-Ibsch (1977:81-84), Forgacs (1986:135-136) Marx and Engels referred to the structure of society and the structure of history as "dialectical". This is a notion that shows the aggressive and contradictory agents at work within the structure of society and the structure of history. Dialectic is also a system by which history and society can be examined in

order to show the true relationship between their component parts. Marx used dialectics in his study of political economy by looking at social classes and some socially decisive views on economic production and capitalism.

Materialism according to Marx and Engels is explicit in the world that stimulates the real development of the individual. The emancipation of the working class is the task of the working class themselves. According to Marx capitalist economy produces material preconditions for classless society and it produces the class of men who will be forced by exploitation to overthrow the capitalist economy in a successful struggle. Using Marx and Engels principle of dialectical materialism we will be able in this study to examine the process of development of Yorùbá society from its earliest times to the present day as depicted by some Yorùbá playwrights.

Historical materialism is the method of extending the principle of dialectical materialism to the study of social life and social development. Marxists state that literature is primarily regarded as ideology and that it must be studied as laid down in historical materialism.

The effect of Marx's material notion of history cannot be easily distinguished from his views on literature. Marx and Engels dialectical materialist and historical theories have profound implications for literary criticism. Marx literary assessment is based on a measure of economic decision which is interested in the reason why a literary work presents advanced or regressive developments in the economic basis. The other assessments are based on the probability according to the literary rules and regulations of his days and the assessment of personal preferences of some writers such as Aeschylus, Goethe and Shakespeare who used the literary canon of their days. Marx first assessment can be regarded as the most important if we consider Marxist literary views, but the other assessments have been used by Marxists.

Jeyifò (1985:7) is of the opinion that:

... Equally important is the fact that drama does not merely subsume conflict as its organising structural motif beyond this, drama also axiomatically attempts a resolution of sorts, a provisional synthesis in the conflicting pulls within its constitutive action, thereby approaching the limit of the

dialectical image potentially realisable
in art ...

This view of Jéyifò (1985) shows that dialectical materialism and historical materialism are useful tools for our analysis of any literature.

2.3.2 Individualism

Individualism according to the Marxists lead the materialists in capitalist societies to find ways of accumulating wealth through the idea of materialism and the alienation of the masses. Individualism in the Marxist literary theory view can lead to class struggle if there are revolutionary classes in a society who are opposed to the reactionary ideas of individuals. Forgas (1986:151-153) asserts that, Marxist literary theorists such as Goldman stresses the origin of a work's mental structure which lies in the social behaviour. Social behaviour in Goldman's views does not arise from the will of separate individuals but from two or more individuals acting as one. The capitalists in our view believe in the efforts of separate individuals in the accumulation of wealth. Udentia (1993:27) contends that; the literature that was of interest in the past was the literature

... under the tutelage of conservative guardians of western literary traditions of aesthetics and dramatic/theatrical practice, the literature that emphasized the dominance of the individual over social forces, a literature of individualism, "free enterprise" and a negation of collective self-determination.

Though Udentia's (1983:27) view is on African literature written in English, it is also true of some literary works in Yorùbá. The views of Yáí (n.d) and Barber (1984) on the novels of Fágúnwà show that Fágúnwà's novels depict the efforts of individuals in Yorùbá society. They hold capitalist oriented views. Yorùbá drama is not an exception as shown in the intra-class and inter-class struggles examined in this study.

2.3.3 Base and Superstructure

The only part of literary criticism on realism which is not extensively disputed by Marxist literary theorists is the base and superstructure. Marx's view on history and society is different from those of his predecessors and his contemporaries. This is shown by the emphasis his predecessors and contemporaries placed

on the socio-economic element which they say is the only determinant of a society's character. Socio-economic element according to Marx means the social relations that are created by a kind of economic production common in a society. This relationship in a capitalist society is between the capitalist and the proletariat. This type of relationship is founded on exploitation and conflict or struggle . The economic base produces a number of social institutions and beliefs which regulate or dissipate the conflict. According to (Forgacs 1986: 136-137), in a capitalist economy, there may be a bourgeois parliament and judiciary, an education system tailored generally to the needs of capitalist production and all the values that uphold these institutions. The various results which emerge from the socio-economic process is called the superstructure of the society by Marx.

According to Engels, he and Marx did not say that base should be seen as the major or the simple determinant of everything in the society. Forgacs (1986:137) asserts that Engels explained that the method of development was a complicated one, and that the various elements of the superstructure interacted to influence historical change.

The uncertainty about base and superstructure had allowed varied Marxist literary interpretations of it. Some Marxist literary theorists hold an established or determinist opinion that the base simply caused the superstructure and that the superstructure reflected the base. Some Western Marxist literary theorists placed more importance on how changes in the superstructure such as political organization and party action can influence and quicken changes in the base. There has been less real agreement among twentieth century Marxist literary critics on how base and superstructure interact. All these views are responsible for the establishment of two schools in Marxist literary criticism. In the first school are the orthodox Marxists who hold that literature is a product of the superstructure which is the economic base. They believe that literature is known by this economic base of the superstructure and can only be analysed by this economic base. There are those in the second school who see literature as moulding, creating awareness of the consciousness and social desires of the downtrodden masses. Marxists in

this school believe that these elements of the superstructure should also be stressed in conjunction with the economic base of the superstructure. Marxists in these two schools accept the fact that literature is a part of a society's social system and they know that literature is related to ideology. The relationship between literature and ideology is not given similar interpretation by the Marxist literary critics as we have shown above in this study in 2.2.1.

Superstructure in the simplest definition by Marxist literary critics is a structure that is built on the top of a base, an arrangement which grows from a simpler base. According to Slaughter (1980: 20-22), other constituents of the superstructure are: politics, religion, philosophy, ethics, law and art including literature. This superstructure is mainly designed in order to establish and concretise the power of the ruling class. The views expressed above about base and superstructure are also important for any analysis of literature in Yorùbá or Nigerian society. As we have shown above literature is one of the important components of Marx's superstructure in any known society. The idea of literature being mainly designed in order to establish

and concretise the power of the ruling class is relevant to literature in Yorùbá society where we have intra-class and inter-class struggles.

2.3.4 Alienation

Alienation is related to dialectical materialism and historical as we have explained above. Alienation according to the Marxist literary critics is a method by which a worker in the historical development of a society renounces or relinquishes his labour power to the capitalist in exchange for wages, and he becomes a subordinate part of a machine. Alienation also deals with appropriation of the labour of a worker in a capitalist society. Appropriation of the labour of workers through alienation results in class struggle. The workers in a capitalist society work for an employer. According to Forgas (1986:137-138), the worker's surplus value is appropriated by his employer.

Yál (1978:120-122) asserts that:

Yorùbá cosmology is certainly an alienation, in Marxist terms, as the cosmology of any nation ...

Alienation as shown by Yáí (1978) is a feature in Yorùbá society. As seen in some Yorùbá plays, alienation is depicted in plays that are based on pre-colonial, colonial and post-colonial Yorùbá society. This view that is one of the causes of class struggle in any society will be critically examined in this study.

2.3.5 Class Struggle

Class Struggle is important to us in this study. It is the major focus in our analysis of Yorùbá historical and protest plays.

Marxist literary theorists such as Lukács believed like Marx and Engels that in every social system the predominant method of production gives rise to inner contradictions that are expressed in class struggle. These contradictions, according to Marx and Engels (1977: 40-41) can be seen in the dialectical development of history. For example, through class struggle, the capitalist method of production developed when it destroyed the feudal method. In the same vein the socialist method developed by destroying the capitalist system. In the capitalist mode of production, the means of production was in private hands because workers who

owned their tools had nothing to sell but their own labour. Class struggle as a result of inherent contradictions was between the capitalists and the workers. The accumulation of wealth or the appropriation of the labour of the workers by the capitalists lead to class struggle in the society. The modern bourgeois society which developed from the destruction of the feudal society has not done away with class conflicts or struggles. It has developed new classes, new conditions of oppression, new forms of struggles in place of the former struggle.

According to Yermakova and Ratnikov (1986:126) class struggle may differ between passive resistance to a hostile class, active attacks on its positions, and violent class conflicts or struggles. Class struggle may be open and hidden, voluntary and conscious. Every change of forms of class struggle is determined by many changes in the situation, by the acuteness of contradictions between the interests of different classes, and by the level of development of each specific class. The forms of the class struggles are associated with the forms of class organization. We can find vivid illustrations of this by using the example of the proletariats'

class struggle, which may assume three principal forms such as economic, political and ideological. The views of Marx and Engels on class struggle according to Slaughter (1980:127-128) are further expatiated by Lukács and succinctly explained by Slaughter. They are of the view that the struggle between socialism and capitalism is still as it had been since the 1848 rising of the Paris proletariat, which is the fundamental reality of the modern age. Marxist literary theory should show the role of class struggle and class consciousness in structuring the experience in which men are able to penetrate the forms of appearance and comprehend them in their necessity.

Class struggle whether hidden or open would either end in a revolutionary reconstitution of the society or a ruin of the society. Class struggle is basic to any revolution. It is when there is struggle between an oppressed class and an oppressor class that an oppressed class through a revolution can replace the oppressor class. A revolution in the words of Lenin (1977:371) is a desperate struggle of classes that has reached the peak of ferocity. According to the rule of social revolution

there is a clash of two ideological opposed classes. One of the classes is the reactionary or the outgoing class trying to preserve its domination and its old relations of production. The second is the revolutionary class that owns the future. In order to achieve Marxist literary critics views of a classless society, the proletariat must be well educated on how they can organise their struggle which will lead to a successful revolt.

The above views of Marxist literary theorists are no doubt relevant to the colonial and post-colonial Nigerian society as evident in the views of Yáí (1978) referred to above. Jéyifò (1985:11-22) examines the hidden class war in The Road a play written by Sòyínká. He examines the materialistic desires and yearnings of some characters who are depicted as the capitalists in the play that could be seen as a hidden class war between these capitalists and their oppressed. Olúránkínṣé (1987) examines class struggle in Yorùbá novels between the ruling elite and the educated elite who are supported by the colonial administrators. The struggle examined by Olúránkínṣé (1987) and the one examined by Iṣòlá (1991: 29-37) as "indigo revolt" belongs to what we call intra-class struggle in this study. Intra-class struggle will

always lead to an "upper crust" revolution which according to Sertsova, Shishkina and Yakovleva (1986:49-50) are

... by their historical import are bourgeois for they serve to establish and strengthen capitalist social relations ... Some or other groups of the bourgeoisie take part in them. During such revolutions the masses cannot set their own goals, for they are pushed aside from active participation in the revolutionary process. They are called "upper crust" revolutions because they leave many substantial elements of the old system unchanged.

The ruling class in such a situation is made up of many sub-groups and factions, with different interests. In order to meet their inordinate ambition these groups look for a leader who will be their spokesman. This is in essence a struggle within one class that will not threaten the domination of that class. This is just a struggle for redistribution of the wealth within an exploiter class and an opportunity for providing better conditions for a group to amass wealth.

Intra-class struggle in the oppressed class is not a focus of Marxist literary critics because their major

focus is based on the fact that exploiters are opposed by workers as a team, there is a confrontation between the working class and the capitalist class, workers secure their groups interests and they promote the fundamental interests of the oppressed class. According to Sertsova et al (1986: 49) intra-class struggle that will lead to "upper crust" revolutions are "historically limited". There are coups and counter coups in our contemporary societies. The ruling elite is made up of many groups and factions with each faction and group having its own special or specific interest. In order to meet their interests these groups look for a government that would be their mouth-piece. This is a struggle within the ruling class which does not threaten the domination by this class. This according to Sertsova et al (1986) is a mere "struggle for redistribution of profit within the exploiter class". It is a struggle for providing better conditions for some or other groups to grow richer. The oppressed in our societies are struggling for power between them and their oppressors. What we have seen is that the capitalists succeed in infiltrating the ranks of the masses in order

to crush their strong revolts as Iṣòlá (1981:107) has shown in his analysis of Réré Rún.

In this study our analysis of class struggles are derived mainly from pre-colonial, colonial and post-colonial settings in the Yorùbá society in particular and the whole of Nigeria in general.¹ Open and hidden class struggles are applicable to both inter-class and intra-class struggles as we will see in our analysis of plays in this study. A struggle is open when all strategies of struggle are revealed from the initial stage of planning to the end when there is a revolt or the revolt is crushed. In the same vein, a struggle is called hidden when all the strategies of struggle are concealed from the initial stage of planning and are only exposed at a later stage when there is a revolt or a revolt is crushed. Open and hidden class struggles are also called open and hidden class wars. That is why Marx and Engels (1977:10-11) say that

The history of all hitherto existing society is the history of class struggles ...

1 A more detailed research work is needed on the position of Obas, Chiefs, Obis, Ezes, Emirs, etc. in Nigerian society.

... in a word, oppressor and oppressed, stood in constant opposition to one another, carried on an uninterrupted, now hidden, now open fight, a fight that each time ended, either in a revolutionary re-constitution of society at large, or in the common ruin of the contending classes (our emphasis).

This study is interested in how hidden and open struggles are artistically presented by some Yorùbá playwrights and how the struggles have helped in revolutionising the Yorùbá society depicted in the plays or in crushing the oppressed masses.

Intra-class struggle as we have shown above will lead to a revolt within the ruling elite. The masses in intra-class struggle are pushed aside from active participation in the revolutionary process of intra-class struggle. This struggle in some cases can arouse the consciousness of the masses so as to set them in motion for inter-class struggle. The masses in intra-class struggle can also note the weaknesses observable in this struggle and use them for their advantage in inter-class struggle. Inter-class struggle is the major focus of Marxist criticism, but it is important to examine their

views no matter how scanty on intra-class struggle so as to know the merits and the weaknesses for our knowledge of inter-class struggle.

2.1.0 Adopted Approach

In this study we have chosen eight written historical and four protest plays as shown in our introduction for analytical purposes. We shall examine the form and content of these plays to discover their structures and the presentation of Yorùbá society in them using the modified Marxist literary views on ideology and genetic structuralism. This is because a critical examination of these literary approaches reveal that none of them can give us a complete solution to the problems of Marxist literary criticism. Literature does more than being a mere mirror or a reflection of ideology. Literature can distance itself from ideology in order to enable a critic know and discuss the ideology from which literature springs up effectively. Literature can also challenge ideology when it uses ideology and it can also negate ideology.

Goldmann's notion that a work of art is an expression of the dominant class a writer belongs cannot be correct

for all works of literature. Some literary works show that an author can transcend the social class which he belongs in order to ally with the masses, if he is a capitalist. Intra-class and inter-class struggles are given prominence in this work because of our examination of the relations between our written Yorùbá plays, the world views and social structures in them. This is because none of these components can be fully comprehended without the others. We hope that our theoretical approach in this study will enable us to really understand the structure of the plays analysed. This approach may serve as a useful tool in the criticism of Yorùbá plays in particular and Yorùbá literature in general. We shall, in the next two chapters try to examine dialectically how applicable are the Marxist theoretical approaches in our analysis of the works of Yorùbá playwrights. This will be done by showing how they are able to rework the elements they have taken from their experiences in such a way that the whole from which they are 'abstracted'² are revealed. What the authors show us in these plays as the literary or artistic representations are not some

² Also examine the views of Slaughter, C. (1980) on literature and dialectical materialism, pp 197-200.

examples of confirmation of a logical generalization but the actual relationship between individuals and groups. It is essential to add that our adopted approach will also take the Yorùbá society into consideration in the use of Marxists concepts discussed in this chapter. Yorùbá society as artistically presented in Yorùbá historical and protest plays is our major focus in our analysis of intra-class and inter-class struggles in these plays. This is why we have to adopt Marxist literary approaches in line with Olátúnjì's (1975:4) advise that concepts from foreign cultures should be modified in line with Yorùbá culture before they are used as tools for our literary criticism. This is exactly what we have done with our use of Marxist literary sociological approaches in the study of Yorùbá plays in this work.

Marxist literary theories are employed in this work because they enable us to know that "literature is primarily conditioned by socio-economic and political factors" (Adéḡwálé 1989:72-73) and because of the prominence they give to the exploited class in the society. As Yáí (1982:2) has noted, it is an accepted fact by even

non-Marxists that there are forms of art and literature that are related to forms of social development. Marxist literary criticism is interested in the revelation of the dialectical relationships in literature, the relative consistency and stability between forms of literary expression and the socio-economic and political contexts, and the possibilities of these literary forms to survive their socio-economic and political determinations or conditionings.

CHAPTER THREE

INTRA-CLASS STRUGGLE IN YORÙBÁ PLAYS

3.1.0 Introduction

This Chapter examines intra-class struggle in some Yorùbá plays by considering the causes of intra-class struggle such as individualism, inordinate ambition of the ruling elite; strategies in intra-class struggle such as clinging to power, usurpation attempts; and the end results of intra-class struggle such as establishing the status quo, incumbent ruler reconfirmed as supreme leader and change of leadership - the usurper takes over.

Intra-class struggle is a struggle within a group. Udenta (1993) examines the issue of intra-class struggle in some early literature in English by African authors. He asserts that,

... one thing about this early period of realism in African literature is its "objective" nature. Though the emphasis is always to look at the destructive role of European intrusion, most of the writers, for example, Achebe in Things Fall Apart and Arrow of God and Ngugi in The River Between and Weep Not Child, bring to the

fore the local conditions, antipathies, animosities and intra-ruling class struggles and certain unwholesome practices that smoothed the way for the imperialists (Udenta 1973:7) (Our emphasis).

The same views expressed above by Udenta (1993) about the novels of Achebe and Ngugi also apply to the analysis of Kólé Qmótóşò's novel 'The Combat', set in Nigeria of the sixties. According to Udenta (1993:14), Qmótóşò's novel condemns the anarchical political system created by those who inherited power from the imperialists and how this system led to a prolonged intra-class civil strife. Olúránkínşé (1987) also examines a sort of intra-class struggle in some Yorùbá novels. This struggle is between the ruling elite on one side and some educated elite who are supported by British imperial administrators on the other side. Although Olúránkínşé (1987) calls this class struggle in general, we know that it is intra-class struggle within two ruling powers who are struggling for leadership in those novels.

In Jéyifò's (1985:49) critical analysis of Kólé Qmótóşò's play, 'Shadows in the Horizon', we are told of

how action starts from the panic created by the "national bourgeoisie", and goes on to the "suicidal intra-class battles" which weakens the ranks of the bourgeoisie before the attack by the formidable action of the workers. To come nearer home to Yorùbá plays, Işòlá's (1991:29-37) analysis of "indigo revolt in Basòrun Gáà," is an example of intra-class struggle in Yorùbá plays and it is re-examined in this study. Indigo is a sign of royalty in Yorùbá society. "Èwù Etù" is a costly native gown by the ruling elite in the society.

All the views examined above prove the relevancy of our examining the patterns and trends of intra-class struggle in Yoruba plays, the ideologies that inform this struggle, the authors who are committed to intra-class struggle and characters as depicted in the plays that are committed to intra-class struggle. There are hidden and open intra-class struggle in Yoruba plays that are of major importance to us in our analysis in this Chapter.

In intra-class struggle, as our analysis will further establish, there is usually the ruler who is supported by some people and another member of the ruling class

who is opposed to the said ruler and who nurtures the ambition to unseat the said ruler. This opposing member of the ruling class also usually have some followers. Among the followers of the protagonist and antagonist are other members of the ruling class and some members of the ruled class who are in fact ignorant of the root cause of the intra-class struggle and are being used for selfish ends.

3.2.0 Causes of Intra-Class Struggle: Individualism and Inordinate Ambition.

At the root of intra-class struggle within the oppressing ruling class is individualism which at times manifests as inordinate ambition for political power. Let us consider individualism alone first before we take it together with inordinate ambition.

As we have earlier discussed in this study in Chapter Two, individualism according to the Marxist literary critics will lead the materialists in capitalist societies to find ways of accumulating wealth. The capitalists believe in the accumulation of wealth. The individualistic views of the capitalists are depicted by some Yorùbá playwrights. The specific temperament of

characters, their individualistic tendencies in accumulating wealth, their motive forces, and their psychology are artistically presented in Yorùbá plays. Characters with capitalist individualistic tendencies do not fight for the supremacy of other characters or the masses depicted in these plays but they always fight only for their own interests. These characters believe in the individualistic capitalist ideologies. They do not support equitable distribution of wealth and their individualistic tendency is responsible for the intra-class struggle in their class.

In Òkédìjì's Şàngó the intra-class struggle between Şàngó and his chiefs on the one hand and Şàngó, and the chiefs of Òyókoro on the other hand is caused by this type of individualistic tendencies. Şàngó wants to be the sole controller of the socio-political and economic situation at Òyó without taking into consideration the views and feelings of his chiefs and immediate subordinates. An illustration can be drawn from the following dialogue between Şàngó and his wife Qya to buttress the claim.

Qya: Kábíyèsí, şé gbogbo àwọn ijòyè lẹ ti
fòrò ọhún lẹ, gbogbo wọn ló sí ti fowó sí i?

Şàngó: Àító ọmọdẹ é rán nişẹ ni lọọ há mi
 dáko wá kí n̄ fún ọ lómii rẹ mu. Ifá
 páşẹ, ẹmí gbà, mo gbà tán mo ní kí wón
 ó laago, kín ni ijòyè kan tún lè rí wí?
 (O.I. 36-37)¹

Qya: Your Majesty, have you conferred with all
 your chiefs on this matter, have they all
 approved it?

Şàngó: Being not able to send a child on an errand
 is the reason why one says go and help me
 buy an ekọ meal so that I will give you
 its water to drink. Ifá gave the command,
 I accepted, after accepting, I commanded
 the town crier to give the message to the
 townspeople, what will any chief contribute
 again? (pp 36-37)

The individualistic nature of Şàngó is revealed in the
 above excerpt. Şàngó feels that he is the sole authority
 in the administration of Òùnkò in this play. Though it
 is true that Ifá decrees that he and his people should
 move from Òùnkò to Òyọkoro, it is proper and ethical for
 him to confer with his chiefs before asking his town crier

¹ All examples in Yorùbá will be tone marked in this
 work for easy reading and understanding.

to relay the message to the townspeople. The system of government in any Yorùbá town needs collective responsibility between the ọba and his chiefs. Though Şàngó is acting on divinatory guidance, the way he is going about it shows his individualistic nature. Şàngó staunchly believes in the domination and control of all the resources at his disposal as the feudal and suzerain overlord of both Ọyọ̀ Ọ̀ǹk̀ò and Ọ̀ỳọ̀k̀òrò.

Ọláọ̀rẹ̀ Afọ̀tẹ̀joyè and Líşàbí Agbòngbò Akàlà are the other plays that illustrate this factor. There is an intra-class struggle between Ọlọ̀yọ̀ọ̀ and the Aláké of Ègbáland and between Ọláọ̀rẹ̀ and Ọbálówò in the two plays respectively.

The individualistic view of Ọlọ̀yọ̀ọ̀ is expressed in Líşàbí Agbòngbò Akàlà in:

... Wọ̀n ti gbàgbé èbùn mi ọ̀dọ̀dún,
 Ó si yẹ kí n rán wọ̀n létí pé
 Bí bàbá wọ̀n, tíí ẹ̀se àwọ̀n ègbọ̀n mi,
 ti máa n ẹ̀se kò gbọ̀dọ̀ yẹ ...
 Ju gbogbo rẹ̀ lọ, èyin ilàrí mi,
 Ẹ̀ ó máa lọ látí orílúú kan dé òmíràn,

Láti lq máa gba èbùn náà wá fún mi,
 Kí ng rí'hun máa fi şe ara rindin (O.I. 4)

... They have forgotten my annual tributes,
 It is necessary that I should remind them that
 As it was customary for their fathers, who were
 my elder brothers, to pay tributes to my
 predecessors, they should not fail ...
 Finally, you my ilàrí.
 You should go from one town to the other,
 To collect those gifts for me,
 So that I will enjoy them.

From the above excerpt including the speech of Şàngó in the former excerpt, the individualistic ideology of Qlqyòq and Şàngó is revealed by the use of pronouns and pronominals 'mi' (I), 'n'(I), 'ng'(I), 'èmf' 'I'. They are interested in their own acquisition of wealth and not in those of their chiefs.

The two examples cited are depictions of pre-colonial situations. It is in the case of the intra-class struggle in Qláòré Afòtèjoyè that we have an example of the *post*-colonial situation as we will show below.

This individualistic tendency, as mentioned is manifested in the inordinate ambition for socio-political power among members of the ruling class. They usually

separate into factions on this and are usually at each others throats for it. Such ambitious tendencies are pronounced in Oláòré Afòtèjoyè, Miààbí Agbòngbò Akàlà, Olú Omo and Basòrun Gáà that will be used for illustrative purposes here. It can, however, also be found in Efúnsetán Aniwúrà, Morèmi and Sàngó.

Oláòré Afòtèjoyè and Olú Omo are examples of plays where either the protagonists or antagonists, seek the cooperation of other members of the ruling elite for their inordinate ambition. The inordinate ambition of the oppressors in these plays is to rotate the leadership of the society among themselves. Oláòré Afòtèjoyè shows a division into two of the ranks and files of the chiefs of Jòntolo. Oyèbòdé and Sẹmẹtọn support Oláòré, the Ọtúnba of Jòntolo who is next in rank to Ọbálọwọ, while Dẹbẹnà and Adéaka support Ọbálọwọ - the oba of Jòntolo. Because of the inordinate ambition of Oláòré, he seeks the cooperation of Ọlọtẹ of Bọtẹ - the oba of Bọtẹ, in his struggle against Ọbálọwọ. Olú Omo shows the struggle between Adébógun, Ọní Akójẹnbú and Oşókálùú who are warriors and members of the ruling elite at Ègbá and Sómóyè, the Basòrun of Ègbáland. Adébógun and his mates want war-lords to be in control of the socio-political

and economic situation in Ègbáland in this play. They want to oust Šómóyè, the Bašòrun. Šómóyè on the other hand is, however, supported by chiefs such as Šókènú, Ògúnbonà, Lará, Anóba, Òkènlá, Madam Tinúbú and a leader of the poor suffering masses named Fásànyà.

The hidden intra-class war² between aláàfin Adégoólú and his Bašòrun Gáà at the initial plot of the play shortly after the enthronement ceremony clearly points to the inordinate ambition of Gáà. Gáà had eliminated four different aláàfin before Adégoólú is crowned king. The hidden intra-class struggle in Bašòrun Gáà is from the beginning of the play till when Gáà kills Àgbònyín, the only daughter of aláàfin Adégoólú. It is after the killing of Àgbònyín that the hidden war becomes an open class war. The views of Abíòdún Adégoólú expressed in this play is no doubt illuminating in this respect.

Ènyin ayaba, ènyin omọ-ọta

Ènyin àgbààgbà àtẹyin erú ọba ...

Kíl'ohun t'ó t'áyọ nínú ẹrẹhẹ

Ọba tí mo jẹ

B'áa bá ş'ọba l'éní-èjì

Ó niye t'áò r'ábò wọn -

² The idea of a hidden class war is borrowed from Jéyifò (1985:11-12) which Jéyifò got from Marx and Engels (1977:41).

Nibo ni nwọn lọ?

Atòtún-àtòsì, lórí Gáà Ọṣọrun ni

Béè ni Gáà l'ó sí fí mí jọba ... (O.I. 2^a)

You royal wives, you princes and princesses

You elders and ọba's slaves ...

What is joyful in my worthless -

ascendance to the throne

If we count the names of ọbas one by one

We know the number that have gone away -

Where have they gone?

All of them could be traced to Gáà the Ọṣọrun

And it is Gáà that made me an ọba ... (p. 2^a)

From Abiódún's view we can say that Gáà has an inordinate ambition to rule. He perpetually wants to be the overlord, hence he is, individualistic. In the play, contrary to the views of Yorùbá that the aláàfin of Ọyọ was in the past a king with absolute power, whose word was law and who had the power of life and death, Baṣọrun Gáà as in history is the one in control of power. It can be argued, however, that the case of Baṣọrun Gáà in history and in this play is an aberration. According to Àtandá:

As a matter of fact, it would seem that it was the Baṣọrun who had the chance of becoming too powerful. This is what the

carrier of Baṣòrun Gáhà (175^h-177^h) seems to suggest (1973:128).

There is no doubt that it is the socio-political tools that allows for Àtándá's observation that Gáà exploits to his own selfish advantage.

Another example of a hidden intra-class struggle for the inordinate ambition of the ruling elite is found in the case of Líṣàbí, the Aláké of Ègbáland and his chiefs in Líṣàbí Agbòngbò Àkàlà. The hidden class war in this play begins after Líṣàbí has successfully led the masses to defeat Ọlọyòọ and his ìlàrí in Ègbáland. Líṣàbí leads the masses in establishing 'egbé àáró'³ (a farmers union) and 'egbé olórógun' (a warriors union), then he mobilises the people to carry out a successful revolt against the oppression of Ọlọyòọ and his ìlàrí. Aláké and his chiefs become jealous of the high esteem given Líṣàbí by the common people, and they think that they may appoint Líṣàbí as their leader after the successful revolutionary struggle. Aláké and his chiefs such as Àrẹ̀gò, Jagùnnà, Lúkòsí, Olúwo therefore treacherously assassinate Líṣàbí:

³ Àáró is a method of cooperation among farmers in Yorùbá society. They cooperate in order to help in each other's farm work.

JAGUNNÀ: Ọrọ wo ni ẹ n gbọ lẹnu rẹ?
 Ẹ jọwọ ẹ pa alákorí rẹ
 Kí ẹ gbé òkú rẹ sínú kòtò yíí...
 (O.I. 128-129)

JAGUNNÀ: Why are you listening to him?
 Please kill the silly idiot
 And dump his corpse in this pit ...
 (pp 128-129)

Some members of the ruling elite in some of the plays, because of their inordinate ambition for political powers support the rotation of rulership among themselves. The principle is that of "íwọ jẹ tí ẹ, kẹmi jẹ tẹmi" (You eat your own and let me eat mine). Ọláọrẹ in Ọláòrẹ Afòtẹjoye expects the incubent oba, Ọbálọwọ to vacate the throne so that he Ọláọrẹ can now ascend it. Similarly the antagonist warlord group made up of Adébógun, Ọní Akójẹnbú, and Oṣókálùú, want Ẹsómóyè the Baṣọrun of Ègbá to step down from the throne so that one of them can take it up. Their view is represented by this statement.

... Àwọn tí wọn jẹ ológun nílẹ ibòmíràn
 papàá tí pè wá pé kí a jọ gba èrò bí ológun
 yóò ẹ máa wà nípò àṣẹ nígbogbo ilẹkílẹ
 ... (O.I. 34-35).

... Those who are warriors in other places have also called us so that we can reason together on how warriors should be in control of authority in all lands ... (pp 34-35)

At the interpretative level it can be concluded that the situations in the intra-class struggle resulting from the individualism of certain members of the elite which is concretized in their inordinate ambition that leads them to either attempt to seize powers, is a satire of the current political situations in Nigeria and many other African countries where there are several coups and counter-coups.

3.3.0 Strategies in Intra-Class Struggle

The protagonists and their antagonists who are members of the ruling class and who are involved in intra-class struggle adopt some strategies such as clinging to power, making attempts to usurp power and tussles as we examine below. The characters involved in intra-class struggle in these plays are the Obas, Baálès, Başòrun or chiefs. It is in Sàngó that we have the Baálè of Òyòkoro. We have Başòrun in Başòrun Gáà

and Sómóyè is the Başòrun of Ègbá in Olú Omo. We also have chiefs in this play who belong to the warrior class. In Líṣàbí Agbòngbò Akàlà, war lords are created for the purpose of the intra-class struggle between Aláké, his chiefs, the Olóyòó and his Ilárí.

3.3.1 Clinging to power and Usurpation Attempts

Some plays portray some characters who want to hold tight to power without relinquishing it to any other person. These characters believe in the divine rulership of kings. It is only death in the opinion of these characters that can remove a king from the throne. These characters do everything at their disposal to see that they defend their territorial integrity so that they remain perpetually as rulers so that they will be the overall controllers of the socio-political and economic situation in their societies. Başòrun Gáà in the play Başòrun Gáà is in this class. Iṣòlá (1991) has aptly described the view that the actions of Gáà after enthroning aláàfin Abíòdún Adégoólú does not show Gáà as leading a struggle to free the poor suffering masses but to cling to power. Iṣòlá writes:

The success of this mobilisation will however depend on the integrity of the leader. Is Gáà sincere? Has he noble aims? Is he prepared to commit class suicide by abandoning elitist privileges and abuses and taking his place among the working class? Another short-coming that weakens Gáà's image as a possible leader for the working class is his inordinate ambition to enjoy the privileges of an ọba ... (1991:32-33)

Gáà successfully adheres to his principle of holding tight to power in this play until Abíódún Adégoólú is able to crush Gáà.

Other plays that depict similar features of the ambition of the ruling elite to cling to power and usurpation attempts are Sàngó, Olàòrè Afòtèjoyè, Olú Omó and Efúnsetán Aniwúrà. Sàngó wants to hold tight to power at all cost at Ọyọkoro. This is because he wants to be the sole controller of the socio-political and economic situation of the town of Ọyọkoro. In spite of the opposition initially organised by the Baálẹ̀, the people of Ọyọkoro and the organised struggle by his chiefs, Başòrun, Alápínni, and Babaláwo he still clings on to power. In his counter revolutionary struggle to

cling to power he destroys himself, his chiefs and many members of his household. Ọbálówò of Jòntolo in Ọláòré Afòtèjoyè wants to cling to power in his struggle with Ọláòré. He removes Ọláòré as the Ọtúnba of Jòntolo in order to consolidate his power. In the opinion of Olúfàjọ (1991:93-103), this play is a political satire about the activities of two political giants of the proscribed Action Group (A.G.) party and the crises and struggles that engulfed the party between 1959 and 1966. The late Chief Ọbáfẹmi Awólówò is depicted in this play as Ọbálówò, while the late Chief Ládòkè Akíntọlá is depicted as Ọláòré. The Late Ọba C.D. Akran of Badagry is depicted as Sẹmẹtọn. One can infer from Olúfàjọ's (1991) views that Sardauna of Sókótó is depicted in this play as Ọlọtẹ of Bọtẹ. Some of the events depicted in this play are derived from major events in the Action Group's crises between 1959 and 1966. Ọlábímtán in his depiction of characters in this play responds to the socio-political and economic changes of his time. He also responds with his total personality to his social environment which changes all the time

because Ọlábímtán as a writer lives and is influenced by history of intra-class struggle in his society. Ọbálówò and Ọláòrẹ belong to the same class of the ruling elite. Ọbálówò is crushed in this intra-class struggle and Ọláòrẹ becomes the Ọba of Jòntolo. Ọbálówò who does not want to relinquish power in this play is seen as an ọba who wants to cling to power. The Ọlòtẹ of Bọtẹ clings to power at Bọtẹ when Jòntolo becomes a subordinate town to Bọtẹ. Ọlòtẹ becomes an absolute monarch in place of Ọbálówò.

Şómóyẹ and Adébógun, Oşókálùú struggle for power in Olú Omo. They struggle for the control of rulership of Ègbá. Şómóyẹ wants to retain power and cling to power in Olú Omo and be a divine ruler, while Adébógun, Ọní Akójẹnbú and Oşókálùú want a change in the rulership. Since Adébógun and his clique who want warriors to be in control of the socio-political and economic situations in Ègbá do not succeed in their struggle to see that Şómóyẹ does not succeed in clinging to power in this play, we cannot categorically say whether they will ally with Ègbá masses. One may even say that Adébógun and his clique are captivated by the money given by Gilèlè of Dahomey. Other members of the warrior class

who should have supported Adébógun and his clique realise the intrigues of Adébógun in their struggle with Sómóyè: Ajíbólá says:

Ohun tí a gbọ ní pé wọn tí gbé owó ñlá
gaan fún Adébógun láti tọjú, àwọn
ológun Ègbá. Àmọ, ẹ́ ẹ́ kúkú mẹnì tẹ ẹ
ní? Ó dàbí ẹ́ ní pé ìwọ́nba diẹ ló fẹ́
fi sílẹ́ níbẹ́. Ó fẹ́ jókòó lé ìyókù.
Bí a ò bá mẹnù lele, kí ó má jẹ́ pé
ìgbó lásán ní yóò fi àwa rú o (O.I. 29).

We have heard that Adébógun is given a huge sum of money to take care of Ègbá warriors. But, you all know the person you have? It seems as if he is going to present to us a small amount out of the money. He wants to control the remaining amount. If we are not determined, he may just use us as mere implements (p. 29).

The above views show that Adébógun is interested in his own individualistic ambition to usurp power. If we also examine the moral aspect of the actions of Adébógun and his clique, we may say that they are not supported because Ègbá people will not like to be slaves. Sómóyè who is interested in holding tight to power because of the benefits he derives from such an exalted position

manipulates some Ègbá chiefs and the masses to crush the revolt of Adébógun and his clique. Èfúnṣetán and Látòósà are engaged in a hidden intra-class struggle that later becomes open struggle when Èfúnṣetán kills her pregnant slave Adétutù. One can in fact infer that Látòósà who is interested in power and wants to control the socio-political and economic situation at Ibàdàn in Èfúnṣetán Aniwúra will do everything possible to eliminate any opposition or threat to his supremacy. In the struggle between Látòósà and Èfúnṣetán, Látòósà is victorious and he clings to power as the divine Àarẹ of Ibàdàn. Though Látòósà frees Èfúnṣetán's slaves when Èfúnṣetán is defeated, we cannot conclude that Látòósà allies with the masses in freeing Èfúnṣetán's slaves, since the masses are not integrated in his administration, he clings to power.

In the desires made by some characters to cling to power, we see other characters who have the ambition of usurping powers from the divine rulers at all cost. These attempts result into tussles or struggles which are either hidden or open-confrontations. There is interrelationship between characters who want to cling

to power and those who want to usurp power in some plays. The characters who want to usurp power are those who are next in rank to some rulers depicted in some cases. In some other cases they are just members of the ruling elite or the capitalists in these plays. We have seen the roles of some of the characters who want to usurp power by clinging to power. Some of the characters who want to usurp power wield much power in these plays. As we have earlier indicated in this study, Baṣòrun Gáà wants or has already usurped power in the play Baṣòrun Gáà after killing four ọbas such as Lábísí, Awónbíojú, Agbólúajé, Májèjèógbé and the appointment of Abíọdún Adégoólú. Initially Gáà makes aláàfin Abíọdún a mere puppet in this play until Abíọdún organises a revolt against him and Gáà is crushed. Adégoólú, the aláàfin of Ọyọ goes to Gáà's house to prostrate himself to him. It is against Yorùbá tradition for an ọba to prostrate himself to anybody. This is a proof of hidden intra-class struggle, "Ó fẹjẹ dúdú sínú, ó tutọ funfun jadé" (He leaves black blood in his stomach, while he pours out white spittle). We have shown the usurpation attempts by Adébógun and his clique in Olú

Omo. In Sàngó the usurpation attempts by chiefs such as Başòrun, Aláplíni and Sàngó's Babaláwo, crushes Sàngó's chiefs, Sàngó himself and his children. The Baalè of Oyókoro may be regarded as the person who usurps power from Sàngó at the end of this play.

Clinging to power and usurpation of power in these plays lead to either open or hidden confrontations in these plays. There are sometimes open or sometimes hidden intra-class struggle between some ruling elite in plays such as Başòrun Gáà, Sàngó, Efúnsetán Aniwúrà, Olú Omo and Oláòrè Afòtèjoyè. In these plays there is struggle between the protagonists and their antagonists. Adébógun is engaged in an open class struggle with Şómóyè of Ègbáland in Olú Omo so that he (Adébógun) and his clique will wrench power from Şómóyè and his chiefs. The Aláké of Ègbáland in Lísàbí Agbòngbò Akàlà and the Olóyòò are engaged in an open intra-class struggle for survival in this play. Líşàbí helps the Aláké and the Ègbá masses from the tussles between them and Olóyòò's ìlari and Olóyòò himself. The initially hidden and later open intra-class struggle between Gáà and Abíòdún Adégoólú in Başòrun Gáà enables Adégoólú to wrest power from Gáà with the help of Oyaàbí the Aàrè Onà Kakañfò

who stays at Jàbàtá outside Ọyọ town. We may say that there is a hidden power tussle between Ẹfúnṣetán Aníwúrà and Látòósà from the beginning of the play until Ẹfúnṣetán kills Adétutù her pregnant slave in the play Ẹfúnṣetán Aníwúra, if we examine the views of Ẹfúnṣetán that Látòósà and the chiefs of Ibàdàn are envious of her riches (p 76) and Ẹfúnṣetán's statement that

Ha! Ọtá yò mí, ọtá yò mí, ọtá yò mí o
(O.I. 75)

Ha! I am mocked by my foe, I am mocked by
my foe, I am really mocked by my foe
(p. 75).

In these plays that depict open or hidden intra-class tussles among the ruling elite, some of the elite who are usually the antagonists are killed or they die in miserable ways. Gáà is killed after a successful war in Başòrun Gáà. Adéboḡun and his clique are sacrificed to Ọgún in Ọlú Ọmọ. Ẹfúnṣetán poisons herself because of the dehumanising condition in which she finds herself in the house of Látòósà. We will now examine the end results of intra-class struggle.

3.4.0 End Results of Intra-Class Struggle: Establishing the Status Quo

An examination of the end results of intra-class struggle in some plays show that the power of the protagonists or the antagonists are established at the end of these plays. This is to say that the status quo is established at the end of the plays. Oláòré Afòtèjoyè, Olú Omo, Morèmi, Efúnsetán Aniwúra, Basòrun Gáà, Sàngó and Lísàbí Agbòngbò Àkàlà are plays that depict the establishment of the status quo. We see the intra-class struggle in these plays as struggle to establish the status quo. Aláàfin Abiòdún, Ọbálọwọ, Şómóyè, Látòósà, Aláyemọrẹ, Aláké, Şàngó struggle with other characters in the above named plays in order to establish the power of divine rulership of kings. It is only in Oláòré Afòtèjoyè and Morèmi that we have changes of batons within the rulership class. Ọbálọwọ, Şàngó and Ọba Igbo in Oláòré Afòtèjoye, Sàngó and Morèmi respectively are the only obas who are not successful in the intra-class struggle against them. The nature and reason for the success of the struggle against them are, however, different. While the victories of Ọláòrẹ and Alayemọrẹ over Ọbálọwọ and Ọba Igbo are directly as a result

of the struggle against them, the victory over Şàngó is on the other hand the result of nemesis rather than that of the opposition against him. All emotions are weaved up in support of Ọbálọwọ by the author to make an average reader identify with the character in spite of his failure. Ọláọrẹ does not mind that Jòntolo becomes a vassal town under the rulership of Ọlọtẹ of Bọtẹ. What matters to him is to ascend the throne of Jòntolo. Hence his collusion with Ọlọtẹ to bring his own town to submission, so that Ọbálọwọ is deposed and he is enthroned instead. Since Ọláọrẹ is the second in command to Ọbálọwọ before the conflict, there is only a change of batton, especially since Ọláọrẹ's intention is not to commit class suicide, that is, abandon the ideology of the oppressing ruling class to which he belongs to enhance the ideology of the suffering masses. Though the "status quo" is sustained, it, however, is not at all enhanced in the play. As far as Şàngó is concerned, he is only partially successful against the oppositions he has at the two fronts. Against the wish of his chiefs and people and against the wish of Baálẹ of Ọyọkoro, a vassal ruler under him. He succeeded in transferring his capital from Ọyọ Ọ̀nkò to Ọyọkoro through the use of tricks. But in order to enhance his

position by instilling fears into his subjects, he demonstrates a lot of mythical powers. He, together with some of his people, however, fall victims of the magical powers and are totally annihilated by it.

Aláyémòrẹ in Morèmi succeeds in the intra-class struggle between him and Ọba Ìgbò. Ọba Ìgbò has been using masked masquerades in his struggle to recapture his original home taken by Ifẹ people. Ọba Ìgbò and his warriors are terrors to Aláyémòrẹ and his people at Ifẹ. Mòrẹmi, a queen in Ilé-Ifẹ helps Aláyémòrẹ and the Ifẹ people to see that Aláyémòrẹ is established as the supreme ruler of Ifẹ and Ìgbò.

Since aláàfin Abíòdún, Şómóyè, Látòósà, Aláyémòrẹ, and Aláké who are the incubent rulers in the plays succeed in their struggle against those who want to oust them, the status quo is clearly seen as established. The masses, therefore, continue to suffer under the yoke of the divine rulership of the ọba. We subscribe to Ìşòlá's observation in his analysis of Basòrun Gáà that,

Monarchy's struggle back to the status quo cannot be attained without the active support of Akin, the working class ... (1991:34)
(Emphasis added).

Since in all the plays the masses are used only as instruments by the ruling elite, one concludes logically that their situation will become worse under Ọláòrẹ in Ọláòrẹ Afòtẹ, Joyẹ, where the struggle favours the antagonist against the incubent leader who is the protagonist. This is primarily because Jòntolo has ironically become, in the process, a vassal town under Bọtẹ. The oppressive steps upon the people will no doubt increase, for the people will now have to serve not only their new bāalẹ but also the new suzerain lord, the Ọlọtẹ of Bọtẹ.

As can be deduced from our discussion above, the underlying ideology and commitment of the ruling elite is the affirmation of the status quo. The ideologies of the ruling elite are based on or derived either directly or indirectly from the ideology of divine rulership of kings. The ideology of divine rulership of kings is an inherited traditional one in Yorùbá plays from the Yorùbá society. According to Àtandá (1980:1923), the known leaders of Yorùbá towns in the pre-colonial society were the obas with their specific titles. An oba in a society is addressed as Aláyélúwà, alásẹ and igbákejí ọrìsà (His Excellency, the commander, and the deputy next to the divinities). There are also titles such as baálẹ and

olójá that are functionally equivalent to that of the oba but are subordinate to it. There are also titles such as basòrun and ààrē ònà kakańfò held by the military supreme rulers of some towns. Şómóyè of Ègbá for example holds the title of basòrun in Olú Omó, while Látòósà of Ìbàdàn holds that of ààrē ònà kakańfò in Efúnsetan Aniwúra. Although the position of the oba and chiefs have changed drastically since colonization, most of the intra-class struggle depict the ideology of the divine rulership of kings. These plays show some members of the ruling elite who wonder how the masses or people can resist the elite's divine rulership. For example, Olóyòḡḡ in Lísàbí Agbòńgbò Akàlà wonders how the Ègbá people can resist his divine rulership when he says:

... Èyí kò wá tún jẹ́ ìyanu báyií bí?
 Àwọn Ègbá tún fẹ́ dá ọwọ́ wú
 Ìyà ní ng ó fí sù wọn pátápátá
 Sé wọn ní àwọn kò fẹ́ sìn mí ní ...
 Lẹ́hìn ogun, wọn yóò má wá sìn mí pẹ̀lú ìyà ...
 Bí Balógun bá tí kó wọn dé, màá so okùn mọ́
 àwọn tí ó jẹ́ ọgá ní'dí ...
 Kí ọwọ́ tó tẹ àwọn ọlòtẹ́ Ègbá wònyí
 Tí ń bá èmi Aláàfin í fagagbága ... (O.I. 81-82)

... Is this not surprising?
 The Ègbá want to revolt again
 I will punish all of them severely
 Are they not protesting against serving me...
 After the war, they will continue to serve me
 with severe punishment ...
 If Balógun carries them here, I will tie the
 leaders with ropes round their waists ...
 Before these Ègbá rebels are captured
 Who are competing with me their Aláàfin ...
 (pp 81-82).

The views expressed by Olóyòò is typical of the obas in the other plays named above. They believe that no one under their suzerainty can question their authority. They share the belief that they have the power of life and death. Anyone who revolts against them will surely die.

All the plays examined above may be said to also depict the ideology of the authors who believe in the establishment of the status quo. They are the creators of characters and events in these plays. We can say that the characters are expressing the views of authors in these plays. Since the authors reveal their minds to us through the creation of characters and events, we can no doubt rightly conclude that the playwrights whose plays are examined in this section are those who believe

in the ideology of establishing the status quo. Authors who depict this ideology as we have seen in this study do not want any change. The playwrights are presenting the true and realistic situation that exist in their society. There is no period in the development of Yorùbá society in particular or Nigerian society in general when the masses are in control of government. These playwrights are not interested in establishing the power of the masses in their plays. They are not interested in an equitable distribution of wealth in their plays. They are those who depict in their plays the belief that an egalitarian society is impossible. Their views in these plays can be regarded as preachings to show that inequalities abound in the society and that, it is impossible to change these inequalities.^a

It is clear that most of the plays that depict the ideology of establishing the status quo are historical plays. Though the playwrights are not mere recorders of history (Ìṣòlá 1981:403, Ògúndèjì 1991:2-11, 1996), it is clear that there are some historical evidences in these plays. What we have seen in these historical plays

^a Aróhunmólàse, O. (1985:82-96) also examines these views in his analysis of the meaningless proverbs of Láuwo in Réré Rún.

is to some extent the depiction of historical realism in Yorùbá society, that is, that the masses cannot change the system of administration. The rulers in these plays are divine in origin, next only to the divinities.⁵ These plays tell us more of the reality of Yorùbá society from the pre-colonial and colonial period to the present time. This is the reality of the social order in Yorùbá society. Borrowing the words of Udentá (1993:46), these plays are "individualistic, escapists, illusion compounded and alienating". Our conclusion is that playwrights in their efforts to depict the status quo are no doubt committed to the rule of a few rich and not to the emancipation of the downtrodden masses.

We have seen that in the desires of some characters and authors to establish the status quo an incubent ruler can be reconfirmed as supreme leader or there may be a change of leadership where the usurper takes over. The incubent rulers in plays such as Olú Omo, Basòrun Gáà, Efúnsetán Aníwùrà and Lísàbí Agbòngbò Àkàlà as we have seen are those who are not crushed by the intra-class struggle in these plays. These incubent rulers such

5 Yorùbá people refer to their òbas as said "Aláṣe èkejí òrìṣà" (Your majesty, next to the divinities).

as Ṣómóyè, Abíòdún Adégoólú, Látòósà and Aláké are still reconfirmed supreme leaders at the end of these plays. They are still in charge of the day-to-day administration in these plays. They are the rulers who are still around to give directives and commands to their subjects in these plays. They are the fortunate leaders of the ruling elite who are not moved by the tide of time at the end of these plays. They are now well consolidated. We can say their cases are comparable with the cases of the abortive coup d'etats in contemporary Nigerian society and in many African societies. We can say that they are the àwòdí (eagle) in the Yorùbá saying: "ewu iná kí í pàwòdí, àwòdí ẹ́ kú ewu" (eagles cannot be killed by flames of fire, congratulations to you eagles). These characters are able to survive the end of the demise of their opponents as seen in the case of aláàfin Abíòdún and Gáà. In Baṣòrun Gáà, Iyá Ilé Orí tells us that aláàfin Abíòdún Adégoólú sees the end of his enemy when she says:

Kábíyèsí, ẹ́ kú rírẹ́hín ọ́tá nyín,

Èran tẹ̀mí nàà tí mo bù rẹ̀ é o,

Nwọ̀n tí rí Gáà m'Àkẹ̀sán

Gbogbo aiyé l'ó tí mbu'ran (O.I. 39)

Kábiyèsí, I greet you for surviving after
 the demise of your enemy,
 This is my own portion of the meat I cut,
 Gáà had been buried alive at Akèsán
 All people go there to cut their own portion
 of meat (p. 39)

Gáà is publicly killed in this play as abortive coup planners were publicly executed as from 1975 during the Murtala-Obásanjó's regime to the Eabangida's military era.

Olú Omo shows that the opponents in intra-class struggle are killed. Adébógun, Òní Akójènbú and others who are opposed to Šómóyè are sacrificed to Ògún in this play. Šómóyè becomes the prescribing authority.

According to Ògúndèjì (1991:45, 1996) we can infer from the historical records from Bíòbákú (1957:41) that the character of Ìṣṣòlá's Adébógun in Olú Omo:

is based on the historical Chief Akíngbógun. Chief Akíngbógun is described in historical records as the "Pharao of Igbórè". He is said to be wicked and very hostile not only to the missionaries but also to his people... But Akíngbógun is never accused of betraying Ègbá in the face of any of the Dahomian invasions. The presentation of Adébógun as a traitor is therefore probably developed by

Akinwumi Iṣòlá from the antagonistic traits of the historical Akingbógun. It is, however, not impossible that Iṣòlá's innovation, in this case, is motivated by the historical account of an unnamed Ègbá traitor who sent secretly to apprise their plans and movement, during the preparation for the Makun war in 1862 (1991:4-5)

The historical evidence stated above shows that Iṣòlá modifies history in his literary creation. He has shown in this play the reality of life in Yorùbá society. Saboteurs are bound to fail as Adébógun and his clique have failed and they are bound to be punished. These are just representative examples of these plays.

Plays that depict change of leadership where the usurper takes over in establishing the status quo as we have seen are also merely presenting the reality in Yorùbá or Nigerian society from the pre-colonial to the colonial and post-colonial periods. The title of the play Olàòré Afòtèjoyè where Olàòrè takes over the leadership of Jòntolo from Obálòwò, shows that the leadership of Olàòrè is based on rebellion. As shown by the author Olàòrè should be regarded as a rebel who should not be given any recognition. As shown by the accounts and the events in this play,

Ọláòrẹ́ has inordinate ambition to rule. He goes to Ọlótẹ́ of Bótẹ́ who had been defeated in several battles by Jòntolo to accept his leadership and to pay him homage. Since Ọláòrẹ́'s leadership is not in support of the downtrodden masses as revealed in this play his actions are condemnable. Even the Yorùbá society will frown at the action of a rebel and a saboteur as displayed in this play by Ọláòrẹ́. Ìṣòlá (1981: A04-A05) and Olúfàjō (1991), as we have earlier indicated in this study say that Ọláòrẹ́ Afòtẹ́joyẹ́ is a satire of topical issues as regards the problems in the political history of the old Western Region of Nigeria between late Chief Ọbáfẹ́mí Awólówọ́ and the late Chief Samuel Ládòkè Akíntólá. Ọlábímtán does not use the actual names of these historical giants because some of them were alive when the book was first published in 1970. Names of actual towns and events are also suppressed in the literary creation but some physical descriptions of the major actors in the play are so revealing to a reader who is familiar with the historical accounts being artistically presented.

Lísàbí Agbòngbò Àkàlà in its literary creation and in the historical accounts already examined above shows

that Ọlọyọ̀ọ̀ and Aláké of Ègbá are members of the ruling elite. Aláké can be regarded by the Ègbá people as a leader who is next to Ọlọyọ̀ọ̀, but the Ọlọyọ̀ọ̀ often troubles the Aláké and his people in the matter of paying tributes. Ọlọyọ̀ọ̀' s agents at Ègbá also commit many atrocities. This leads to a sort of open intra-class struggle between Aláké and Ọlọyọ̀ọ̀. In this struggle Aláké mobilises his chiefs and the Ègbá masses with the help of Líṣàbí so as to defeat the Ọlọyọ̀ọ̀. In the war and confrontations that ensued Aláké is victorious and he becomes well established as the overall ruler of Ègbá. This can be seen as a change of leadership from Ọlọyọ̀ọ̀ to Aláké in this play. The views expressed above are also true of historical facts in Ègbá history (Bíòbákú 1957:9-11). The news about the routing of Ọlọyọ̀ọ̀ and his armies by Aláké and his Ègbá forces is given by Ọmọ Ogun in:

... àwa ọmọ Ègbá ti sẹgun wọn.

A ti lé gbogbo wọn dànù, ...

A ti r'ẹhin odí (O.I. 100)

... we Ègbá people have defeated them.

We have sent all of them away, ...

We have seen the end of our enemies (p. 100).

As we have earlier discussed in this study, we may accept the crushing of Ṣàngó and the survival of Baálẹ̀ of Ọ̀yọ̀koro in Ṣàngó as a change of leadership. This will mean that the Baálẹ̀ of Ọ̀yọ̀koro takes over the administration of the merged Ò̀nkò and Ọ̀yọ̀koro from Ṣàngó as the next chief to Ṣàngó. As this is not a feature created by the playwright, we are only making an assumption. It seems as if this play is a literary creation of the history of aláàfin Ṣàngó as recorded by Johnson (1921: 149-152). As seen in Johnson's (1921) account the Baálẹ̀ of Ọ̀yọ̀koro or old Ọ̀yó was not made the aláàfin after the demise of Ṣàngó but, Ṣàngó's brother Àjàká who had been earlier dethroned to pave way for the ascendance of Ṣàngó as the aláàfin was recalled to the throne. This view from Johnson shows that in pre-colonial administration intra-class strifes may lead to changes of leadership as we have seen in Yorùbá plays.

We may also consider the case of Aláyémọ̀rẹ̀ and Ọ̀ba Ìgbò in Morèmi. As presented in this play there is an intra-class struggle between Aláyémọ̀rẹ̀ and Ọ̀ba-Ìgbò. Ọ̀ba-Ìgbò is in control of Ile-Ifẹ̀ the town where Aláyémọ̀rẹ̀ reigns as is evident from the incessant ravages of Ifẹ̀

by Ọba-Ìgbò and his armies. Through the help of Mọ̀rẹ̀mi in this play, Ifẹ̀ is able to defeat Ọba-Igbo. Mọ̀rẹ̀mi is, no doubt, a tragic heroine in this play (Ọ̀gúndéjì 1988). When Ọba-Ìgbò and his armies are defeated, they all come to settle at Ilé-Ifẹ̀ under the rulership of Ọ̀nì Aláiyémọ̀rẹ̀ as shown in the speech of Ọba-Ìgbò in this play. He says:

Aláiyémọ̀rẹ̀, Ọba Ifẹ̀!
 Odùduwa ni àwa mọ̀
 Gẹ̀gẹ̀ bí ọ̀ba mímọ̀ nítòótọ̀,
 A sí tún mọ̀ Ọ̀rànmiyàn pẹ̀lú
 Gẹ̀gẹ̀ bí ọ̀ba idà,
 Sùgbọ̀n ìwọ̀ Aláiyémọ̀rẹ̀
 Ni a mọ̀ tí tí láíláí ... (O.I. 56)
 Aláiyémọ̀rẹ̀, Ọba of Ifẹ̀!
 We knew Odùduwà
 As a very honest ọ̀ba,
 We also knew Ọ̀rànmiyàn
 As an ọ̀ba with a sword;
 But you Aláiyémọ̀rẹ̀
 Is now recognised by us for life (p.56)

The view expressed in this excerpt is clearly that of a submissive ruler. This view may lead us to the assumption

of the fact that Aláyémorè, a usurper now takes over the leadership in this play. As seen in Ògúndèjì's (1988) analysis of Morèmi, we may assume that Ifè people through Odùduwà came to occupy the original home of the Ìgbò and they drove Ìgbò people away. Morèmi is a literary creation to show the efforts of Ìgbò in regaining their ancestral home. This attack on Ifè is a struggle by the Ìgbò to regain their land. In the struggle of the Ìgbò to regain their land they are defeated by Ifè people. According to Johnson (1921:147):

It happened that the city of Ifè was at one time in a state of frequent commotion and unrest, owing to the repeated raids of a tribe of people called the Igbos. This continued for a series of years.

This view shows that the Ìgbò as artistically presented in Morèmi and as in history troubled Ifè for a certain period. Ifè people later emancipated themselves from these raids.

3.5.0 Concluding Remarks

As we have shown in this chapter all the plays that depict intra-class struggle are all historical plays.

The playwrights of these plays artistically present historical plays that are more interested in the social and historical judgements of individuals in a society. These plays as we have seen are committed in their ideological orientations to the power of the ruling elite and the will of specific individuals. As presented in the plays an individual can amass material wealth at the expense of the masses. Intra-class struggles in Yorùbá plays are weapons used by the authors to illustrate the problems that are inherent in Yorùbá or Nigerian society and the protests within the sub-groups in the society. It will not be totally wrong for us to reach the conclusion that the intra-class struggles depicted in the plays are being used by the playwrights to inform the masses to take advantage of this palace instability in organising a revolutionary struggle that will free them from oppressors. The masses if properly handled may use the weaknesses and loop-holes observable in intra-class struggle as grounds for launching a successful revolutionary struggle.

The historical plays examined here show us that class struggle started in the pre-colonial era in Yorùbá society in form of intra-class struggle. This intra-

class struggle as depicted in Yorùbá historical plays still exist in Yorùbá society in the colonial and post-colonial era as seen in intra-class struggle between our political leaders and the military dictators. The socio-political and economic realities in Yorùbá society as depicted in such plays as Bašòrun Gáà, Sàngó, Efúnsetán Aníwúrà, Olú Omo, Oláòré Afòtèjoyè, Lísàbí Agbòngbò Akàlà and Morèmi, show the anarchical political structures of the pre- and pro-imperialists powers.

Plays that depict intra-class struggle as shown in this study are not interested in the emancipation of the downtrodden masses in Yorùbá society. Intra-class struggle within the ruling elite in these plays does not lead to the establishment of the rule of the masses. What is seen in these plays is the lust of some members of the ruling elite to remain in power and to exchange power within themselves. A successful revolutionary struggle of the ruling elite in these plays still enthrones another ruling elite. The masses are not active participants in intra-class struggle but they are required to support the ruling elite if their struggle result into a revolutionary war within the ruling elite. Sertsova et al (1986) refer to a revolutionary war within the ruling

elite as we have said in this study as an "upper crust revolution". The struggle that leads to such revolutions is what we refer to here as intra-class revolution. The struggle depicted in these plays is among individuals. These plays as we have said portray the socio-political and economic conditions as in Yorùbá or Nigerian society in its true perspective. They are all committed to the cause of the ruling elite. They are plays that are committed to the political, social and cultural problems of the ruling elite. These are plays whose playwrights are committed to the cause of the capitalists and they show the capitalists ideological orientations. They want us to believe that it is not an easy task to change the status quo. In their own views the masses are not well educated and they are not well articulated for the task of a revolutionary change desired by them. These playwrights as depicted in their plays may feel that an ideology of changing the status quo is an illusion that cannot be achieved in contemporary Yorùbá or Nigerian society.

An examination of the historical facts from which these plays emanate show us that even though the playwrights modify history in their literary creations, the

socio-political and economic realities manifest^{ed} in history is not suppressed in these plays. The historical plays are manifestations of the intra-class struggle within the ruling elite from the pre-colonial period to the contemporary Yorùbá society. The views expressed by Ògúndèjì (1991:3, 1996) in his analysis of Iṣòlá's plays are also similar to our views. Ògúndèjì is of the opinion that even though a literary artist can transform history there are restraints to be faced in transforming the historical materials at his disposal. This is because he can be charged with the view that he is doctoring historical facts.

The views examined and expressed in this chapter will enable us to examine inter-class struggle in Yorùbá plays so as to determine how inter-class struggle is related to intra-class struggle. What are the advantages to be derived by inter-class struggle from our knowledge of intra-class struggle? Which of the two struggles is realistic in our present day dispensation? These are the questions to be critically examined and analysed in Chapter Four.

CHAPTER FOUR

INTER-CLASS STRUGGLE IN YORÙBÁ PLAYS

4.0 Introduction

Inter-class struggle as depicted in Yorùbá plays will be our focus in this chapter. We will examine issues such as causes of inter-class struggle, strategies adopted in inter-class struggle by the oppressed masses and the strategies of oppression in inter-class struggle.

4.1.0 Inter-Class Struggle

Inter-class struggle is a struggle between two opposing groups or classes. The opposing groups involved in inter-class struggle may be the oppressors and the oppressed. The oppressors may be the capitalists while the oppressed are the poor masses.

4.2.0 Causes of Inter-Class Struggle

The issue of the causes of inter-class struggle can be squarely approached through the views of Marxist literary theorists on alienation, materialism and individualism. As we have already examined in Chapter Two, Marxists perspective of the universe is based on class consciousness. They contend that social reality is not a separate background out of which literature

springs. Social reality has a shape. This shape is historical and Marxist literary critics see it as a series of struggles between opposing social classes and the forms of economic production they are engaged in. The shape is also what we can see being reflected in the literature of any society. This is mainly because particular class relationships as seen in literature and particular political, cultural and social institutions are related to the system of economic production in a fixed way. As we have examined in Chapter Two, the structure of society is what Marxist literary critics call dialectical materialism and historical materialism (Forgacs 1986: 135-136). This is to say that in a society such as the Yorùbá society what is depicted in its literature must have a class of oppressed people and a class of oppressors. We have these classes because the oppressors who are few in number are affluent and rich people who want to dominate the society. They are able to establish industries. In the industries established by these oppressors in Yorùbá society, labour is needed in order to make these industries functional. The oppressed who are poor and have no means

of livelihood are employed to work for the oppressors in their industries. The oppressors become employers of labour, while the oppressed are the employed. The labour of the oppressed is appropriated by the oppressors. In Marxist literary critics view the appropriation of the labour of the oppressed by their oppressors have caused contradictions and resulted to class struggle in every society. This is also true of the Yorùbá society depicted in Yorùbá plays. The desire of oppressors who are the capitalists in any society to amass wealth by the appropriation of the labour of the working classes is tantamount to materialism. Plays such as Réré Rún and Ayé Yẹ Wọ̀n Tán depict the desires of some oppressors in these plays to amass material wealth at the expense of the working classes. In their desires to acquire the material wealth as seen in these plays, they engage in struggles with the oppressed working classes. Onímògún, Arẹ̀sà, Olúgbón, Balógun and Akòwé Agbà are the oppressors who appropriate the labour of the oppressed workers such as Láwúwo, Adeníyí, Mátíù-Sápẹ̀nẹ̀, Bọ̀dúndé to name a few in Réré Rún. Şiyanbọ̀lá, Başòrun, Oyin, Adédùn, Ajé and Òní are the oppressors who appropriate the labour of

the oppressed classes such as Fášakin - the Principal of Ípo Grammar School, Òbílàdé - a Policeman, Àyànlọlá - a drummer and other workers in Ayé Yẹ Wọ́n Tán. These plays depict the struggles between the capitalist oppressors and the oppressed workers because of material wealth.

The capitalists desires on material acquisition of wealth is clearly expressed in these two plays. In Réré Rún, Onímògún says:

Kò burú ... Báyíí ní... Iwọ ganṣṣ, akòwé,
 b'ó bá ti d'áárọ ọlá, ní kùtùkùtù, kó àwọn
 ọlọpáá, pẹlú àwọn akódà, kí iwọ náà sí tún
 pẹlú wọn, kí ẹ máa bèèrè iwé owó-orí lẹwọq
 gbogbo ẹni t'ó bá nkọjá, àt'onílé, àt'àlejò
 (O.I. 20).

It is not bad ... This is it ... You in particular, the clerk, by tomorrow morning, very early, take some policemen, and some messengers, you yourself should go with them, you should ask of the tax receipts from all those who are passing-by, both indigenes and strangers (p.20).

Taxes collected in the town of Mògún are appropriated by Onímògún and his cohorts. Ajé, a member of the

capitalist group in Ayé Ye Wón Tán expresses the materialist principle when he says:

Bí owó bá n bẹ lówò gbajúmò ilú... Ì;
 sì tún jẹ kí n rán yín létí ilérí ilé
 isẹ wa nípa idáméwàá owó tí a ti yọ sílẹ
 fún èyin tí ẹ wà nídíf ètò yíí... Owó
 náà kí í sí í şowó kékere o (O.I. 35)

If the well-known people in the town have money ... Please let me remind you about the promise of our firm about ten percent of the money set aside for those of you who are planning for this venture ... The money involved is not small at all (p.35)

Ajé in the above excerpt refers to other capitalists by his use of the pronoun "yín" (you) and the pronominal "èyin" (you), to show us one of the various means by which capitalists acquire material wealth through contracts, ten percent kickbacks they receive from such contracts.

The reason why there is inter-class struggle in some Yoruba plays is because of the alienation of the masses by the capitalists. Alienation as we have discussed in Chapter Two, deals with appropriation of the

labour of a worker in a capitalist society. This is depicted by some Yorùbá playwrights as a cause of class struggle between the employers of labour and their employees. Even in Yorùbá plays that depict the pre-colonial Yoruba society, we see a sort of alienation that leads to class struggle between the masses and their rulers. Ègbá masses in Lisàbí Agbòngbò Akàlà,¹ are alienated by the Qlòyòò, while in Atàrí Ajànakú, the masses of Gbáńdú are alienated by Baálè of Gbáńdú, his chiefs, Aláàfin's Ilàrí and his son Tèlà. In resistance to alienation by the Qlòyòò, Qdètúndé a peasant farmer says:

Şé ẹ ní gbò?

Kóóko un, ng ò ní pa á;

Kò sí nńkan t'ó sí lè mú mi pa á (O.I. 10)

Do you hear?

That grass, I am not cutting it;

There is nothing that can make me cut it (p.10)

The views of Qlòyòò in this play also show the alienation of the masses of Ègbá by the Qlòyòò. He says:

1 As stated in Chapter Two, there is a hidden inter-class struggle in this play, if we consider the role of characters such as Qdètúndé, Mọńìgbà, women who are

... Ju gbogbo rẹ̀ lọ, ẹ̀yin ilàrí mi,
 Ẹ́ ó máa lọ láti orílúú kan dé òmíràn,
 Láti lọ máa gba àwọn ẹ̀bùn náà wá fún mi;
 Kí ng rí'hun máa fi ẹ̀ ara rindin (O.I. 4)

... Finally, you my ilàrí,
 You should go from one town to the other,
 To collect those gifts for me;
 So that I will enjoy them (p.4)

Gifts as used by Ọ̀lọ̀yọ̀ọ̀ in the above excerpt is an euphemism for tributes to be collected from the vassal towns. These tributes are appropriated by the Ọ̀lọ̀yọ̀ọ̀ while the masses of Ẹ̀gbá are alienated. This also leads to class struggle between the masses of Ẹ̀gbá and Ọ̀lọ̀yọ̀ọ̀ and his agents. The alienation of the masses of Gbáńdú is succinctly expressed in Àtàrí Àjànàkú by Gongobiàgbà when he says:

forcefully taken by the Ọ̀lọ̀yọ̀ọ̀s ilàrí and their husbands killed and the role of Líṣàbí in 'ẹ̀gbé àáró' and 'ẹ̀gbé Olórógun'. Líṣàbí may be an ally of the masses in his intention to stamp out oppression in all its ramifications. His role in mobilising the masses is an indication of his support of the oppressed masses.

... Wọn ti fi àjàgà wúwo bọ àwọn ará ilú
lọrùn ... Wọn ní mú èniyàn lò bí ẹrú, bí
ìwọfà ... (O.I. 29).

... They have oppressed the masses in the
town ... They use the masses as slaves, as
pawns ... (p. 29)

The message sent by the Baálẹ̀ and his chiefs to the
people of Gbáńdú also confirms the extent to which the
masses are alienated.

Jagunlabí: ... Baálẹ̀ sọ pé!

Lati igbà yíí lọ,

Èmẹ̀jì lẹ̀dún lẹ̀ ẹ̀ máa san isákólẹ̀ fún
Baálẹ̀ ...

Ilú yóó máa dáko ní lá kòòkan

Fún Baálẹ̀ àti iyáwó

Ati omọ́ tó bí gbogbo

Ati gbogbo Ìjòyè ... (O.I. 17)

Jagunlabí: Baálẹ̀ commands that!

As from now,

You should pay tributes twice a year to
Baálẹ̀ ...

The masses should prepare one large
farm each

For the Baálè and his wife
And all his children
And all the chiefs ... (p. 17)

All the examples above from Líṣàbí Agbòṅgbò Akala and Atàrí Ajànákú show that the masses in these plays are alienated. They have to work for the Feudal Lords who appropriate their labour. The masses are not free to work and keep all the proceeds for themselves and the upkeep of the members of their families. This persistent exploitation of the labour of the masses triggers inter-class struggle between the masses and the Feudal Lords in these plays.

Our discussion above have shown that alienation is related to materialism. This is because the masses as we have seen them are alienated from the material wealth they produce by their oppressors. As materialism is related to alienation, so also is individualism according to Marxist literary theorists. Individualism allows an individual person to accumulate material wealth for his own personal use.

4.3.0 Strategies Adopted in Inter-Class Struggle by the Oppressed Masses

The masses in their struggle with their oppressors adopt some tactics in their desire to see that they are successful. These tactics are: use of formidable unions and use of resolute leaders, and education for the conscientization of the masses.

4.3.1 Use of Formidable Unions and Resolute Leaders

Some playwrights present formidable unions and resolute leaders in order to see that the oppressed succeed in their struggle against their capitalist oppressors. The unions press for an equitable distribution of wealth in these plays. They also ask for better conditions of service for their members who are workers. The unions depicted in these plays are given different names as in Lisàbi Agbòngbò Akàlà where the masses name their struggle group 'Egbé Àáró' (pp 40-58) (a farmers union) which is later changed to 'Egbé Olórógun' (pp 62-66) (a union of warriors). The two unions may be seen as representing the passive and active stages of the struggle. The 'egbé àáró' is meant to bring the masses together and inculcate unity and trust in them since the

farmers union is used only as preparatory ground for the real attack on the oppressors' agents at the second stage of the struggle. Apart from this the first stage no doubt would act as a sort of disguise that would make the powers that be not suspicious of the revolutionary intention. The workers cooperative union in Igbà Ló Dé is named 'Ayé' (pp 54-57). It is the coming together of all the suffering masses of Ògbojò. Under this umbrella of the masses of Ògbojò they carry out a revolutionary struggle against the Resident, an agent of the British colonial administration, Ológbòjò (the oba), his chiefs and the educated elite of Ògbojò. As far as the masses are concerned, these different opposers of their purpose belong to the same class of oppressors. Through the union, the people mobilise themselves for their struggle in order to stop the exploitative collection of taxes at Ògbojò. Ògúnṣíná (1995) succinctly summarises the views of the masses of Ògbojò and their struggle against their oppressors when he says:

... the generality of his [Ológbòjò] subjects are stoutly opposed to the colonial innovations. They vehemently repudiate the Resident's order to dig pit

latrines, and violently rebuff his injunction on increment of tax rates. They are uncertain of the Ológbójò's stand on the colonial innovations. Indeed, they accuse him of timidity and administrative ineptitude. They organise themselves into a formidable pressure group under an intimidating name - "Aye" (1995:300).

Other plays where the struggling masses have such formidable unions are: Ayé Ye Wón Tán and Réré Rún. The suffering masses in Ayé Ye Wón Tán name their union for the struggle 'egbé aláfowósowópò' (cooperative union). The capitalists in this play indirectly acknowledges that the cooperative union is a formidable one when Baṣòrun says:

... Ọrò tí egbé alájùmọ̀ṣe yí sí tí fẹ́ẹ́
dì íṣọ̀nu láàrín ilú. Gbogbo m̀ẹ̀kúnnù ilú
lọ wà nínú rẹ̀ (O.I. 3^a).

.. The cooperative union is a problem to be reckoned with in the town. All the masses in the town are members (p.3^a).

In Réré Rún the union is named 'egbé àwon òsìṣẹ̀' (workers' union), which is broken down to sub-unions such as that of the carpenters, sawyers, painters, traders, blacksmiths and

office workers as implied in this speech by Mátíù

Awon egbeẹ káfińtà ... fi àádọta nálrà ẹ
 ọrọnọwọ

Ọun náà ni yíí o ...

Èmi náà, orúkọ mi ni Mátíù Sápẹné.

Èmi náà ni onóri naginagi, tàbííí ...

gbéginódò

Mo mú owó ẹgbẹ tiwa náà wá, ọgọta nálrà (O.1.23)

Carpenters union ... send fifty naira for help

This is it ...

Myself, my name is Matthew Sápẹné.

I am the head of sawyers, or timber carriers.

I bring our own union's money, sixty naira (P.23)

The sub-unions in this play cooperate in the forming of a formidable union in their struggle against their capitalist oppressors. Àtari Ajàńàkú is another play where the masses of Gbándú represented by Gòngòbiàgbà, Jẹńriyin, Ayọmẹyẹ, Igbàroọlá, Tọyọbọ and Ariwoọlá cooperate in order to liberate themselves from their oppressors. They cooperate in their desire to form a government named 'Kónkónbíló' where there would be no king, no chiefs and where everyone will live a life of equal opportunity. The masses in this play have no name for their cooperative group. In spite of this, the cooperative feature exists.

We have shown in the examples above how the poor suffering masses in Yorùbá plays form formidable unions in their struggles against their oppressors. It is essential to examine the importance of these unions for the masses' struggle. The views we enunciate in our analysis cuts across all the plays we examine.

The poor masses in these plays know the importance of unity in their struggles against their oppressors. They know that it is through unity that they can achieve their desired objectives. It is a common saying that "united we stand, divided we fall". Because the oppressed masses do not want to fail in their struggle, they emphasise the need for them to cooperate. We liken the idea of cooperation preached by the masses in these plays to what Goldmann (1973:115) says about the origin of a work's mental structure. According to Goldmann a work's mental structure can be seen in its social behaviour. This social behaviour is not from the will of different individuals but from two or more individuals acting as one entity. This is explained in the way people cooperate to perform certain tasks. Goldmann asserts that, a great writer is the one who is able to elaborate the mental structure of a group so that the author's literary creation

could relay back to the group, a sort of sharpened awareness of that structure. A writer does not simply reproduce the collective consciousness in a mechanical way but he puts forward in a considerable manner the degree of the structural coherence which the mutual consciousness has so far attained in a rough and ready fashion. This makes a literary work a collective achievement through the individual consciousness of its author. This is an achievement that will show the group what it is moving towards without its knowing it. The perspective of the authors of these plays no doubt agrees with that of Goldmann when they use individual characters such as Láuwo in Réré Rún (p.27), Fáṣakin in Ayé Yē Wōn Tán (p. 41) and Adégún in Ìgbà Ló Dé (p. 54) to advise the oppressed classes to cooperate in order to free themselves from the clutches of their oppressors. An example, from Ayé Ye Wōn Tán will suffice. Fáṣakin stresses the need for unity among the oppressed classes at Ìpo so that the oppressors cannot break the stronghold of the masses struggle.

Fáṣakin: Bì oyin bá ṣù, tí oyin bá n lẹ, taa ló lè dúró doyin? ...

Àlṣòwòṣòrìn ejò ní n ṣekú pa wón ...

Oun ló difá fún ẹgbẹ Alájùmòṣe yíí o. Kò sí ohun tí a lè dá ṣe láìso ọwọ pọ, láífmò ṣòkan o (O.I. 41).

Fáṣakin: If the swarm of bees assemble, if the swarm of bees move, who can wait for the swarm of bees?... Being not able to move together by snakes cause their deaths... He divines for this Cooperative Union. There is nothing that we can do without cooperation, without unity (p. 41).

The masses in these plays use cooperation as a weapon to mobilize themselves to support their struggle against their oppressors. The masses use their unions in tackling their problems in their struggle against oppression. They use their unions as their mouth-piece. In some instances they send delegations to their oppressors. An example, from Igbà Ló Dé is interesting. Here members of "Ayé" send a delegation led by their chairman to Ológbojò.

Alága: Gbogbo m̀̀kunǹ̀ Ogbójò yí pátápátá lé rán wa sí yin ...

Àwọn Ayé ní àwọn kò ní san ju sílè m̀̀ta àábò tí àwọn tí ǹ̀ san t̀̀lè l̀̀, è b́́a pa àwọn p̀̀l̀̀b̀̀, iṣ̀̀é tí ẁ̀n rán wa sí yin. ǹ̀yí (O.I. 57)

Alága: All the masses of Ógbojò sent us to you. Ayé people say they are not paying more than three shillings and six pence (35 kobo) which they were paying before, even if you pound them flat, that is the message they ask us to relay to you (p. 57).

Gòngòbíàgbà leads the delegation of the masses to the oppressors at Gbáńdú in Àtari Àjànàkú (pp 3-10). He says:

... ilú rí i pé mo kún ojú iẁ̀n ní ẁ̀n ṣ̀̀e rán mí (O. 1. 3)

... The masses count me worthy that is why I am sent (p. 3).

The masses in their Unions reason together and plan how they will solve their problems in their revolutionary struggles. They plan the strategies and take decisions on how to strike if their oppressors punish them as in Igbà Ló Dé (p. 75), Líṣàbí Agbòngbò Àkàlà (p.83). The masses

form unions in order to help one another and to see that they consolidate their efforts. Apart from helping one another, they also use these unions as avenues of teaching one another about the revolutionary processes and the need for them to cooperate in their struggles as in Lisàbi Agbongbo Akàlà (pp. 53-54, p. 83) and Ayé Yé Wón Tán (p. 35). The masses in their unions are also taught the importance of not receiving bribes as this will weaken their cooperation for revolutionary struggles. An example from Ayé Yé Wón Tán is illuminating.

Fáṣakin: ... Èni tó ń fún ni ní ribá kí í ṣòré ẹni, ó ń fọbọ lóni ni. Nígba tí ẹni kan fẹẹ jí ẹgbẹrún náírà, owó gbogbo wa, tí ó wáá fún iwọ ní náírà márùún kí o má ba à pariwo, o ò rí í pé ó fọbọ lò ọ? (O.I. 42).

Fáṣakin: ... He who gives one bribe, is not one's friend, he is making a fool of one. When somebody wants to steal a thousand naira, the money that belongs to all of us, he then gives you only five naira so that you will keep quiet, don't you know that he is calling you a fool? (p. 42).

Another related example is in Réré Rón (p. 28). The masses in these plays detest bribery because they know that if they take bribes, their capitalist oppressors will use bribes as baits in infiltrating into their ranks and thereby breaking their formidable unions.

If there are no formidable unions and cooperation among the oppressed ones they will not be able to carry out successfully their struggle against their oppressors. The importance of their unions and cooperation is to enable them wield power so that their aim of forming an alternative government that is devoid of oppression may be realized. These unions as we have seen will enable the masses in these plays to be able to resist in some ways the negative forces of their oppressors. Another strategy used by the masses in their struggles is the use of resolute leaders as we will examine below.

The leadership in inter-class struggle is one of the issues depicted artistically by playwrights who examine issues of inter-class struggle and the use of formidable unions in their plays. There cannot be inter-class struggle if we do not have leaders who will lead the masses in their struggle. These are leaders who

have leadership qualities, good vision for a revolutionary struggle and who are acceptable to the masses. They are also resolute leaders who are determined to lead the masses in a successful revolt.

Plays such as Réré Rún, Kòseégbé², Ayé Yẹ Wón Tán, Atàrí Ajànakú, Igbà Ló Dé and Líṣàbí Agbongbò Akàlà present determined leaders of the masses such as Láwúwo, Máko, Qládépò and Fáṣakin, Gòngòbíàgbà, Alága-Adégún and Líṣàbí. Some of these leaders stand out of their classes in these plays to ally with the downtrodden masses. These leaders transcend their class view or vision to champion the cause of the masses. Máko, Qládépò, Fáṣakin, Gòngòbíàgbà and Líṣàbí belong to this group. Máko - the head of Customs Department, Qládépò - a prince of Ìpo, Fáṣakin - the Principal of Ìpo Grammar School, Gòngòbíàgbà - the son of a chief in Gbáńdú and Líṣàbí - an Egbá chief all transcend their class to ally with the masses. Some of these leaders are able to mobilize the masses in these

2 Kòseégbé is examined with these category of plays because of our assumption that Máko the Customs Officer in this play may be employed or sponsored by a pro-masses government. It is because of this assumption that we regard Máko as a resolute leader of the masses. He allys with the masses in this play.

plays.

Some of these resolute leaders are good orators who know the techniques of mobilising the masses for the cause of their struggles. These leaders know how to arouse the consciousness of the masses in their mobilization efforts. Sometimes these leaders resort into sentimental arguments in order to mobilize them for struggles against their oppressors. They see to it that there is no disintegration among the masses in their mobilization efforts. Examples of mobilization efforts by the resolute leaders of the masses are taken from Réré Rún (pp 26-33) and Líṣàbí Agbòngbò Akàlà (pp 52-66) Láwúwo in Réré Rún and Líṣàbí in Líṣàbí Agbòngbò Akàlà use oratory in mobilising the masses. The masses in these plays show that they fully support the steps being taken by Láwúwo and Líṣàbí in the development of the workers struggle against their oppressors.

It is through the "àáró" that Líṣàbí in Líṣàbí Agbòngbò Akàlà mobilizes the masses to support the struggle against Ọlọyọ́ọ́. Líṣàbí helps other members of the masses in working in their farms but he does not invite them to help him in his farm because of his desire

to use the masses for his revolutionary struggle against Ọlọ́yọ́. The masses are mobilized by Líṣàbí when the 'egbe àáró' is changed to 'egbé olórógun'.

LÍṢÀBÌ: È ẹun,
 Kò sí idúró,
 Mo rò pé gbogbo yín ni ẹ ti mò pé
 Àáró ti n kan ọ̀pọ̀lọ̀pọ̀ nínú wà,
 O wá yẹ kí ng sọ fún yín
 Pé àáró náà wá kan èmi pàápàá lóníí...

ÀWỌN ỌMỌ ẸGBÈ: O ẹun, ó ti yá
 Ẹ́é oko kíkọ ni tàbí igbó ẹ́ṣá
 Tàbí ọ̀nà yíyẹ? ...

LÍṢÀBÌ: Ibi tí tẹ̀mi ti wá yàtò ni èyí,
 Iṣẹ̀ tẹ̀mi kí í ẹ̀e oko ẹ́ṣá,
 Èbè kíkọ tàbí ọ̀nà yíyẹ
 Iṣẹ̀ tẹ̀mi niyí
 Bí ẹ bá ti gbọ́ iró ibon kàà látí Igbèhin wá
 Mo pa ajẹlẹ̀ Ọlọ́yọ́ tí n bẹ̀ lódò mi niyẹn,
 Àáró tẹ̀mi ni pé kí olúkúlùkù
 Bẹ̀rẹ̀ sí pa gbogbo ajẹlẹ̀ tí n bẹ̀ lódò wọ̀n.
 Ọ̀rọ̀ mi kò jù bẹ̀ẹ̀ lọ
 Àáró mi niyẹn o (O.I. 72-73).

LÍṢABI: I thank you,
 There is no time to waste,
 I think all of you have known that
 Some of us have taken their 'àáró'
 It is necessary for me to tel. you
 That it is my turn to take my 'àáró' today...

AWQON QMỌ EGBẸ: Thank you, we are ready
 Is it making of heaps or clearing
 the bush
 Or hoeing the pathway? ...

LÍṢABI: This is where my own differs,
 My assignment is not clearing the farm,
 Making of heaps or hoeing the pathway.
 This is my assignment
 If you hear the sound of a gun shot "kàà"
 from Igbèhìn
 That means I have killed the Qlọyọọ's "ajélé"
 in my place,
 My own "àáró" is that everyone
 should start killing the "ajélé" in their
 places.
 That is all I have to say
 That is my "àáró" (pp 72-73).

Lísàbí is able to mobilize the Ègbá masses through "àáró"
 to take up arms against the Qlọyọọ's ilàrí who oppress
 Ègbá people. The leaders examined above see that there
 is no disintegration among the masses in their struggles

The leaders of the masses in these plays believe in an equitable distribution of wealth. These leaders identify with the downtrodden masses. They also detest the capitalist views of materialism, alienation and individualism and they want a type of government where there will be no king, no chiefs, where every person will live a life of equal opportunity. They talk of a life of "you-are-not-greater-than-me-I-am-not-greater-than-you". These views are well illustrated by Gōngòbíàgbà in Àtárí Ajànáku (p. 49) and in:

... Wọn ti fi àjàgà wúwo bọ àwọn ará ilú lórùn. Wọn ní jayékáyé. Wọn ní mú èniyàn lò bí ẹrú, bí iwọfà. Gbígba àbètẹlẹ ... Wọn ní gba oko olóko fún ẹlómíràn. Wọn ní gba ilé onílé, wọn gba ilẹ onílẹ. Wọn ní fẹni tí kò tọ joyè ... (O.I. 29)

... They have started increasing the burden of the townspeople. They are doing what they like. They force people to use them as slaves, pawns. Receiving bribes ... They take farms forcefully from some people to be given to others. They confer chieftaincy titles on unworthy people ... (p.29).

These are the things that the capitalists in these plays do that are not in line with what the resolute leaders of the masses want. The resolute leaders of the masses want the removal of the heavy burden placed on the masses. They want an equitable distribution of the communal lands. Apart from the leaders' views of an equitable distribution of wealth, the purposeful and resolute leaders of the masses struggle also believe in fighting for the cause of the masses at the expense of their lives.

The leaders of the masses revolutionary struggles in these plays believe in fighting for the cause of the masses at the expense of their lives. The capitalists in plays that depict resolute and purposeful leaders who want to fight on behalf of the masses accuse such leaders of causing confusion and inciting the masses to revolt. Such resolute leaders are sometimes charged to court or detained so as to ruin their carriers. For example, Láwúwo is detained in Réré Rún and charges of incitement are levelled against him by the capitalists. In Ayé Yé Wón Tán; Faşakin is accused by the capitalists of inciting his students against the capitalists. The

attempts by some capitalists in these plays to lure the resolute leaders to their side usually result in failure. Láuwo refuses the offer of the capitalists in Réré Rún and their attempt to lure him to their side because they refuse to offer the masses anything.

Láuwo: Mo kọ àbètélẹ nyín
 Mo sí mbèèrè fún iyípadà rere fún àwọn
 ọ̀sìṣẹ̀. Ẹ̀ tètè mójútó o wéréwéré
 Àí jẹ̀ bẹ̀ẹ̀, ... àídá wọn lóhùn lásíkò ...
 a sẹ̀sẹ̀ bẹ̀rẹ̀ ní, díẹ̀ l'ẹ̀ tíì rí (O.I. 50)

Láuwo: I reject your bribe.
 I am asking for a good change in the
 condition of the workers. You should *see*
 to this immediately.
 Without that, ... without
 satisfying them in time, ...
 we have just started, you have
 just seen a little problem (p. 50).

Ìṣòlá (1981:407-408) succinctly enumerates the qualities of Láuwo when he says:

... Láuwo, the union leader and a committed activist, does not believe in any compromise.

The plan of the capitalists to destroy Láuwo is realized when his wife Morênikê dies and Láuwo's mental sanity is shattered.

Fáşakin and Oládépò are the leaders of the masses in Ayé Yẹ Wọn Tán who die fighting for the masses' cause. They fight for the release of a piece of land for their cooperative farming. The actions of the capitalist in sharing the land among themselves after giving a large portion of the land to Ajé's contracting firm to build an ultra modern hotel is exposed by Fáşakin to the masses in:

... Şé ẹ rí 1, níbi tí a gbọ ọrọ yíí dé,
lòòótọ wọn ò tíí kọwé sọ fún wa o, a tí
mọ pé wọn tí pe àpèjẹ kan látí dá àwọn
agbaşẹşẹ tí yíò bá wọn kọ ilé ọhún lólá ...
(O.I. 44)

... Do you know, what we heard about this matter, really they have not written to inform us, we know that they are organising a luncheon for honouring the contractors who are going to build the houses tomorrow...
(p. 44).

The resolute leaders of the masses such as Oládépò and

Fásakin are killed by hired assassins in this play. Fásakin goes to the luncheon party of the capitalists in this play at the expense of his life to know what the capitalists are up to. His intention is to fight for the cause of the masses until they succeed in their struggle against the capitalists. Fásakin is killed after his speech in the excerpt quoted above (p.157). This leads to an uprising against the capitalist oppressors who are finally crushed.

Plays such as Àtárí Àjànàkù, Ìgbà Ló Dé and Kòseégbé also depict leaders who are prepared to fight for the cause of the masses at the expense of their lives. These leaders are Gòngòbíàgbà, Adégún and Máke. Gòngòbíàgbà fights for the masses of Gbáńdú at the expense of his life. His mates also support him. Gòngòbíàgbà is the bold man who is able to tell Ìlárí, Baálẹ̀ and the chiefs of Gbáńdú about the opposition of the masses to their oppression. The Ìlárí, Baálẹ̀ and the chiefs plan to kill Gòngòbíàgbà and his mates. Ayọ̀mẹ̀yẹ̀, one of the mates of Gòngòbíàgbà confirms this when he says:

... àyàfí bí wọn bá tètè fẹ̀ ojú àwọn ọ̀dọ̀
nàà kù (O.I. 43)

... unless you quickly destroy the youths (p. 47).

The Báalẹ̀, the chiefs and Ìlàrí are not quick in destroying Gòngòbíàgbà and his mates. The youth kill all the chiefs and Baálẹ̀ and establish communism at Gbáńdú. Gòngòbíàgbà and his mates support the cause of the masses until they are arrested, detained in prison, tried and finally freed by the Aláàfin of Ọ̀yọ́.³ There are some plays that depict leaders' good visions for revolutionary struggles.

The leaders of the struggle are also depicted as having good visions about the masses or workers' revolutionary struggles. The playwrights share the view that workers or the masses should struggle so that they

3 It seems as if Láyuyì Ọ̀gúnníran in this play is not interested in Marxists views about the dictatorship of the proletariat. We see that a successful revolutionary struggle of the masses is crushed in this play. We can also argue that Ọ̀gúnníran in this play is telling us about the realistic position in contemporary Yorùbá society. In an interview with Láyuyì Ọ̀gúnníran at the Department of Linguistics and African Languages, University of Ibadán on the 23rd of August, 1995, he told us that he is merely telling his readers that the society is not yet ripe for communism. Ọ̀gúnníran's views are debatable. Our playwrights should teach the masses how they can struggle successfully against the oppressive forces in their society.

can free themselves from the clutches of their oppressors. Another important vision of some of these leaders is that the masses should form an alternative government where all members in a society will be equal. They believe that the material wealth in a society should be evenly shared among the people. Gòngòbíàgbà for instance in Atàrí Àjànàkú as we have shown holds the view of establishing communism. He wants a government of equal opportunities named Kònkónbiló⁴. The views of Láuwo in Réré Rún also show that he has a vision that the workers in this play will succeed in their struggle against their capitalist employers. He may also be said to hold the view that the workers will form a workers government that is devoid of oppression

⁴ It may be argued that Láuwo Ògúnníran uses the events in his play Atàrí Àjànàkú, to predict the collapse of the Socialist Structures in the Union of Soviet Socialist Republic (U.S.S.R.). (This is inferred from our interview with Láuwo Ògúnníran, see footnote No.3). If this opinion is correct, we may say that Ògúnníran is in support of the capitalist system of government in Yorùbá society. We may also argue that the view of George Orwell that, "all animals are equal, but some are more equal than the others", is supported by Láuwo Ògúnníran in this play. See also the views of "Arápáyagi" about Gòngòbíàgbà and his colleagues (pp 56-62).

after a successful struggle.

Láwúwo: ... A ó borí dandan ni ...
A ó ṣṣégun wọn ... ọjọ́ ẹlẹ́sínwọn ku
ọ́la (O.I. 30).

Láwúwo: ... We will surely win ...
We will be victorious ...
They will be disgraced in a matter of
days (p. 80)

Líṣàbí is confident in Líṣàbí Agbòngbò Àkàlà that the
Ègbá masses in their struggle will defeat the Ọlọ́yọ́ọ́ and
his ìlàrí and Ègbá will become a free nation.

Líṣàbí: Bí ó tí wù kí àwọn ọ́tá tí lágbára tó ...
Àwa l'a ó máa borí wọn (O.I. 66).

Líṣàbí: No matter how strong the enemies are ...
We shall defeat them (p. 66)

Líṣàbí has the vision that Ègbá masses will defeat the
oppressive forces of Ọlọ́yọ́ọ́ and a free government of the
masses will be established in Ègbá.

The resolute and determined leaders of the masses
in the plays named above are whole-heartedly accepted by
the struggling classes. The masses in these plays do not
question the authorities of their leaders in the plays.
Even in plays where the masses revolutionary struggle fail,

majority of these masses support their acclaimed leaders. Even though Láuwo's leadership in Réré Rún is doubted along the line towards the climax of the play by members of the working class, he was loved by the workers for not allowing the oppressors to succeed in infiltrating the ranks of the workers by appointing Ìdòwú as a rival union leader. The dialogue among Mopélólá, Adéníyì and Kàrímù shows how Láuwo is accepted by the masses in Réré Rún. The dialogue is revealing and it shows that workers know the worth of Láuwo in their struggle with their capitalist employers.

Mopélólá: Awon ọga Láuwo mà kọ o. Awon ọgá Láuwo kọ o...

Kàrímù: È, L'o si ní ọgá ńpè wá! Ọgá tiyin nù un, ki í ẹ tiwa.

Adéníyì: Yù sí í! Awa ò ní ọgá méjì, kàrè ọgá Láuwo ...

Kàrímù: Ọkọ Onímògún, ọkọ gbogbo igbimò (O.I.9)

Mopélólá: I am not referring to Láuwo, our master. I am not talking of our master Láuwo...

Kàrímù: È (in disgust). And you say our master wants to see us!

That is your own master, he is not our

master.

Adeníyi: You see! We have no other master except our master Láwúwo ...

Kàrímù: The terror to Onímògún, the terror to all members of the council (p. 9).

The masses in Ayé Ye Wón Tán respect and honour Ọládépò in their struggle against their oppressors. He is accorded the honour of an oba among them and addressed as 'Kábíyèsí' (Your majesty). Any time he wants to address the masses they hail him and honour him. He is the only prince of Ìpo during the tussle for Ìpo stool who presented an ideology of an equitable distribution of wealth among the people of Ìpo. He does not receive the support of the kingmakers of Ìpo who constitute the oppressing group.

The capitalist oppressors in this play fear Fáşakin as the leader of the masses because he is loved by all the masses and all the students in Ìpo town. Fáşakin - the Principal of Ìpo Grammar School is accused of teaching his students what he is not expected to teach them.⁵

5 This view is comparable to the views expressed by Abisóyè Panel that looked into Students and Staff Crises at Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, during General Babangida's regime. The panel is of the

The oppressors accuse Fásakin of teaching his students to be rude to them. He teaches his students how to preach about the oppression of the capitalists in Ípo. The masses in Átárí Ajánàkú recognise Gòngòbíàgbà and his colleagues as their leaders. When Gòngòbíàgbà establishes the power of the poor masses devoid of oppression and exploitation, he enjoys the total support of all. The successful struggle that leads to revolt and change in administration is announced by Jagunlabí the town-crier, and the townspeople are happy about the change. This shows that they accept the leadership of Gòngòbíàgbà and his mates (p.55). Plays such as Igbá Ló Dé, and Líṣàbí Agbòngbò Akàlá depict acceptable leaders of the masses such as Adégún who is named 'Alága Ayé' and Líṣàbí who is nicknamed 'Agbòngbò Akàlá' respectively. All the views expressed about the good and resolute leaders of the masses in their struggle against the oppressors show the ideology and commitment of the leaders to the cause of the masses.

view that University Lecturers teach what they are paid not to teach. Íṣṣlálá in this play shows the views of the oppressors in our society.

We will now examine how the resolute and determined leaders of the masses use education for the conscientization of the masses as one of the strategies in their struggle. We will examine the levels of education for the conscientization of the masses.

4.3.2 Education for the Conscientization of the Masses

4.3.2.1 Use of Education for the Conscientization of the Masses.

Playwrights such as Oḷádẹ̀jọ̀ Òkédìjì, T.A.A. Ládélé, Láwuyì Ògúnníran, Olú Owólabí and Akínwùmí Iṣọlá develop the consciousness of the masses in their plays by educating them on how they can unite to fight their oppressors and be able to form an alternative proletariat rule instead of that of their capitalist oppressors. The envisaged rule of the proletariat is a classless society. According to Marcheray (Forgacs 1986:151), literature is 'one of the apparatus in our education system'. Our use of education in this study has nothing to do with the Western oriented education. Education as used here is for the creation of awareness and the development of the consciousness of the masses for a revolutionary struggle. Revolutionary

struggle can only be attained when the masses know the meaning of the struggle and what they will gain in it. The consciousness of the masses is also aroused through their consciousness about the ideology of the masses and their commitment to the cause of a revolutionary struggle. Commitment of the masses to the cause of a revolutionary struggle will later lead to a struggle that will lead to a successful revolt of the masses. Once the masses are successful in their revolt against their oppressors, they will establish the rule of the proletariat where there will be equal opportunities for every member of the society. All the views about class struggle, ideology and the commitment of the masses can only be achieved through the development of the consciousness of the masses. This implies the education of the masses about their conditions and its implication and what they can do to achieve progress.

The educators of the masses in plays such as Réré Rún, Igba Ló Dé and Líṣábi Agbòngbò Akàlà to name a few are the same as the leaders treated above in 4.3.1 who believe in the importance of education for the conscientization of the masses for the purpose of helping them in

in their class struggle. The masses are, in the process made to realise the state of their historical and material conditions. They are taught to develop themselves in a socialist world outlook. The masses training in Yorùbá plays is comparable to what Duncker (1962:219) calls training in the "peoples school". People's school according to Duncker is a universal school under socialism. We can infer from Duncker's view that the masses in Yorùbá plays are educated in informal universal schools by their educators because the educators know that:

... contemporary education is still designed to perpetrate the inequalities of the existent class system and to reinforce the capitalist status quo (Etzioni-Halevy 1981:192)

Marxists prefer the same type of education for all members of a society. According to Duncker (1962:219) under socialism, everyone can learn everything. He believes that, human beings are versatile by nature. Only tempo and teaching method may need to be different. According to Lenin (1948:28), in the education of workers' party, Marxism educates the vanguard of the proletariat

that is capable of assuming power and leading the whole people in a society to socialism. The proletariat should direct and organise the new system, by being the teacher, the guide, the leader of all the working and exploited people in organising their social life without the bourgeoisie and against the bourgeoisie. Yorùbá playwright create an awareness in the minds of the masses by presenting the teachers of the masses as educators, using different methods of educating the masses such as creating awareness, planning and implementation of their strategies of struggles by the use of oral poetry and other relevant aspects of Yorùbá life and institutions. Oral poetry used are folksongs, folktales, Ifá stories and proverbs.

The teachers of the masses who are responsible for teaching the masses by creating awareness in them, planning ways of struggles and implementation of the strategies of struggles are also educators. The educators of the masses are those who plan strategies for mobilising the masses in their revolutionary struggles against their oppressors. As teachers we can say that they are more knowledgeable than their mates in revolutionary ideologies and commitments. This is why they have to educate the masses in

order to achieve their aims and objectives. We use the word educators as used by Duncker (1962: 219- 264), because the teachers in these plays are educators for socialism in a universal school where every one is educated. According to Duncker:

The first (necessary measure) would be a general education for all ... without exception ... an education which is the same for all and continues to the time when individual is capable of entering the society ... (1962:129)

In this system of education, young men are educated on the whole system of production. Educators of the masses in the Yoruba plays are Oládépò, Fášakin in Ayé Yẹ Wón Tán, Láuwo in Réré Rún, Lisàbi in Lisàbi Agbòngbò Akàlà Gòngòbíàgbà in Atàrí Ajànakú and Adégún in Igbà Ló Dé. It is because of their conviction about the masses' revolutionary struggle that they are able to convince and carry the masses along with them in these plays. These educators are able to build socialism by emphasising socialist consciousness. They may have problems in achieving this, but they are the people who stand in front of the people in socialism. In achieving the

laudable aims and objectives in educating the masses in Yoruba plays, the playwrights use the resolute and determined leaders of the masses to teach by creating awareness, plan ways of educating the masses and how they can implement the tactics they have learnt in their struggles against oppression.

The leaders of the masses use education as a means of creating awareness in the masses.

4.3.2.2 Education for Creating Awareness in the Masses

The purposeful leaders of the masses educate them on solidarity, truthfulness and honesty as a means of mobilising them for their struggles. They emphasise the value of solidarity, honesty and faithfulness to the masses and the cause of this struggle. The masses in the plays are educated on the need to organise a successful revolt against their oppressors. They are educated on the need for solidarity for mutual help and a common bond of collective men. The educators hammer on the need for unity in their struggles. For example, Fáṣakin in Ayé Yẹ Wón Tán educates the masses on the need for solidarity and unity. He says:

Kín ni ó ní kó iyà jẹ wá? ...

... àìṣe ara wa l̄òkan... (O.I. 41)

Why are we suffering? ...

... not being able to make ourselves one

... (p. 41)

Láwúwo in Réré Rún indirectly educates the masses on the need for solidarity in their struggles against their oppressors when he says:

Ṣùgbón ẹ má mikàn. E'ó ṣe kùmò, b'ó ṣe

Kóndó, bí mo bá tí p'ó yá ni ẹ yọgi ...

Gbogbo wọn l'a ó kó lógbón ... (O.I. 27)

But you should not fear. If it is cudgels, if it is batons, if I say it is time you should bring out sticks ... We are going to teach all of them sense ... (p.27)

In some cases the masses are expected to take an oath in order to ensure that they are faithful and honest to the cause of the masses struggle. This idea of truthfulness and honesty is also to consolidate the idea of solidarity. Adégún in Igbà Ló Dé in order to impress the idea of truthfulness and honesty to the cause of the masses revolt says:

Njẹ́ kí ètè olúkúlukù mọ̀tẹ, k'ẹnu mọ́'nu.
 Ẹni tí yóò bá f'ètè m'ètè k'ó fí irin
 Kékeré yíí kan ẹnu ... Ẹyin náà mọ
 itumọ̀ ohun tí ẹ ní ẹ se yíí o. Ẹ ní mulẹ
 ní yíí o, ẹ máse dalẹ, ẹni bá dalẹ, á
 bá'lẹ lẹ (O.I. 51).

I say you should keep secret secret. Any
 one who wants to keep secret secret should
 touch his mouth with this small iron...
 You all know the meaning of what you are
 doing. You are taking an oath, you should
 not make any abomination, any one who
 makes an abominable thing will definitely
 die (p. 51).

Fáṣakin in Ayé Yẹ Wọ̀n Tán also educates the masses on the
 need for truthfulness and honesty when he says:

... Awọ̀n aṣáko àti àwọ̀n agbèyìnbebojé
 ló ní fà wá sẹhìn o... Ẹni tó ní fún ní
 ní ribá, kíí ẹ̀rẹ ẹni, ó ní fòbọ̀ lẹni
 ní ... (O.I. 42)

... Those who have gone astray and
 saboteurs are those drawing us back...
 One who gives one bribe, is not a friend,
 he is fooling one ... (p. 42)

Fáṣakin in this play educates the masses that they should be truthful and honest in their actions. If the masses are not truthful and honest and they receive bribes, those who give them bribes are merely cheating them. The money the oppressors give as bribes belong to the whole society. These oppressors merely give a token of the huge amount stolen as bribes to the masses. Fáṣakin educates the masses that if they should receive bribes they are merely oppressing themselves as they will be slaves for life. The masses according to these educators named above should be truthful and honest in their struggle against their oppressors. Another leader who educates the masses on the need for faithfulness and honesty in their revolutionary struggle against their capitalist oppressors is Láwúwo in Réré Rún. He advises the workers as follows:

Iṣéṣe tiyín ni kí ẹ múra sí, nítorí
òrìṣà tí gbòlẹ̀ ọ sí ... (O.I. 27).

A ńgẹ̀ nyín lówọ̀, ẹ̀ tún ńbọ̀ ọ̀rùka!
Bí mo ti ńkẹ̀ tó, bí mo ti ńparọ̀wa,
ẹ̀ tún ńfẹ́é maa ré èèsun dà sínú ìbú
(O.I. 29).

You should face your own work squarely, because there is no divinity that supports a lazy person ... (p.27). We cut your hands, yet you put on rings! Even as I shout, as I even warn you, you still want to scoop water from the spring to fill the large expanse of water (p.29)

When workers face their work squarely and are not lazy, they will be truthful and honest in their place of work. By scooping water from the spring to fill a large expanse of water the educator vividly illustrates the stupidity of the workers actions in supporting their oppressors.

4.3.2.3 Methods in Educating the Masses

Educators in plays such as Lísàbí Agbòngbò Àkàlá, Ayé Yẹ Wọ̀n Tán, Réré Rún and Ìgbà Ló Dé use some methods in educating the masses. The leaders who are also the educators know the importance of cooperation in Yorùbá life and institutions. Cooperation is therefore explored as a means of educating the masses in their struggles. Lísàbí uses the 'àáró' a system by which farmers work in their farm in rotation as a means of helping themselves and as a means of inculcating the spirit of cooperation in

Mobilization folksongs are used as a means of educating the masses on the importance of their struggles. An example of such mobilising folksongs making them to be alert to their responsibilities is the one given by 'Onílù àáró' drums in Líṣàbí Agbòngbò Akàlá:

È ṣe gírí, è dídè,
 È ṣe ṣàṣà, è dídè.
 È ṣe gírí, è dídè,
 È ṣe ṣàṣà, è dídè (O.I. 51)

Be quick, arise;
 Be brisk, arise.
 Be quick, arise,
 Be brisk, arise (p. 51)

Fáṣàkin in his educational plan in using 'Egbé aláfowósowópò' as a means of educating the masses uses a folksong in mobilising them. Fáṣàkin sings:

Oyin ṣù,
 Oyin ní lẹ!
 Oyin á ṣù,
 Oyin á pọn roro (O.I. 41)

There is a swarm of bees,
 The swarm of bees is moving!

There will be a swarm of bees,
The swarm of bees is danger red (p.41)

These folksongs indirectly educate the masses on the need for cooperation and that the idea of laziness will not help them in their revolutionary struggles against their oppressors. They should cooperate in order to be able to help themselves in their struggles. Fáşakin's song educates the masses indirectly about the persistent revolutionary struggle between the masses and their oppressors. The masses are educated on the importance of cooperation for a revolutionary change. If bees assemble as a swarm, nobody can wait for it. This can be seen as an analogical comparison of the masses with a swarm of bees and that as a swarm of bees the capitalists cannot face them.

Proverbs which are important weapons in customs, beliefs, thoughts and knowledge in Yorùbá society are utilized by some Yorùbá playwrights and some leaders of the masses in some plays in educating the masses. Proverbs are used in the society for advice, encouragement, explanation and reproach. Proverbs are used for encouraging the masses by leaders such as Láuwo in Réré Rún (p.30),

Adégún in Igbà Ló Dé (p.54), Lisabi in Lisabi Agbòngbò Akàlà (p 56) and Gòngòbíàgbà in Atàrí Ajànakú (p.30). We bring only some representative examples from Igbà Ló Dé and Atàrí Ajànakú. Adégún the 'Alága Ayé' says:

... Èyí fihàn pé àrùn tí n̄ ṣe ogóji ní n̄ ṣe ọ̀dún, ohun tí n̄ ṣe Abóyadé, gbogbo ọ̀lọ́ya ní n̄ ṣe (O.I. 54)

... This shows that the sickness that affects forty also affects three hundred, what affects Abóyadé also affects all the Qya people (p.54).

Gòngòbíàgbà says:

... Bì sòbia yóó bá di egbò, Olúgàbe làá ké sí
... A kíf bá ni tan, ká fa ni n'ítan ya
... (O.I.30)

... If guinea-worm pus wants to form a sore, we should send to 'Olúgàbe'
... We cannot say we are relations, when we tear one's thighs apart (p.30).

The excerpt above from Igbà Ló Dé shows that Adégún the 'Alága Ayé' advises the masses of Ògbojò not to fear

because all the masses are in full support of their revolutionary struggle against their oppressors. The masses are aware of the fact that they have a common enemy. All the masses of Ògbojò want freedom from oppression and they are not opposed to the revolutionary struggle (pp 54). In Àtári Àjànàkú, Gòngòbiàgbà uses the above excerpt to teach the masses how the oppressors should be warned to stop their oppression of the masses because the masses are prepared to revolt against their oppressive rule (pp 30-31). The above proverbial expressions are relevant for mobilising the masses in their struggles against their oppressors. The leaders in the plays mentioned above use these proverbs in showing the importance of cooperation in their struggles. These proverbs also emphasise the need for faithfulness and truthfulness in the private and public life of the masses. The leaders of the masses in these plays also use proverbs as a sort of encouragement to the masses. The masses are also educated on the disparity between them and their oppressors. They are encouraged and advised not to keep quiet but to do something about their oppressors. Proverbs are also used to enlighten the masses on the need for their support of their revolutionary

struggles. They should know that many people in the plays are being oppressed and they should be united to take part in a revolt against their oppressors. The masses are also educated about the need for hard work and effective work so that they will be able to plan well for their revolt without delay. The masses are also intimated about the atrocities perpetrated by the capitalist oppressors and also educated on the need for caution, tact, because not all the plans of the masses revolutionary movements could be discussed publicly. The masses are also educated to do something about the atrocities of the oppressors highlighted in these plays.

We shall now examine the implementation strategies used in educating the masses by the determined leaders of the masses.

4.3.2.4 Implementation Strategies Used in Educating the Masses

As we have seen above the resolute leaders of the masses use cooperative unions in their planning for the education of the masses in their revolutionary struggles. These unions are also used in their implementation strategies for educating the masses. Oládépò and Fàṣàkin in

Ayé Ye Wón Tán did not live to see the implementation strategies they had planned in the education of the masses by establishing 'ēgbé aláfowósowópo'. This 'ēgbé aláfowósowópò' are able to educate the masses and the townspeople in this play how to crush the capitalist oppressors. The revolutionary cooperative song that Fášakin taught them is used in mobilising and educating the masses on why a mass movement is necessary to crush the capitalists. The mass movement of workers, the peasants and all the townspeople singing the mobilising song:

Oyin şù;

Oyin n lẹ! ... (O.I. 90)

There is a swarm of bees;

The swarm of bees is moving! ... (p. 90)

shows how effectively they were mobilised by Oládépò and Fášakin at the planning stage of their revolutionary struggle.

Líşàbí in Líşàbí Agbòngbò Àkàlà in his educating the masses on the implementation strategy for their struggle changes the name of 'ēgbé àáró' to 'ēgbé

olórógun'⁷ (a warriors union). Lífàbí uses 'egbé olórógun' in a successful revolt by Ègbá masses against Ọlọ̀yọ̀ọ̀. The revolutionary educative folksong used in the implementation of a successful struggle is:

Ọ̀nì á gbóná jan jan jan
 Ọ̀lá á korò jogbó bí òro o
 Ọ̀nì á gbóná jan jan jan
 Ọ̀lá á korò jogbó bí òrò o
 Ogun Ọ̀lọ̀yọ̀ọ̀ r'ẹ̀run àjùlé o ...
 Ènì kónkó pa, àpagbé o (O.I. 90)

Today will be very hot
 Tomorrow will be as bitter as 'òro' fruit
 Today will be very hot
 Tomorrow will be as bitter as 'òro' fruit
 The Ọ̀lọ̀yọ̀ọ̀' s armies are crushed ...
 Those killed with batons are crushed for
 ever (p. 90)

This song is a mobilising song of the masses in their struggle against Ọ̀lọ̀yọ̀ọ̀. The masses are assured of their success in this folksong in a war they have not started. The masses in this play are indirectly educated in their 'egbé olórógun' with this folksong on the need to be

7 'Egbé Olórógun' (a warriors union or class) is comparable with Alááfin of Ọ̀yọ̀' s warriors or 'Eso Ikoyi' in the olden days Yorùbá society.

resolute in their revolutionary struggle against their oppressors. The playwright also educates the reading audience indirectly through *Líṣàbí*. The educating of the *Ègbá* masses about revolutionary activities may only be seen as an indirect teaching or educating the audience by using *Líṣàbí* as the active agent in the dramatic educating process. As we have already shown above we are brought into the middle, of the implementation strategy at the beginning of the play *Réré Rún* with a mobilisation song - "Èrò tí ñ ròjééje".

Èrò tí ñr'Òjééje, Òjééje;
 È wí fún iyáà mi, Òjééje;
 Èyin t'ó fi sílẹ̀, Òjééje;
 L'orogún sè f'òmọ̀ rẹ̀, Òjééje;
 Èwùrà t'ó kan bóbó, Òjééje;
 L'orogún sè, t'ó fún mi jẹ̀, eéje;
 Èrò tí ñr'Òjééje, Òjééje;
 Èrò tí ñr'Òjééje, Òjééje (O.I. 5)

Crowd (people) going to Òjééje, Òjééje;
 Help me tell my mother, Òjééje;
 The egg she leaves (behind for me), Òjééje
 Orogun (the co-wife) cooks for her child, Òjééje;
 A sour water yam, Òjééje;

Is cooked by the co-wife, for me to eat, eéje;
 Crowd (people) going to òjééje, òjééje;
 Crowd (people) going to òjééje, òjééje (p. 5)
 (As translated by Adéwólé 1987: 39-40).

This is the popular song of the masses in this play. Workers in the play sing it at every traumatic situation they find themselves. When the masses donate money for the release of Láuwo they sing this song (p.22). When Morèniké, Láuwo's wife, dies and the working masses go to bury her, they sing this song (p.85). They also sing this song at the end of the play when the working conditions of the workers become unbearable (p.96). This song is to educate the masses about the relationship between them and their capitalist oppressors as regards the distribution of wealth in the socio-political and economic system in the society. There are provisions for all men in the society but the capitalist oppressors in the society deprive the masses of the amenities and the wealth of the society. Onímògún and his chiefs who are the capitalists in this play are in charge of everything that belongs to the masses. They control the wealth of the society at the expense of the masses. This folktale song is educating the masses that they should do something about the capitalists who

cheat them. Since the song is an opening to the play we can say that it is used as a mobilising song for the revolutionary struggle of the masses. When the masses contribute and donate money for the release of Lawwo, they use this song in mobilising themselves to contribute willingly and when Lawwo's wife Morenik dies, the masses also use this song to mobilise themselves for active participation in the burial. Il (1981:400-401) and Adwl (1987:39) call this folktale song the workers' anthem, this is to show the importance of this song in the education and mobilisation of the masses in their revolutionary struggle in this play. This song also shows the relationship between the masses and those in authority who should act like good caretakers for the people. Our rulers who are in control of everything that is owned by the people in a society take the best of what is available and they leave those things which are less valued to the masses. The co-wife as used in this song represents the capitalist oppressors who are in control of the socio-political and economic situation of Mgn. The child represents the masses. The town of Mgn is naturally endowed with precious things by God.

The mother in this song represents God, while the precious things are comparable to an egg in the song. The sour water yam is the impoverished masses of Mògún and the crowd going to Òjééje in the song stands for the "socialist minded people of the world" (Adéwólé 1987:40). This folksong shows that the masses are cheated by their capitalist oppressors. The masses are educated by the use of this mobilisation song that they must do something as regards their oppressors so as to stop the cheating. Işòlá (1996:98) stresses the importance of dramatic language in folktales and how this is used as a major weapon of cultural socialization. Òkédijí in our view uses this folktale song as a weapon of educating the masses on revolutionary struggles.

The folksongs used in Igba Ló Dé by 'Ayé' in the implementation strategy as a weapon for educating and mobilising the masses in their revolutionary struggle are:

Ó n̄ polówó, à! ó n̄ polówó
 Èlékọ ọrun n̄ polówó ...
 Òkè Agidan ó j'ẹran,
 Òkè Agidan ó j'ẹran,
 Bí ọ bá rí t'Ológbojò

A mú ti woléwolé

Okè Agidan fẹ́ j'ẹran (O.I. 83)

He is hawking, ah! he is hawking
The heaven's grilled maize pudding seller is
hawking ...

Agidan hill will eat meat,

Agidan hill will eat meat,

If it can't find that of Ológbòjò

It will take that of the sanitary inspector

Agidan hill wants to eat meat (p. 83)

These are revolutionary songs specially created by the author and used by the people of 'Aye' to protest against their oppressors in their revolutionary developments. The songs are indirectly educating the masses on the end results of violent revolutions so that they may know and achieve their set goals and objectives of revolting against their oppressors and by completely destroying their oppressors in a revolutionary struggle. The songs are to educate the masses that there is a revolutionary situation and to awaken their revolutionary consciousness and arouse their determination for the revolutionary struggle. The idea of hawking in the songs and the eating of meat refer to death. When there is a successful

revolutionary struggle the oppressed in the society are destroyed. The songs show that Agidan hill will eat the meat of either Ológbojò or the sanitary inspector who may be killed during the revolutionary struggle of the masses against their oppressors.

Some determined leaders of the masses and some Yoruba playwrights are able to use folktales, folksongs, proverbs and Yoruba life and institutions in education for the conscientization of the masses as we have shown above. But all these devices are a part of literature which the Marxists see as a part of the superstructure used by the oppressors in legitimizing their domination. How then can Yorùbá authors use literature in the liberation of the oppressed? It is true that bourgeois literature according to Marxist literary critics is a weapon in the hands of the capitalists in the society to establish their oppression. Marxist literary critics however advocate the use of the same literature to wrest power from the oppressors. The views of "Socialist Realism", "Critical Realism" and the views of Mao (1950:120-121) are evidences that since the era of the development of Marxist literary theory in China and United Soviet

Socialist Republic, the socialist leaders had been calling on writers to educate the masses on how to organise revolutionary struggles of the masses against their oppressors. Craig (1975:i-vi) examines the views on 'Socialist Realism' and 'Critical Realism' and he asserts that a literary artist should be on the side of the masses.

We have shown in Chapter Three how some playwrights are able to create artistically from historical records. We have also shown the areas where the playwrights tilt to history. Only two historical plays Lisàbi Agbòngbò Akálà and Igbà Ló Dé are examined under inter-class struggle. Ládélé uses fictional characters in Igba Ló Dé. Only the events discussed in this play are historical. In Lisàbi Agbòngbò Akala, there are some historical characters such as Lisàbi, the Aláké and some chiefs. The name Qlòyòò (Bíòbákú 1957) is not the historical name of the Aláàfin who was involved in the incidents depicted in the play. Aláàfin Abíòdún was the Aláàfin who was mentioned in the historical accounts. The class struggles as depicted in these plays are the same with the historical accounts. The other plays such as Àtàrí Àjànàkú, Ayé Yẹ Wón Tán, Réré Rún and Kòseégbé are not

historical plays. Some of the playwrights examined are those who are committed to the cause of the proletariat. They are those who make attempts to see that the masses find ways of freeing themselves from oppression. They also believe in the ideology of a revolutionary change in their plays by establishing the power of the proletariat. If the masses in these plays are successful in their revolution because they are many and they are united, the oppressing few would definitely fail. But the minority oppressing class as we will show below possess all the instruments of coercion and alienation which they use for achieving their purposes. The playwrights therefore expose all these visions in their plays. We will now examine strategies adopted by the few oppressors in inter-class struggle.

4.4.0 Strategies of Oppression in Inter-Class Struggle.

Playwrights expose some strategies employed by the oppressing class for the benefit of the struggling members of their audience. If there is no cooperation among the oppressors the masses' struggle will result into a successful struggle. When there is a successful

revolution, the masses or the proletariat in Marxist literary critics view will form an alternative government. There will be a period of the dictatorship of the proletariat before the envisaged communism, which is the last stage of the development of a society. The capitalists in Yoruba plays cooperate in order to see that the revolutionary struggle of the oppressed classes does not succeed. There are ways by which the oppressors thwart the efforts of the oppressed. They use force and intimidation to frustrate the struggle of the masses. Our views are supported by Etzioni-Halevy's (1981:182) comments on the claims of Marxists and others that, it is actually the ruling elite or the ruling class that moulds the consent of the people to itself (the ruling class) so as to ensure its own rule. This view shows that consent descends from the top, and not ascending from the bottom to the top. In our modern societies those who hold power have often exercised this power in hidden ways. The power of the ruling elite or the capitalists in Yoruba plays is exercised in the following ways: maximization of the economic, political and social conditions, infiltration into the workers' ranks, terrorization and murdering of the leaders of the

oppressed class.

4.4.1 Maximization of the Economic, Political and Social Conditions

The capitalist oppressors in these plays are able to retain power because of the power they wield in maximizing the economic, political and social conditions in the plays. Some capitalists in these plays want to maximize the economic, political and social conditions for profit. They need money for their upkeep, therefore, the masses must be taxed and the excess money appropriated by them. They award contracts and they receive kickbacks from the contracts awarded. The capitalists enjoy the economic, social and political conditions at the expense of the masses in these plays. Plays that depict these views are: Ìgbà Ló Dé, Ayé Yẹ Wọ̀n Tán, Atàrí Ajà̀nàkú, Rẹ̀rẹ̀ Rún and Kòşẹ̀égbé. These representative examples from Ìgbà Ló Dé and Ayé Yẹ Wọ̀n Tán will suffice.

Ajẹlẹ: Tell the Ológbojò that because of the increased development and demands in the Division, the Alawani-in-Council find it expedient to increase the tax per head to five shillings this year. So the Ológbojò must make every tax

payer know this (p.43)

Ogbifò: Omíràn tún dé o. Ajèlè ní òun pàápàá pàtáki àti Aláwáni, Ikú bàbá-yèyè, ti fi owó kún owó orí yín ní ọdún ní. Sile mǎrùún ní ẹnì kọ̀ọ̀kan yóò san. Kí e kéde fún gbogbo àwọn tí ń dá owó orí ní ilú rẹ. Tí o bá si tún fẹ o, kí o má rí i pé gbogbo wọn l'ó dá a (O.I. 43).

The Resident in Igba Ló Dé, a representative of the British colonial administration increased tax from thirty five kobo to fifty kobo in Ògbojò. The colonial administration needs money for its upkeep, therefore the masses must bear the burden of taxation. Another example from Ayé Yẹ Wọn Tán is:

Oní: Olòṣi ọmọ àti bàbá iranù wọnyí sí fẹ́ ba aré òní jẹ́ fún mí. Ká má rí i (O.I. 53).

Oní: A useless daughter and her nauty father want to spoil today's party for me. It should not be allowed (p. 63).

When Ajé's firm wins a contract for the building of

an ultra-modern-hotel at Ipo, a luncheon party is arranged by Şiyabólá, Òní, Başòrun, Adédùn, Oyin and Ajé for the contractors. The poor masses are not invited. Òní one of the capitalist oppressors invites Òbílàdé's daughter who is a student at Ipo Grammar School to the luncheon party. Òbílàdé, a member of the poor masses goes to the venue of the luncheon party to forcefully take his daughter from Òní. In the excerpt above, Òní calls Òbílàdé a nauty father while he calls his (Òbílàdé's) daughter, a useless daughter. The above excerpt shows how the capitalists enjoy the socio-political and economic conditions at the expense of the masses. In order to achieve their aims and inordinate ambitions they do everything at their disposal to see that the masses are silenced.

4.4.2 Infiltration into the Workers' Ranks

The oppressors in some of the plays sponsor rival workers to break the revolutionary struggles. These sponsored rival workers help the capitalist oppressors in thwarting the efforts of the masses. This is an indication that the ruling elite actually moulds the people's consent to itself in order to ensure its

permanent rule in these plays. The oppressors in these plays infiltrate the ranks of the oppressed, break their solidarity and shatter their hopes. The oppressors do not come openly to destroy the revolutionary struggle of the masses. Secretely they sponsor characters who believe in establishing the status quo of the capitalists or ruling elite. They do not believe in the establishment of the power of the working classes or the poor masses. Examples of plays that depict infiltration of the capitalists into the workers ranks are Réré Rún and Àtárí Ajánakú. Ìdòwú is sponsored in Réré Rún as a rival union leader by Onímògún and his chiefs. Ìdòwú wants to destroy Lávúwo the acclaimed workers' union leader in order to make himself popular and consolidate his position among the workers. Ìdòwú plans with money doublers and Moréniké, Lávúwo's wife is duped. Moréniké in fear of Lávúwo's reaction commits suicide by taking an overdose of her headache medicine. The death of Moréniké is a shock to Lávúwo. This shock shatters his sanity. The insane Lávúwo cannot continue to be a union leader. Workers in this play are forced back to work after intimidation and coercion. Some of the workers are

retrenched and some like Mopélqlá resigned voluntarily because of frustration.

Arápáyagi is sponsored by the oppressors in Atàrí Ajanakú. In this play there is an initial successful struggle of the masses under the leadership of Gòngò-bíàgbà. The leadership of the struggling masses unite and eliminate members of the ruling elite of Gbáńdú including Baálẹ̀, Òsi, Ìyálóde and Sẹ́ríkí. Mábqlájẹ̀, Aláàfin's Ilàrí and Tẹ̀là escape from Gbáńdú. Immediately after the success of the struggle that leads to a revolt Gòngòbíàgbà establishes the power of the poor masses devoid of exploitation. This however does not last. The Aláàfin of Òyọ̀ craftly sponsors Arápáyagi to thwart this effort. The method employed by Aláàfin is a hidden one because we do not see any open interaction between the Aláàfin and Arápáyagi. We are only able to infer that the views expressed by Arápáyagi are those of the Aláàfin who crushes the revolt at Gbáńdú. Arápáyagi says:

Ẹyin náà lẹ ẹ tún un mọ

Ẹyin tẹ ẹ pèteperò

Tẹ ẹ wólé qlá

Ẹyin náà lẹ ẹ tún un mọ (O.I. 62)

You are the one to rebuild it
 You that planned and decided
 And pulled down royalty
 You are to rebuild it (p. 62)

4.4.3 Terrorization and Murdering of Leaders of the Oppressed Class

The capitalist leaders in some plays use terrorization and murdering of the leaders of the oppressed class in order to see that the masses struggle is crushed. Known leaders of the masses who are championing the struggle against the capitalist oppressors as constituted authority are frustrated, punished and in some instances killed as seen in the hidden inter-class struggle in Lísàbí Agbòngbò Akàlà where those who are opposed to the supremacy of Ọlọ́yọ́ and his Ilàrí in Ègbáland such as Ọdẹtúndé who is killed (pp 10-12), Mọ̀nìgbà who is forcefully taken away from her matrimonial home and taken to Ọ̀yọ́ as a wife for Ọlọ́yọ́ (pp 17-25). Two women are also forcefully taken from their husbands and their husbands who protested are killed by Ọlọ́yọ́'s Ilàrí (pp. 31-33).

The oppressors in these plays are afraid of the strong resistance of the oppressed against them. Some

leaders of the oppressed masses in Yorùbá plays are totally committed. They do not believe in any compromise. Where there are committed leaders of the oppressed, the oppressors use all possible means at their disposal to eliminate such leaders. They usually kill such committed leaders. Ayé Yẹ Wón Tán, Igbà Ló Dé and Líṣàbí Agbòngbò Àkàlà are plays that depict the killing of committed leaders of the masses by their oppressors. In some plays, hired assassins are used to kill the resolute and strong leaders of the oppressed as in Ayé Yẹ Wón Tán where the capitalist oppressors use hired assassins to kill Ọládépò Ọ̀jígí and Fásakin who are the strong and articulate leaders of 'egbé Aláfowosowopò' at Ipo. Ọládépò is killed in a public meeting of 'Egbé Aláfowosowopò' by gun men who are hired assassins as shown in:

Awon ọkúnrin nàà fetí ko ara won létí.
 Ọkan nínú wón sí nàka sí Ọládépò. Afi
 'kà!' tí a gbó. Ìbọn dún ní àyà Ọládépò.
 Ó pòòyì, ó ṣubú lulẹ, ó kú (O.I. 47)

The gun men whisper in each other's ears. One of them points to Ọládépò. We suddenly heard the sound 'kà!' (the booming sound of a gun). Ọládépò is shot in the chest. He

spins round, he falls down, he dies
(p. 47).

The death of Ọládépò does not deter the revolutionary struggle of the working classes in this play where Fáşakin is chosen as the new workers' leader. The capitalist oppressors in this play decide to kill Fáşakin on the day a party is organized for Ajé's contracting firm that is commissioned to build an ultra-modern hotel for the capitalists. The land to be used in building this hotel is the one forcefully taken from the workers cooperative union. The capitalists in this play send an invitation card to Fáşakin to lure him into the trap of the hired assassins:

Fáşakin: Ẹ gbà mí o, ọlọpàá o! ẹ gbà mí.
Wón fẹ́ẹ́ lọọ pa mí ni o.
Wón n̄ lọọ pa mí ni o.
Ọlọpàá, ọlọpàá!!! (O.I. 55)

Fáşakin: Please rescue me, policemen! rescue me.
They are going to kill me.
They are going to kill me.
Policemen, policemen!!! (p. 55)

When Fáşakin is killed there is tension in the town of

Ìpò. The people of Ìpò rise up and demand that the ọba of Ìpò and his capitalist chiefs should swear before the city divinity as a proof that they are not responsible for the killing of Ọládépò and Fáşakin. Şiyانبólá and his capitalist oppressors use hired assassins to thwart the efforts of the townspeople who ask him to swear before the town's divinity. The attempt by Şiyانبólá and his cohorts to rig the swearing ceremony fails and he and his accomplices are arrested. According to Ìşòlá (1981: 407), "this is an illustration of what the people themselves could do to save themselves". The events at the end of the play as shown above imply a final success for the masses.

After a successful revolutionary struggle of the masses of Ogbojò in Igba Ló Dé, the Resident uses the coercive power of the British Imperial Administration to eliminate all the recognised leaders of the masses in the play. This is to make the people realize that the authority of the colonial administration is superior to the authority of the masses.

Ajélẹ: Therefore, these five men will be hanged today just near the Ológbojò's house, over there (p. 99)

Ògbifò: Nítorí náà, ó ní a ó yẹgi fún àwọn
máràárún yíí lóníí ní ègbé ilé
Ológbojò níbèun (O.I. 99).

The recognised leaders of the struggling masses of Ògbojò who are killed include Jagun, Adégún, Júawo, Fákóredé and Fágbohùn.

The case of Líṣàbí in Líṣàbí Agbòngbo Akàlà seems to be different from the above cases. Líṣàbí led the masses in establishing 'ègbé àáró' and 'ègbé olórógun', so that Ọlọyọ́ and his Ìlárí who oppressed the Ègbá masses are crushed and Ègbá is freed. Líṣàbí the leader of the oppressed masses is killed by Aláké and his chiefs. Aláké and his chiefs who are the oppressors in Ègbáland may think that the masses may appoint Líṣàbí as an acclaimed leader and ruler after Ègbá's successful revolutionary struggle. Since we have established that there is a hidden inter-class struggle in this play, Líṣàbí who allys with the masses is killed with the cooperation of Ègbá chiefs such as Àrẹ̀gò, Jagùnnà, Lúkòsì, Olúwo and Aláké of Ègbáland. We assume that Aláké and his chiefs are oppressors in Ègbáland after the defeat of Ọlọyọ́. Jagùnnà says:

Òrò wo ni è ní gbọ́ lẹnu rẹ?
 È jòwọ́ ẹ pa alákorí rẹ
 Kí ẹ gbé òkú rẹ sínú kòtò yíí ...
 (O.I. 128-129)

Why are you listening to him?
 You should kill the silly idiot
 And dump his corpse in this pit ...
 (pp. 128-129)

As we have shown above, apart from killing the leaders of the masses, the capitalists in these plays also terrorize the masses. For example, Gòngòbíàgbà, Tọyọbọ, Ìgbàróọlá, Ayóméyẹ, Jẹnríyìn and Ariwoọlá in Atàrí Ajànakú (pp 88-123) are forcefully taken to the judgement throne of Aláàfin of Ọyọ to be punished, subdued and placed at the mercy of their oppressors. Ayànlọlá in Ayé Yẹ Wọ̀n Tán (pp 76-78) is subjected to inhuman treatment by Şiyanbọlá because of Ayànlọlá's refusal to drum at the birth-day celebrations of Adédùn, Şiyanbọlá's queen. In Réré Rún the insanity of Láwúwo may be attributed to the antics of Onímògún and his chiefs. Olúgbón says:

Èkejì ni pé ... bí Láwúwo ò bá gbà lẹrò,
 ǎ sì ba aiyé rẹ jẹ (O.I. 51)

Secondly ... if Lawwo refuses to accept our gentle plea, we will destroy him (p. 51).

We have shown how the oppressors use all possible means at their disposal to terrorize and eliminate the committed leaders of the masses.

4.5.0 Concluding Remarks

All the playwrights that depict inter-class struggle in their plays as we have shown in this work are against the exploitation of the masses. The authors are interested in the establishment of the power of the proletariat. They are playwrights who are committed to the cause of establishing a classless society. These plays are comparable with those which Jeyif (1985:47) describes as plays that examine the roles of workers, peasants, the urban and rural masses, their leaders and representatives in plays written in English language. Plays that are wholly interested in the establishment of the power of the masses are Rer Rn, Ay Y Wn Tn and Ksegb, while those that are partially interested in the establishment of the power of the proletariat are

Igbà Ló Dé, Atàrí Ajànakú and Lisàbi Agbòngbò Akàlà. The authors of Lisàbi Agbòngbò Akàlà, Igbà Ló Dé and Atàrí Ajànakú probably feel that it is not an easy task to change the status quo as we have shown in the views of Láuwayi Ògúnníran in this chapter, Igbà Ló Dé and Lisàbi Agbòngbò Akàlà may be merely presenting the real historical events of Iséyìn-Okèihò rising (Ògúnṣínà 1995) and the Ègbá revolt against the Òyó Empire (Bíòbákú 1957). The titles of these plays may also be suggestive of these views. Igbà Ló Dé (A change in time has come), may definitely mean that there is a change within the ruling elite when the colonial agents subdue the Yorùbá ruling elite. The struggle of the masses against the colonial and Yorùbá ruling elite does not succeed. The play may be merely presenting the integration of colonial administration with the Yorùbá administration through Lugard's indirect rule. The colonial and native rulers are all agents of oppression. Atàrí Ajànakú derives its title from a part of a Yorùbá proverb - "Atàrí Ajànakú kí í ṣerù òmòdé" (the head of an elephant is not a load to be carried by a small child). This title is in effect suggestive that the author of

this play is telling us that it is not an easy task for the masses in contemporary Yorùbá or Nigerian society to stage a successful revolt. This is because the masses have not got the awareness and consciousness for such a revolt. There is a need for education for the conscientization of the masses before such a revolt can be successful.

Even though the masses in Réré Rún are not successful we assume that the major interest of the author as Işòlá (1981:406) says, is to show the interest of the masses in revolutionary leaders such as Láuwo and to show the masses bitterness for reactionary forces such as Onímògún and his chiefs. Òkédíjì in not ending the play with a success for the masses, he wants the masses in Yorùbá society to be dissatisfied and be embittered about the actions of reactionary forces in the play so that they will be able to organise themselves and be able to free themselves from their capitalist oppressors. Òkédíjì is able to allow the sympathy of his readers to lie with Láuwo and his workers in this play. He is able to create a sort of consciousness in the masses in the society in this play.

In Işòlá's plays Ayé Ye Wón Tán and Kòşéégbé, the masses are victorious even though in reality in our present circumstances there is no victory for the oppressed. We can say that this is what the author wishes for the society. The playwrights who are wholly or partially committed to the cause of the masses want us to believe that the masses will one day in future take over from their capitalist oppressors if they are given the proper education on how to do this. These authors believe that literature in general and Yorùbá plays in particular should be used as a tool in propagating the ideology of the oppressed masses for a revolutionary change. If the masses are able to organise a successful revolt in Yorùbá society depicted in these plays, the idea of oppression, appropriation of the labour of the oppressed, and the idea of man's inhumanity to man may be eradicated.

Plays that depict intra-class struggle (as examined in Chapter Three) and inter-class struggle (in Chapter Four) in Yorùbá society may be out to teach their readers (audience) what exists in some human societies. If Yorùbá masses who are able to read these plays could

be well educated by the playwrights the masses may know and be able to decide the type of government that is better for them. Inter-class struggle as depicted by some Yorùbá playwrights is not a feature well developed in pre-colonial, colonial and contemporary Yorùbá or Nigerian society. This may be due to the individualistic tendencies of our pre-colonial, colonial and contemporary rulers who believe in accumulation of material wealth and in alienating the masses. Some characters who are the representatives and the leaders of the masses, and some events as depicted in these plays may not be realistic in Yorùbá society. For example, it will be very difficult to find people who act like Máko, Fáṣakin and Ọládépò in Yorùbá society. The idea of swearing before the town's deity in Ayé Yẹ Wón Tán may be a mere fiction of imagination in the contemporary situation. This is not to say that we may find a few people who can take up the responsibilities as leaders of the masses in the society. It may take a long time to see many committed leaders as depicted in these plays. The masses and oppressors as shown in these plays are mere literary creations of the authors. The masses in plays that depict inter-class

struggle have not taken the advantage of intra-class struggle to achieve successful revolts. This is because the capitalist oppressors or the ruling elite that usurp or are reaffirmed as rulers do everything possible to consolidate themselves. They also adopt new and coercive methods of oppression.

It is also observed that despite the powerful thrust of the artistic vision in the plays under reference, the playwrights seem to lack necessary awareness that could inform successful inter-class struggle in the plays. This is probably because of their lack of a socialist consciousness. Therefore this study validates the views of Marxists that bourgeois literature legitimises the ideologies of the ruling elite in a class society. By logical extension, the two categories of Yoruba plays we have identified above belong to bourgeois literature. In other words the Yorùbá playwrights seem not to have weighed the implications of a defeatist artistic vision on a society that seriously needs a drastic socio-economic and political re-generation.

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSION

5.0 Introduction

In this Chapter we attempt a summary of our findings. This include the relevance of the study to the society, the contribution to knowledge and suggestions for further research.

5.1.0 Summary of Findings

In this study we have examined the applicability of some Marxists critics views to Yorùbá historical and protest plays. The thematic contents of the plays that ally with the revolutionary struggles of the masses and those that ally with the capitalist oppressors in the society are examined. The oppression and exploitation of the masses and the poor working classes which lead to class struggles and revolutionary developments properly articulated in the plays are examined.

It is revealed in this work that some of the playwrights depict intra-class struggle which do not lead to a successful revolt of the oppressed masses. These intra-class struggle within the ruling elite establishes

the status quo. Plays analysed under this category include Basòrun Gáà, Qláòré Afótejoyè, Sàngó, Efúnsetán Aníwùrà, Morèmi, Olú Omq and Lisàbi Agbòngbo Akalà. These plays seem to show the contemporary aristocratic situations which many African nations are grappling with. According to Babáwálé (1990:9), one man rule and life presidency is established in many African countries. Military intervention in politics is institutionalised thus aggravating the problem of political instability rocking the continents ship since independence. Yorùbá playwrights seem to be expressing the views of one man rule in their plays with intra-class struggle. Even though these playwrights do not set out to illustrate socialist view, it is merely incidental in them. These plays have not successfully illustrated the Marxist literary critics' views about class struggle. Class struggle in these plays is shown not to be for the establishment of the dictatorship of the proletariat. Plays in this category are said to support the status quo, the ideology of divine rulership of kings and of the capitalists. Yorùbá historical plays are those that depict intra-class struggle. The plays in other words depict the social reality in contemporary Yorùbá or

Nigerian society.

Some of the plays are on the other hand also shown to present inter-class struggle between the oppressed and their capitalist oppressors. It is revealed that class struggle in such plays lead to revolts, revolutionary developments of the ideologies of the masses and commitment to the cause of the masses. In some of the plays there are counter-revolutionary struggles to crush some successful revolts, while in some other plays revolutionary struggles, ideologies and commitments do not lead to successful revolts. Ayé Ye Wón Tán, Lísàbí Agbòngbò Akàlà, Igbà Ló Dé, Atàrí Ajàràkú, Réré Rún and Kòseégbé are the plays that belong to this category of plays. They are the ones, in our view, that make use of Marxist literary theorists canons. They show their readers that they are conscious of the idea of man's inhumanity to man in Yorùbá society in particular and Nigerian societies in general.

Playwrights such as Iṣòlá, Okédèjí, Ládélé, Owólabí and Ògúnníran have successfully handled the matter of education of the masses for the purpose of conscientizing them towards ideological commitment to

their class struggle. These playwrights use education for the mobilisation of the masses for a successful struggle against their oppressors.

Our analysis also shows that all Yorùbá plays that depict inter-class struggle are protest plays. The plays in this category are seen as projecting into the future about what the Yorùbá society should look like. The vision of these playwrights is to re-assert the future classless society which is yet to materialise in our contemporary situation. The playwrights definitely do not present the reality in the society. They are just expressing their wishful visions. We may say they are the futurist playwrights.

The two classes discussed in our analysis are the oppressor class, the ruling elite or the capitalists and the oppressed, the working classes, the peasants or the masses. We are able to observe that the masses are mere participants in intra-class struggle because they are merely used as instruments by the ruling elite in their desire to establish the status quo. The study also reveals that in inter-class struggle both the masses and their oppressors are actively involved. The masses

in plays that depict inter-class struggle have not taken the advantage of intra-class struggle to achieve successful revolts. This is because the ruling elite that are re-affirmed as rulers do everything possible to consolidate themselves.

Our application of the Marxist literary theories in the analysis of intra-class and inter-class struggles in Yorùbá plays will help us immensely in our understanding of the sociology of Yorùbá plays in particular and the sociology of literature in general. This study has also enabled us to understand the more the place of intra-class struggle in the realisation of inter-class struggle. The capitalists in most cases are able to infiltrate the ~~rank~~ and file of the masses to break their solidarity and therefore establish their rule of oppression in inter-class struggle. There has not been a successful intra-class struggle because there is no masses party in reality in Yorùbá society. It is, however, discovered in this study that a perfect situation for a classless society is yet to materialise among Yorùbá playwrights. The reason is not far to seek, for a classless society is yet to manifest in the society.

This study thus validates the views of the Marxists that bourgeois literature legitimises the ideologies of the ruling elite. It seems as if Yorùbá playwrights merely use protest plays to create a sort of awareness and arouse consciousness of the masses for an envisaged masses revolt in future.

5.1.1 Suggestions

We are of the view that the masses in our society should take the weaknesses and the shortcomings observable in plays that depict intra-class and inter-class struggles in consolidating their plans for inter-class struggle thereby achieving a successful revolt and a change in governance. The masses should learn some lessons that are useful to their struggle from the work of arts that are committed to re-establishing the status-quo as in the case of the Yorùbá plays depicting intra-class struggle.

Our playwrights should face the realities of life by writing literary works that are committed to the cause of the masses in order to create a sort of awareness in them and arouse their consciousness. They should use Marxist

theories to help in educating the masses about the pre-colonial, colonial and the contemporary neo-colonial order in Yorùbá or Nigerian society and how they can unite to fight these reactionary forces who still support colonialism. They (the masses) should be taught that these reactionary forces took with one hand what they had formerly given with another hand. The colonialist make independence a farce. The intra- and inter-ethnic strifes in the society, elitist greed, nepotism, lack of political accountability in Nigeria on the part of the ruling elite (politicians, military), abuse of power, and governmental tyranny that is imposed on the masses by the civilian and military despots in power should be of interest to our playwrights. Our playwrights should see that the masses are well oriented in their struggle so that they will become the engineers of their own history and collective fate. The playwrights should gear their mass audience towards this line of thought and action. The masses should be taught through the Yorùbá plays that they should become the subject and not the object of development. They must struggle for a return to genuine socialist democracy where there will be

mass involvement, equitable distribution of wealth and socialisation and not the privatisation of productive forces in our economy. The masses must be taught that unless they help themselves nobody will help them out of the present socio-economic and political confusion. Yorùbá playwrights must teach the masses to learn correct lessons and collective struggle so that they will be able to overhaul the elitist educational system in our society. The educational system will be able to reflect the ideology of the masses on mass education. Onoge (1984:14) in his study of Marxism and literature asserts that, Marxist literary critics must be guided by the need to create alternative democratic structures where the masses can become creators rather than passive consumers of art or literature.

We must be aware that, there is no theory, formalism, structuralism that is all embracing for our critical analysis of literature. The humanist aspect of Marxism (Craig 1975:13-14) and the relationship of literature to the society that produces it and the importance of literature as a symbolic criticism of social values and its concern with men and society (Ògúnfà 1987:20)

makes Marxist literary theory an important tool in our analysis of literature in general and Yorùbá historical and protest plays in particular in this study. Yorùbá historical and protest plays can be studied and understood by using Marxist literary theory as a product which is made up of an absolute entity within the ideological. Absolute is not a mere abstract essence of a man but is the whole world of the activities of men, the development of their sensibilities, their struggle for the control of nature, their ability to preserve and develop a material and spiritual heritage (Slaughter 1980:212-213). A society cannot remain stagnant, we are hoping for change from the passive masses seen in intra-class struggles to the active masses participation in inter-class struggles. The masses may refuse to fight in any revolt within the ruling elite. In contemporary Yorùbá or Nigerian society, the masses may refuse to support any coup-detat because military rule is an aberration. They should not listen to any announcement in our media houses (both print and electronic) by "I, Major or Brigadier ..."

Our hope is that Yorùbá playwrights should write plays that are on the side of the people and should note that there are two important struggles in the life of a

human being; the struggle with nature, and the struggle with other human beings for the control of the material produced from the struggle with nature. We hope the issues we have raised under items such as intra-class struggle within the ruling elite, inter-class struggle between two classes - the masses and the capitalists, ideology of establishing the power of the proletariat - the power of the masses, education for the conscientization of the masses and authors and characters commitments to the ideology of the ruling elite - the capitalists, should also be carefully examined by others. Others can examine more critically the issue of commitment in Yorùbá plays using Marxist literary theories. The position of òbas, obis, ezes, etc in Yorùbá and Nigerian society is another area of possible research by scholars. We hope the major topics listed above, which are the major topics examined in this study will generate further discussions, arguments and explanations that will further enhance the development of Marxist sociology of Yorùbá plays and as such keep the arguments and discussion alive and make them functional for literary criticism in general and sociology of Yorùbá plays in particular.

Class struggle in Yorùbá plays, the major focus in this study will definitely contribute extensively to our critical analysis of Yorùbá literature in general and to Yorùbá drama in particular.

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